

VALKYRIES

D7.6 Report of the use case: Slovakia-Italy

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1. Executive Summary

The aim of this document is to describe activities of VALKYRIES project task T7.6, which led to the execution of demonstration based on **Use Case (UC) 2 – Cross-border response to the disaster containing the spread of toxic substances.**

Exercise scenario creates the prerequisites for **multi-casualty incident (MCI)** as well as the emergency situation represents a cross-border threat. It reflects the need for collaboration of several responding units within response action, so the exercise was **multi-agency and also cross-border** oriented.

Scenario is based on real cases and issues Slovakia is facing with. Fire of landfill was chosen as one of the most often and tricky at the same time and placed close to the border with Austria. Due to the fact, that there is no partner from Austria, for the purpose of the project it is simulated, that it is the border with Italy (instead of Austria).

Implemented exercise served as tool to test selected tools, procedures and generally opportunities identified during the previous project activities. Evaluation and validation methodology was prepared within the project also and was applied. Captured data are used for dissemination and exploitation of the project results.

Figure 1 - VALKYRIES Use Cases

2. Identification

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Name of lead participant: ISEMI

Name of Contributors: All partners

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Details: This specification applies to the project VALKYRIES: Harmonization and Pre-Standardization of Equipment, Training and Tactical Coordinated procedures for First Aid Vehicles deployment on European multi-victim Disasters funded under the SU-DRS03-2018-2019-2020 (IA), subtopic 3 Grant Agreement of the Horizon 2020 (H2020) tendering conditions. This document describes the outcomes achieved when existing the VALKYRIES solutions in a real demonstration between Slovakia and Italy, as well as outlining the impact of the demonstration outcomes and end-user acceptance.

3. Introduction

VALKYRIES is a project that focuses on analysis of the current state of protocols, nomenclatures, technologies and procedures implemented by European first responders, to propose a series of pre-standardization and harmonization actions that would allow them to operate jointly in cross-border incidents. These harmonization proposals are implemented on a platform as reference integration. Their validity was demonstrated, while this document describes use cases 2 (UC#2).

With aim to prepare and implement the demonstrations (exercises) optimally standardized process was agreed between the related partners and all the steps was captured in document called **EXSPEC** (Exercise Specification, respectively DEMSPEC-Demonstration Specification). It was the crucial document for preparation and implementation of demonstration. Goal of this document was to summarize and prepare all the information related to demonstrations of stated UCs and necessary to implement them in effective manner with aim to present VALKYRIES elements on a relatively simple case before moving on to an extensive deployment. Data from this document are used here.

3.2. Justification

Gaps and needs of the end-users was analysed during the first project phase and set of the requirements was formulated. Situation on how are these gaps covered by different technological tools, systems and equipment, as well as by the operational procedures and common practice and last but not least also by training and education system together with mutual cooperation possibilities, all from cross-border, cross-sectorial and cross-hierarchical perspective. Subsequently the opportunities for harmonization and standardization were developed. Findings from this process is subject of evaluation and validation also via the demonstrations. Tested tools and opportunities are described in more detail in chapter 9.

3.3. Requirements compliance matrix

ID	Priority	Traceability with objectives	WBS Deliverables	Compliance	Results
REQ_BASE_T7.6_1	P1	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-4	D1.3 D1.16	REQUIRED	Data Management Plan (D1.3, D1.16, D1.17)
REQ_BASE_T7.6_2	P1	VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ4	D2.3 D2.8	REQUIRED	Architecture Design Document (D.2.8)
REQ_BASE_T7.6_3	P1	VALK-OBJ2 VALK-OBJ4	D7.6	REQUIRED	Architecture Design Document (D.2.8)
REQ_BASE_T7.6_4	P1	VALK-OBJ2 VALK-OBJ4	D7.6	REQUIRED	Architecture Design Document (D.2.8)

ID	Priority	Traceability with objectives	WBS Deliverables	Compliance	Results
REQ_BASE_T7.6_5	P2	VALK-OBJ2 VALK-OBJ4	D7.6	REQUIRED	Architecture Design Document (D.2.8)
REQ_BASE_T7.6_6	P1	VALK-OBJ2 VALK-OBJ4	D7.6	REQUIRED	After each UC execution questionnaires spread to feedback compilation from end-users (D7.5, D7.6, D7.7, D7.8)
REQ_BASE_T7.6_7	P1	VALK-OBJ2 VALK-OBJ4	D7.3	REQUIRED	System Validation and Evaluation (D7.3) Report of the Use case 2 (D7.6)
REQ_BASE_T7.6_8	P2	VALK-OBJ2 VALK-OBJ4	D7.6	REQUIRED	N/A (SIGRUN is not final product)
REQ_COM_T7.6_1	P2	VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-7	D2.3 D2.8	REQUIRED	Architecture Design Document (D.2.8), GLOBAL COP based on web
REQ_COM_T7.6_2	P1	VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-7	D2.3 D2.8	REQUIRED	Architecture Design Document (D.2.8) System Validation and Evaluation (D7.3) Reports of the Use Cases (D7.5-D7.8)
REQ_COM_T7.6_3	P1	VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-7	D7.6	REQUIRED	Architecture Design Document (D.2.8) System Validation and Evaluation (D7.3) Reports of the Use Cases (D7.5-D7.8)
REQ_COM_T7.6_4	P2	VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-	D2.3 D2.8	REQUIRED	Architecture Design Document (D.2.8)

ID	Priority	Traceability with objectives	WBS Deliverables	Compliance	Results
		OBJ-6 VALK- OBJ-7			
REQ_COM_T7.6_5	P1	VALK- OBJ-4 VALK- OBJ-6 VALK- OBJ-7	D7.6	RECOMMENDED	Architecture Design Document (D.2.8) System Validation and Evaluation (D7.3) Reports of the Use Cases (D7.5-D7.8)
REQ_COM_T7.6_6	P1	VALK- OBJ-4 VALK- OBJ-6 VALK- OBJ-7	D7.6	RECOMMENDED	Reports of the Use Cases (D7.5-D7.8)
REQ_COM_T7.6_7	P2	VALK- OBJ-4 VALK- OBJ-6 VALK- OBJ-7	D2.3 D2.8	REQUIRED	Architecture Design Document (D.2.8)
REQ_COM_T7.6_8	P2	VALK- OBJ-4 VALK- OBJ-6 VALK- OBJ-7	D7.6	RECOMMENDED	Architecture Design Document (D.2.8), GLOBAL COP based on web.
REQ_COM_T7.6_9	P2	VALK- OBJ-4 VALK- OBJ-6 VALK- OBJ-7	D7.6	RECOMMENDED	Architecture Design Document (D.2.8)
REQ_COM_T7.6_10	P1	VALK- OBJ-4 VALK- OBJ-6 VALK- OBJ-7	D2.3 D2.8	REQUIRED	Architecture Design Document (D.2.8), In the UC SIGRUN interoperated with iSafety C2.
REQ_COM_T7.6_11	P1	VALK- OBJ-4 VALK- OBJ-6 VALK- OBJ-7	D7.6	REQUIRED	Not implemented as it was not part of any selected opportunities.

ID	Priority	Traceability with objectives	WBS Deliverables	Compliance	Results
REQ_COM_T7.6_12	P2	VALK- OBJ-4 VALK- OBJ-6 VALK- OBJ-7	D7.6	REQUIRED	N/A (SIGRUN is not final product)
REQ_COM_T7.6_13	P2	VALK- OBJ-4 VALK- OBJ-6 VALK- OBJ-7	D7.6	REQUIRED	N/A (SIGRUN is not final product)

Table 1 – Requirements compliance matrix T7.6

4. Demonstration specification

4.2. References

This document is prepared based an in relation with:

- Project VALKYRIES, Number: 101020676 — Harmonization and Pre-Standardization of Equipment, Training and Tactical Coordinated procedures for First Aid Vehicles deployment on European multi-victim Disasters (Description of Action)
- requirements stated on Description of Action (DoA) of this project related to D7.6 Report of the UC #2: Slovakia - Italy
- D7.1 Testbeds and Evaluation Methodology
- D7.3 System Validation and Evaluation

4.3. General data

FULL NAME:	CROSS-BORDER RESPONSE TO THE DISASTER CONTAINING THE SPREADING OF TOXIC SUBSTANCES	
NICKNAME:	"MAGIC CLOUD"	
SERIAL NUMBER:	002	
LEVEL:	OPERATIONAL	
FORM:	LIVEX	
TYPE:	FX with the elements of TTX	
DATES:	21 – 22 June 2023	
AREA:	Training facility of MoI SR, Stupava, SLOVAKIA (GPS: 48°15'33''N, 16°58'58''E)	
OFFICER SCHEDULING AND CONDUCTING THE EXERCISE	Martin Kostolný	
EXERCISE DIRECTOR:	Zoran Benedikovič	
PLANNING OFFICER:	Pavel Matulay	
LOGISTIC OFFICER:	Beáta Korpesio	
EVALUATION DIRECTOR:	Meritxell Bassols Tayeda	
HOST INSTITUTION:	ISEMI with support of Department for Detection of Hazardous Substances and Environmental Crime, National Center for Specific Crimes, Presidium of the Police Force, Ministry of Interior of the Slovak republic	
PARTICIPANTS:	ISEMI HaZZ PPZ KChL RPZ	INDRA TASSICA PARTICLE AREU BDI USN

Table 2 – UC2 General Data

5. Overall requirements

5.2. General framework

The outcomes of technological, procedural and collaborative streams will converge in the VALKYRIES reference integrated platform (SIGRUN), evaluation and demonstration actions.

Activity is based on project Task 7.6 and shall cover the planning, implementation, integration, executing, analysis and reporting activities concerning the demonstration scenario: Reassessment toxic threats for cross-border regions in Europe It is considered as incident on the border between Slovakia and Italy. (For the needs of the project Italy is in position of neighbouring country even though in reality it is not so).

5.3. Relation to other demonstrations

The Demonstration “Magic cloud” represents UC2 and is one of the four different demonstrations within the project. Not all VALKYRIES elements are necessarily tested in this demonstration. Overlapping or missing parts will be subject to subsequent assessment and evaluation.

6. Demonstration aims and objectives

6.2. Demonstration aim

Organization of demonstration event involving multi-response (different responding units) including cross-border interaction in order to test added value of the VALKYRIES system.

6.3. Demonstration objective

EO1: Organize presentation for First Responders as a pre-exercise shaping platform for coordinated response of first responders to scenario “Magic Cloud”

EO2: Execute intervention action/response of First responders based on outcome of exercise plan

EO3: Provide extensive presentation of selected VALKYRIES tools/system to First responders.

EO4: Provide related First responders with outcomes of VALKYRIES system. Organize, conduct and evaluate intervention action/response of First responders using the benefits of VALKYRIES system in order tackle the scenario Magic cloud.

EO5: Provide conditions for evaluation of the added value of VALKYRIES system as the tool of improvements of End user capabilities

EO6: Disseminate the project outputs and support exploitation of the project results

6.4. Testing objectives

TO1: To evaluate and validate tools proposed by VALKYRIES project in almost real conditions and by team leaders of end-users,

TO2: To evaluate and validate standardization and harmonization opportunities proposed by VALKYRIES project by team leaders of end-users.

7. Operational scenario description

Scenario is the fundamental and basic part of exercise. It determines all the activities, procedures, forces and resources. It is recommended to use scenario based on real cases on one side, as well as scenario based on the real needs of the trainees.

Concerning UC2, the scenario is based on several real fires of landfills, especially the fire of plastic materials in the village Zohor, on 25.4.2019. This place is only 4 km away from the place of the exercise.

Figure 2 - Picture of landfill fire, Zohor, 25/4/2019¹

Figure 3 - Picture of landfill fire, Zohor, 25/4/2019²

Unfortunately, the actuality of this scenario was also confirmed by the fire that occurred on the exact day of the exercise. This event happened in company producing plastic products situated in village Rovinka, only 20 km away of the training area.

Figure 4 - Picture of plastic production fire, Rovinka, 22/6/2023

Figure 5 - Picture of the same fire, Rovinka, 22/6/2023

¹ <https://www.topky.sk/gl/582349/2389291/FOTO-ako-z-katastrofickeho-filmu--V-obci-Zohor-hori-vyrobn-hala-aj-skladka-odpadu>

² TASR, Jakub Kotian, <https://ipravda.sk/res/2019/04/25/thumbs/sr-zohor-poziar-hala-skladka-dym-plamene-clanokW.jpg>

Scenario is reflecting the need to present Multi-Casualty Incident (MCI). That is why the fire of polyurethane foams products is included. Toxicity of such a smoke and vapour is lethal, respectively highly hazardous³.

Scenario is also reflecting the need of multi-agency training and cooperation support. This was the requirement of the project and, at the same time, it is the need identified by the Slovak responders.

Last but not least, scenario creates threat with cross-border effects and conditions, when cross-border response action will be required. On the level of communication as well as on the level of request/ deployment of neighbouring country units.

SCENARIO:

The toxic cloud coming from the fire is threatening densely populated territory of Slovakia, as well as its border area. The plume containing isocyanates is spreading by wind. A large number of victims are reported to the hotline. Several different intervention units must be deployed.

Fire itself is not in a focus of the exercise. It is the search and rescue of victims. In addition, the first reconnaissance team identified suspicious chemical and similar material in various containers. The commission of a crime is very likely.

Effective communication and cooperation, as well as harmonized procedures are needed, including the view of the cross-border threat.

INTEL:

Private company operating landfill is storing different types of waste in large quantities. For unknown reasons, a fire broke out at this landfill.

Monday, 6:30 AM:

Explosion/fire in the private company storing different materials – waste dump – has been reported to emergency number 112. Cloud is spreading. Number of people have serious symptoms (vomiting, burning eyes, nose and throat, also respiratory problems) as well as mortal victims are possible.

Company is situated between the Stupava, Zohor and northwestern part of Bratislava - Devínska Nová Ves. Close to Morava River and the borders with Austria (for project purpose it is Italy).

Two dead persons have been identified so far, together with several injured. They are complaining of vision loss, burning eyes, nose and throat, difficulty to breath – this looks to be main cause of death.

It is cold weather, soft northeast wind (1 to 2 degree of Beaufort scale, direction 25°). It is highly probable that similar symptoms will occur in Devínska Nová Ves and in border area of Austria. Area of 50 km² have to be immediately secured and monitored.

³ <https://firesciencereviews.springeropen.com/articles/10.1186/s40038-016-0012-3>

Responders will have to use PPE. Contamination of persons have to be taken into consideration. Special (specific) FRS units – HAZMAT Teams and other related forces have to be deployed immediately.

There is reasonable apprehension that a crime may have been committed, related criminal police unit is deployed as well. Standard police is deployed automatically as well as EMS.

In meantime, number of emergency calls are being received from this area. People are afraid of the cloud, some of them report problems with breathing and burning eyes.

Area should be checked and monitored. Mobile Control chemical laboratory is asked for support.

More ambulances are required. Victims are very likely contaminated. It is necessary to manage removal of the wounded, because some hospitals reports admitting patient issues.

This is the starting line for entire Exercise.

8. Concept of the exercise (demonstration)

8.2. Phase I – Preparation

Preparation of the Exercise comprises all necessary administration and action which leads to successful session conduct. The non-exhaustive list critical of actions with expected achievements:

- **Initial coordination meeting** with Police and FRS (based on this meeting a number of follow-up meetings and communication was carried out with aim to reach particular points: Exercise coordination team established; Enviro/CBRN criminal police unit confirmed and responsible person appointed; Training area confirmed; participation of FRS confirmed and responsible person appointed; Involvement of EMS confirmed; KChL unit confirmed and responsible person appointed; Volunteers playing roles of victims are confirmed).
- **Initial Reconnaissance of Ex site** in Stupava (training field, briefing room, storage space, power and communication connectivity, etc.).
- **Invitation of practitioners, observers and other participants** (in this case, this was covered by exercise coordination team and VALKYRIES project meetings).
- **Managing of transportation** for entire event.
- **Managing accommodation and catering**
- **Dissemination and PR activities** (dedicated person confirmed, dedicated persons and processes within the project consortium confirmed, preparation of communication channels)
- **Procurement of material for exercise** (list of material confirmed, processes agreed)
- **Final Reconnaissance of Ex site** in Stupava with heads of Responders Units (agreement on the exercise plan, confirmation of partial activities and all the details)
- **Event registration**
- **Preparation of Info and registration Package** (for distribution even before event registration)
- **Ice-Breaker** and Cultural tour organization (social event before the exercise)

8.3. Phase II – Shaping – Technology and participants (intervention) preparation

The Shaping phase basically includes two necessary actives as:

- Preparation of trainees and
- Adjustment of VALKYRIES technology on site.

Both, technical partners and trainees received initial briefing on Wednesday 21/6/2023, as well as the site tour, all in order to exploit all provided benefits of given infrastructure of training side in Stupava.

Briefing was implemented on Fire and Rescue Station “HS4 – Bratislava, Dubravka”. This station is specialized on HAZMAT incidents including spread of toxic material in air and represent the first unit on place of incident. All the responding units of next day exercise was present. Also, selected partner of VALKYRIES project.

As first, the project VALKYRIES was explained to the practitioners. Subsequently, the exercise scenario, place of incident, distribution of forces and means as well as expected course of the action (main points) was presented. Separate part was focused on descriptions of the tools to be tested. How the works, how to operate with them, what might be the added value for increasing of response action. Participants were familiarized with the process of how individual tools will be evaluated after the exercise.

The technical partners had allocated time for technology preparation and adjustments of particular components. They also had to develop simulation script and tools to set-up and run the UC2 scenarios.

Used application and solution in UC2:

- SIGRUN (implementation reference)
- ISAFETY
- GLOBAL COP
- Applications for digitalizing triage process
- TASSICA TB Bracelets
- TASSICA 3 triage cards

Additional tools were developed and used to run and set-up the UC3

- Victims' simulators
- Ambulance / vehicles / vessel assets simulators (routes and status)
- Set-up demo scenario scripts
- Events / Tasks simulators

8.4. Phase III – Conduct live exercise

The conduct phase is considered as the main part of the exercise and focuses on exploitation of selected capabilities of VALKYRIES system by First responders tackling the scenario.

Aim is to investigate the added value of VALKYRIES system and its particular subsystems for the benefit of First responders facing the same scenario where paramount features are effectivity, time and safety. At the same time, it was an opportunity to train joint response action on multi-agency and cross-border level.

Practitioners gone through the scenario and provided the response activities. Details are described in Annex C – UC2 implementation plan.

The key points of the exercise:

- **Incident commander post (IC post)** – improvised
 - in the close suitable room or outside (based on real weather and conditions)
 - IC is a firefighter
 - IC has at disposal team leader of FRS, EMS, Police
 - Communication via TETRAPOL (C2), walkie-talkie (responders)
 - using papers / flipchart (no special equipment)
- **Nest of wounded** – improvised
 - outside tent / suitable room
 - managed by EMS representative
 - means of communication: TETRAPOL, mobile network (civil)

- **Crime scene**
 - separate space close to the fire
 - fire is not affecting this site
 - different containers with various substances
- **Decontamination site – responders**
 - build by FRS
 - dedicated to responders
- **Decontamination site – victims**
 - dedicated to the victims before leaving dangerous zone (build by FRS)
- **Command and Control post (C2) – improvised**
 - operation centre of 112
 - ways of communication: TETRAPOL (CoordCom), mobile network
 - improvised C2 – only VALKYRIES tools
 - partially experts from project and partially persons from SK responders (FRS, EMS)
- **VOST – simulated**
 - fictitious organization
 - pre-prepared messages coming to C2 in form of e-mails

The milestones of the exercise:

- Receiving an emergency call,
- Deployment of forces (basic sources and resources),
- Arrival of forces/unit(s),
- IC establishing,
- Decontamination prepared,
- Reconnaissance (including measurements and detection),
- Reporting (METHANE),
- SAR (search and rescue),
- Fire localization and extinguishing,
- Triage (different levels),
- Handing over and receiving the wounded,
- Transport of wounded,
- Take-over the situation by the police.

8.5. Phase IV – Evaluation (Brief description of the approach (algorithm and methodology) for validation and testing of the VALKYRIES results)

Within the first phase of the project activities, also document Testbeds and Evaluation Methodology (D7.1) was developed. This document describes the development and the conceptual design of the Testbed and the system which was used in the four use cases of the Valkyries project as well as the methodology for end users' validation of harmonisation opportunities, which was identified under the framework of the different Work Packages of the Valkyries project. These are described in chapter 9 below.

Separate part of the methodology is devoted to the evaluation. In simplified way, the evaluation is understood as the means to identify if a system, a tool, a procedure or players' performance has achieved predefined objectives or not. In an exercise-trial, evaluation has to be both end

user driven and technically oriented. End users are considered the first responders in the context of the Valkyries project, as it is related to disaster management and more specifically to first aid response. First responders are the final recipients, and the development of novel solutions is specifically designed to address their operational needs. Therefore, their point of view is of utmost importance to assess whether or not a solution has practical value.

The core point of the evaluation process is the division between the technical verification and the end user validation. Technical verification is not in the scope of this document. Validation process examines the solutions in terms of effectiveness, efficiency and satisfaction, thus in terms of their overall acceptance by end users. Evaluation of the exercise and particular tested objects was provided by the pre-prepared surveys / evaluation forms (Annex B).

9. VALKYRIES Integrated System

Valkyries project produced number of harmonization proposals and developed a platform as reference integration. Validity of selected ones was demonstrated in exercise based on Use Case 2. Brief description of tools used are described in “D7.3 System Verification and Evaluation v.A/1.Annex F”

9.2. Global Technological Schema

This is the global schema for UC2 with the tools and command and Control configuration.

Figure 6 - UC2 Technological Scheme

iSafety was deployed in the Command Centre and was used to run the entire exercise in the C2 simulated (incident creation, resource allocation and vehicle status update). At the incident site, the application was used to digitise the triage process sending real-time data to SIGRUN. This medical data was visualised in both GLOBAL COPs.

The tools used for UC2 where iSafety, SIGRUN, GLOBAL_COP, an application for digitalizing triage process, TASSICA TB triage bracelets, TASSICA 3 Triage Cards and Blockchain encryption module (this module run on background – practitioners did not realize that).

Screenshots of the tools used during the UC2 for the execution of the exercise can be seen in Annex H.

10. Harmonization opportunities

10.2. WP4 harmonization opportunities

This section will provide an explanation of how the harmonisation of the opportunities assessed in UC2 has been carried out. A specific explanation of UC2 will be given.

The harmonization opportunities implemented for UC2 are the following

- **CO.WP4.42: Reduce voice communication, digitalising most information exchanges**
- **CO.WP4.21. Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms**

A detailed description is included in “D7.3 System Verification and Evaluation v.A/1.Annex F”

1.1.1. CO.WP4.42: Reduce voice communication, digitalising most information exchanges

For UC2, a simulated Valkyries control post is set up to simulate the Command and Control (C2) functions (incident creation, resource allocation) and additionally the headquarter is simulated with the global vision of the scenario provided by GLOBAL-COP and iSafety as a C2 tool that runs the exercise in parallel in the Valkyrie environment. For this UC the collaboration with Italy is carried out with the incorporation of the Italian FRs in the triage process. Unlike the other UCs, no additional Command Centres are created for Italy. Only medical data is shared in real time through the GLOBAL-COP.

In this scheme that comes from the initial architecture document [2]) which although a bit different from the global scenario defines well the interactions that are measured for this opportunity.

Figure 7 - Use Case 2 Interaction

In this use case, the interactions between the FRs responsible for the triage process and the simulated Valkyries test panel (Interaction 2 and 3 in the diagram) have been analysed. The exercise was carried out with traditional tools (radio communication) and with the tools provided by Valkyries (GLOBAL COP and Application for digitalizing triage process integrated in SIGRUN).

10.2.1. CO.WP4.21: Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms

This opportunity has an identical implementation and validation in the 3 UCs, therefore, it is described in “D7.3 System Verification and Evaluation v.A/1.Annex F”

10.3. WP5 harmonization opportunities

The opportunities resulting from the WP5 works that have been evaluated in the UC2 demonstrator are the following:

- **CO.WP5-1: Standardisation of terms in planning, preparedness and execution of the emergency response:** CO-WP5-1-D01 - VALKYRIES collaborative glossary for the response planning, preparedness and execution of Project UCs.
- **CO.WP5-7: Harmonization of operating procedures in emergency response:** Two enablers have been evaluated to the UC demonstrator to address this opportunity:
 - CO.WP5-7-1 Unification of triage priority coding and tagging in MCI and disasters at EU level: Use of unified casualties triage priority coding (VALKYRIES pentapolar coding) and tagging (colours) in the UC.
 - CO-WP5-7-2-D01 - TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims’ information register and traceability in MCI and disasters: Use and evaluation of the TASSICA 3 triage card in the UC.
- **CO.WP5-12: Standardization of information sharing in emergency response:** Use of the Emergency Medical Services Minimum Data Set (EMS MDS) as the standard for information exchange in UCs demonstrators.
- **CO.WP5-13: Establishing a common federated system for sharing information in emergency response:** Deployment and evaluation of SIGRUN as an integration reference to facilitate the deployment and response of emergency services in the UC demonstrator.
- **CO.WP5-3: Harmonization of alert and warning procedures in emergency response:** Adoption of the METHANE model for sharing the essential incident data between emergency services in the UC.

The assessment of the enablers in the UC3 demonstrator was carried out through the following verification actions:

- Questionnaires in the framework of the specific training actions of the UC3.
- Records made during the exercise: Collection (manually or automatically) of the information necessary to evaluate the MEs (mission success measures) and to determine whether or not the established KPIs (Key Performance Indicators) were met. These records were made
- On-line questionnaires at the end of the UC3 to collect the evaluation of the participants in the UC simulation.

A detailed description is included in “D7.3 System Verification and Evaluation v.A1/Annex F”.

10.4. WP6 harmonization opportunities – BDI

The selected opportunities were implemented in UC2

- **CO.WP6.2. Use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data**
- **CO.WP6.7: Use of Virtual Operation Support Teams (VOSTs)**

A detailed description is included in “D7.3 System Verification and Evaluation v.A/1.Annex F”

1.1.1. CO.WP6.2. Use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data

This opportunity has an identical implementation and validation in the 3 UCs, therefore, it is described in “D7.3 System Verification and Evaluation v.A/1.Annex F”

10.4.1. CO.WP6.7: Use of Virtual Operations Support Teams (VOSTs)

VOST in nutshell is and unit of trusted agents who cooperates with national emergency management agency. One of the main goals is to do social media (SM) analytics during extraordinary events / disasters and provide verified information to the responders.

In principle, SM have been identified as source of valuable information. The use is twofold:

1. Extracting and exploitation of information on SM.
2. Utilization of SM for providing information to the public.

Current opportunity is related to the first option. For UC2 exercise it was assumed that VOST team exists in Slovakia that SM was analysed during the first hours of incident and extracted and verified findings are provided to the C2. Messages was pre-prepared in advance.

Objective of testing was whether such an information can improve / support responders and improve response action.

Evaluation was carried out in form of questionnaire with the practitioners after the exercise.

More details also in “D7.3 System Verification and Evaluation v.A1/Annex F”,

11. Validation and testing – Analysis of the results

The results of the tests carried out for each opportunity are detailed below. Both the preliminary tests and the tests performed at the time of the exercise are described. The detailed description of each test performed is described in the verification and validation document D7.3[3] and the methodology in D7.1 [3].

In this section, the summary of the results obtained is reported and the analysis of these data is performed.

Annex E. WP4 Results, Annex F. WP5 Results and Annex G. WP6 Results reflect the result sheets and describes in more detail the tests performed for each WP.

11.2. WP4 Results

11.2.1. CO.WP4.28. Cross Border Data Trace

11.2.1.1. Preliminary Tests

The same tests as in UC1 and UC3 were repeated with no reported errors or problems

11.2.1.2. UC Results

The same results as in UC1 and UC3 were validated with no reported errors or problems

11.2.2. CO.WP4.42: Reduce voice communication, digitalising most information exchanges Results

11.2.2.1. Preliminary Tests

Several tests and verifications were performed prior to the UC and have been documented in “Annex E. WP4 Results”. All of them were performed remotely. The day before the simulation, a general communications test was performed to verify 4G coverage. The purpose of these tests was to verify that the pre-configured data was correct and that the integration with SIGRUN was working correctly.

To ensure the correct functioning of the tests, it is important that the applications have the corresponding URLs and APIs properly configured and that the master data of SIGRUN and the applications match. Most of the tests failed due to these configuration discrepancies.

This is the data structure and sequence of the exercise that has been verified in the tests. All actions and tasks performed by First Responders are created and updated in iSafety and shared through the SIGRUN platform.

In the case of UC2, the integrations had already been tested in the rest of the UCs and in this case the integrations with the API/URL and the static dataset of UC2 were mainly verified.

FORCES:			Personnel									
1	FRS	3 units	AH2S	EKOS	CAS	SAHS	Ambulance1	Ambulance2	police car	CBRN Van	Ambulance	(amb.)
2	PPZ	1 unit	1+3	1+2	1+2	1+1	1+2	1+2	2	3	3	3
3	SCM	1 unit + simulated FRS (C2)										
4	RZP	2 ambulances										
5	AREU	1 ambulance (only triage)										
6	VOST	simulated unit										
Mission			vehicles (and staff)									
delay	starting		FRS	RZP	PPZ	SCM	AREU					
	11:30 AM	emergency call	AH2S	EKOS	CAS	SAHS	Ambulance1	Ambulance2	police car	CBRN Van	Ambulance	(amb.)
0,05	11,35	deployment of forces	M1 - Control + M2 - Medical Support	Create + "On the Way"	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes			
0,20		arrival of forces	M1 - Control	"Active"	yes	yes	yes	yes				
		IC establishment										
	11,55	decontamination for responders										
		reconnaissance										
		firefighting										
		decontamination for victims										
	12,00	arrival of forces	M1 - Control + M2 - Medical Support	"Active"			Ambulance1	Ambulance2	police car			
	12,10	nest of wounded										
	12,10	reporting (METHANE)										
	12,12	deployment of forces	M3 - Control	Create + "On the Way"						yes	yes	
	12,15	pre-triage and deco of victims										
	12,20	triage (2 levels)										
	12,30	reporting (new/more victims)										
		request for more forces/deployment	M4 - Medical Support	Create + "On the Way"								yes
	12,40	firefighting completed	M1 - Control	"Resolved"								
	12,45	SaR completed				X						
	13,00	arrival of forces	M3 - Control	"Active"						CBRN Van	Ambulance	
	13,05	VOST information										
	13,15	measurements and sampling										
	13,30	arrival of forces	M4 - Medical Support	"Active"								(amb.)
	14,00	medical services completed	M2 + M4 - Medical Support	"Resolved"			X	X				X
	14,15	on-site activities completed										
	14,30	response action completed	M1 + M3 - Control	"Resolved"	X	X			X	X	X	

Figure 8 - data structure and sequence of the exercise

11.2.2.2. UC Results

TEST	Description	KPI	Results
CO-WP4-42-T03-Reduce Voice Communication	The test consists of verifying that the information update from SIGRUN is updated in real time in the Platform and the information is updated according to the central Database.	KPI 1: Time elapsed (since Incident is created in iSafety and registered in SIGRUN Database)	Not valid results.
		KPI 2: Time elapsed (since task is created in iSafety and registered in SIGRUN Database)	1,094 s
		KPI 3: Time elapsed (since asset is created in iSafety and registered in SIGRUN Database)	2,729s

Table 3 - COP-WP4-42_T03 Test results summary

Final results sheets with all the results are included in “Annex E. WP4 Results”

The general criteria for the KPI is as follows

- < 60 sec | 100% success
- Between 60 and 90 sec | 50% success
- Between 90 to 120 sec | 25% success
- > 120 sec | 0% success

As we can see the results are very positive and the centralisation and digitisation of the data with the SIGRUN platform provides information in real time with a standard communications environment.

With respect to the incident insertion metrics and once the data had been analysed, we found that for some reason the traceability with respect to incident insertion, but from the results of the values, it should be similar to the UCs. In this case there was only a single incident (unlike the rest of the UC's) and the data collected does not match the rest of the UC's or insertions and we do not consider it valid.

11.2.3. CO.WP4.21: Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms (UMU)

11.2.3.1. Preliminary Tests

To carry out this opportunity, the same processes have been carried out in the different use cases, the significant differences between them is whether or not there is simulated data and the amount of total data that has been obtained in each dataset. Specifically, for this UC there has been no simulated data and this is going to be noticed due to the scarcity of data in the dataset of this use case. The resulting dataset is composed of 264 real data samples and 0 simulated data samples. All the detailed information is in deliverable D7.2.

11.2.3.2. UC Results

TEST - 01	Description	KPI	Results
CO-WP4-21-T01- Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms	SIGRUN must be capable of integrating data from multiples sources, such as, specific data for each first responder during an emergency, allowing to analyse the data to create a trained model.	KPI 1: Adequacy: 90%	<i>Different data processing techniques have been applied to obtain the most important features, and then three Machine Learning models have been generated. The first one consists of predicting the second triage based on the data obtained in the first one. The second model predicts the patient's death after the first triage. The last model predicts the patient's worsening after the first triage. All information about the processing techniques and the generated models can be found in D.7.2.</i>
		KPI 2: Penalties in execution time: 5000 ms	

Table 4 - CO-WP4-21-T01 Final Results.

Results sheets with all the results are included in "Annex E. WP4 Results"

11.3. WP5 Results

See full results in Annex G – WP5 Result sheets opportunities

1.1.1. CO.WP5-1: Standardisation of terms in planning, preparedness and execution of the emergency response

CO-WP5-1-D01 - VALKYRIES collaborative glossary for emergency response planning, preparedness and execution: DEMONSTRATION			
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
Importance of all emergency services using a unified glossary to plan and respond to MCI and disasters	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 1: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by respondents.	Demonstration (questionnaire)
Verification action	Date and location	Bratislava (Slovakia), 22 June 2023.	
	Participants	Consortium and local partners' experts involved in UC2 previous organization tasks.	
	Analysis and results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> KPI 1: Importance: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) 	
	Quality	A, maximum adequacy (>90% compliance with the KPIs).	
	Result	Successful verification: YES	

Table 5 - Results sheet CO.WP5-1-D01

Evidence of implementation and compliance:

See Annex G – WP5 Result sheets Opportunities

11.3.1. CO.WP5-7: Harmonization of operating procedures in emergency response

11.3.1.1. CO.WP5-7-1 Unification of triage priority coding and tagging in MCI and disasters at EU level

CO.WP5-7-1-D01 - Unification of triage priority coding and tagging in MCI and disasters at EU level: DEMONSTRATION			
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
Relevance: Degree of importance attached to the use of a common classification and coding of victim priorities in a MCI.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 1: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration (questionnaire)
Stakeholder coding and labelling agreement: A	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL	KPI 2: A subjective favourable perception of	Demonstration (questionnaire)

CO.WP5-7-1-D01 - Unification of triage priority coding and tagging in MCI and disasters at EU level: DEMONSTRATION			
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	at least 80% by stakeholders.	
Cross-border cooperation improvement : The perceived improvement in cross-border cooperation between EMS when using a standardised classification and coding system.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 3: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration (questionnaire)
UC coding standardisation compliance: The degree of adherence in the UC to the standardised classification and coding of MCI victims proposed by VALKYRIES.	YES/NO (compliance = success).	KPI 4: The information related to the triage of victims in SIGRUN complies with the standardised classification and coding proposed by VALKYRIES.	Demonstration (questionnaire)
Verification action #1	Date and location	Bratislava (Slovakia), 22 June 2023.	
	Participants	Consortium and local partners' experts involved in UC2 previous training tasks.	
	Analysis and results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Relevance: 100% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 2: Stakeholder coding and tagging agreement: 100% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 3: Cross-border cooperation improvement: 100% (ACHIEVED) 	
	Quality	A: Maximum adequacy (>90% KPIs achieved)	
	Result	Successful verification: YES	

CO.WP5-7-1-D01 - Unification of triage priority coding and tagging in MCI and disasters at EU level: DEMONSTRATION			
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
Verification action #2	Date and location	Stupava (Slovakia), 22 June 2023	
	Participants	Bratislava Control Chemical Laboratory (Slovakia), Bratislava Emergency Medical Service (Slovakia), ENVIRO Department for detection of hazardous substances and environmental crime (Slovakia), Bratislava Fire and Rescue System (Slovakia), AREU Agenzia Regionale Emergenza Urgenza (Italy)	
	Analysis and results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 4: Coding compliance: YES (ACHIEVED) 	
	Quality	A: Maximum adequacy (>90% KPIs achieved)	
	Result	Successful verification: YES	
Verification action #3	Date and location	Online survey, 22 June 2023 and thereafter.	
	Participants	All participants in the UC2 drill.	
	Analysis and results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Relevance: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 2: Stakeholder coding and tagging agreement: 87,50% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 3: Cross-border cooperation improvement: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) 	
	Quality	A: Maximum adequacy (>90% KPIs achieved)	
	Result	Successful verification: YES	

Table 6 - Results sheet CO.WP5-7-1-D01

Evidence of implementation and compliance

See Annex G – WP5 Result sheets Opportunities

11.3.2. CO.WP5-7-2 TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in mci and disasters

CO-WP5-7-2-D01 - TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in mci and disasters: DEMONSTRATION			
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
Inter-rater reliability: The consistency in triage decisions among different first responders using the TASSICA triage card.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 1: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration (questionnaire)

CO-WP5-7-2-D01 - TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in mci and disasters: DEMONSTRATION

ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
Decision-making confidence: improvement in healthcare staff confidence in making triage decisions using the TASSICA triage card, as measured by self-reported score	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 2: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration (questionnaire)
Traceability: the extent to which the card helps to improve the traceability of victims throughout the chain of care at the scene of an MCI.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 3: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration (questionnaire)
Victim information completeness and accuracy: degree of ease of recording complete and accurate victim information using the TASSICA triage card.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 4: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration (questionnaire)
First responder wellbeing: The degree to which the card helps the	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY	KPI 5: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration (questionnaire)

CO-WP5-7-2-D01 - TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in mci and disasters: DEMONSTRATION

ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
first responder in their care tasks and reduces their stress during operations.	HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).		
Task execution efficiency: The reduction in time taken to perform tasks in an MCI compared to using other options, as perceived by first responders.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 6: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration (questionnaire)
Collaboration efficiency: The improvement in cross-border EMS collaboration, to coordinate and perform joint tasks using the TASSICA triage card, as perceived by first responders.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 7: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration (questionnaire)
Stakeholder satisfaction: The overall satisfaction of first responders with the TASSICA triage card.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 8: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration (questionnaire)

CO-WP5-7-2-D01 - TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in mci and disasters: DEMONSTRATION			
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
Time to triage: The average time taken to assign triage priorities using the TASSICA triage card.	Time (in seconds) from the victim first approach to the determination of triage priority and immediate actions.	KPI 9: A maximum acceptable average time to assign primary triage priorities: 1,5 min (90 sec).	Demonstration (functional validation)
Triage accuracy rate: The percentage of correct triage decisions made using the TASSICA triage card.	% (rate calculated by dividing the number of correctly triaged casualties by the total number of triaged casualties, expressed as a percentage).	KPI 10: Minimum 80% of correctly triaged casualties made using the TASSICA triage card.	Demonstration (functional validation)
Verification action #1	Date and location	Bratislava (Slovakia), 22 June 2023.	
	Participants	Consortium and local partners' experts involved in UC2 previous training tasks.	
	Analysis and results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Inter-rater reliability: 80,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 2: Decision-making confidence: 80,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 3: Traceability: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 4: Victim information completeness and accuracy: 80,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 5: First responder wellbeing: 90,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 6: Task execution efficiency: 80,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 7: Collaboration efficiency: 60,00% (NOT ACHIEVED) • KPI 8: Stakeholder satisfaction: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) 	
	Quality	A: Maximum adequacy (>90% KPIs achieved)	

CO-WP5-7-2-D01 - TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in mci and disasters: DEMONSTRATION			
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
	Result	Successful verification: YES	
Verification action #2	Date and location	Stupava (Slovakia), 22 June 2023	
	Participants	Bratislava Control Chemical Laboratory (Slovakia), Bratislava Emergency Medical Service (Slovakia), ENVIRO Department for detection of hazardous substances and environmental crime (Slovakia), Bratislava Fire and Rescue System (Slovakia), AREU Agenzia Regionale Emergenza Urgenza (Italy)	
	Analysis and results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 9: Time to triage threshold (TASSICA 3): 25,18 sec (ACHIEVED) • KPI 10: Triage accuracy rate (TASSICA 3): 100% (ACHIEVED) 	
	Quality	A: Maximum adequacy (>90% KPIs achieved)	
	Result	Successful verification: YES	

Table 7 - Results sheet CO.WP5-7-2-D01

Evidence of implementation and compliance:

See Annex G – WP5 Result sheets Opportunities

11.3.3. CO.WP5-12: Standardization of information sharing in emergency response

CO-WP5-12-D01 - Emergency medical services minimum data set (EMS MDS) for sharing information in MCI and disasters: DEMONSTRATION			
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
Data relevance: The perceived relevance of the data exchanged during the trial for proper management of casualties by EMS in an MCI or disaster	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 1: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration (questionnaire)
Data usefulness: The perceived usefulness of the exchanged data in the performance of care tasks	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 2: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration (questionnaire)

CO-WP5-12-D01 - Emergency medical services minimum data set (EMS MDS) for sharing information in MCI and disasters: DEMONSTRATION			
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
by first responders.			
Verification action #1	Date and location	Bratislava (Slovakia), 22 June 2023.	
	Participants	Consortium and local partners' experts involved in UC2 training tasks.	
	Analysis and results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Data relevance: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 2: Data usefulness: 77,78% (NOT ACHIEVED) 	
	Quality	D: Sufficient adequacy (50-59% KPIs achieved)	
	Result	Successful verification: YES	

Table 8 - Results sheet CO.WP5-12-D01

Evidence of implementation and compliance:

See Annex G – WP5 Result sheets Opportunities

11.3.4. CO.WP5-13: Establishing a common federated system for sharing information in emergency response

CO-WP5-13-D01- SIGRUN as an integration reference for facilitating the deployment and response tasks of emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: DEMONSTRATION			
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
Information exchange facilitation: The perceived improvement in information exchange between services using SIGRUN.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 1: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration (questionnaire)
Task execution efficiency: The perceived improvement in the efficiency of task execution in an MCI using SIGRUN compared to the current situation.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 2: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration (questionnaire)

CO-WP5-13-D01- SIGRUN as an integration reference for facilitating the deployment and response tasks of emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: DEMONSTRATION

ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
Integration and cooperation: The perceived improvement in integration and cooperation with other services and/or procedures in responding to an MCI using SIGRUN.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 3: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration (questionnaire)
Implementation ease: The perceived ease and simplicity of implementing SIGRUN by first responders in an MCI.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 4: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration (questionnaire)
First responder well-being: The perceived improvement in the well-being of first responders during their operational tasks in an MCI using SIGRUN.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 5: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration (questionnaire)
Added value in cross-border MCI management: The perceived added value of using SIGRUN for managing and	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 6: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration (questionnaire)

CO-WP5-13-D01- SIGRUN as an integration reference for facilitating the deployment and response tasks of emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: DEMONSTRATION

ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
responding to an MCI affecting several communities or countries.			
Satisfaction with information content: The overall satisfaction with the content of the information exchanged using SIGRUN.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 7: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration (questionnaire)
Satisfaction with the operating procedure: The degree of satisfaction with the operational procedure implemented and based on the capabilities offered by SIGRUN.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 8: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration (questionnaire)
Time to triage: The average time taken to assign triage priorities using SIGRUN.	Time (in seconds) from the victim first approach to the determination of triage priority and immediate actions.	KPI 9: A maximum acceptable average time to assign primary triage priorities: 1,5 min (90 sec).	Demonstration (functional validation)

CO-WP5-13-D01- SIGRUN as an integration reference for facilitating the deployment and response tasks of emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: DEMONSTRATION			
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
Triage accuracy: The percentage of correct triage decisions made using SIGRUN.	% (rate calculated by dividing the number of correctly triaged casualties by the total number of triaged casualties, expressed as a percentage).	KPI 10: Minimum 80% of correctly triaged casualties made during the MCI drill using SIGRUN.	Demonstration (functional validation)
Verification action #1	Date and location	Bratislava (Slovakia), 22 June 2023.	
	Participants	Consortium and local partners' experts involved in UC2 previous training tasks.	
	Analysis and results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Information exchange facilitation: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 2: Task execution efficiency: 88,89% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 3: Integration and cooperation: 44,44% (NOT ACHIEVED) • KPI 4: Implementation ease: 55,56% (NOT ACHIEVED) • KPI 5: First responder well-being: 88,89% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 6: Added value in cross-border MCI management: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 7: Satisfaction with information content: 77,78% (NOT ACHIEVED) • KPI 8: Satisfaction with the operating procedure: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) 	
	Quality	C: High adequacy (60-79% KPIs achieved)	
	Result	Successful verification: YES	
Verification action #2	Date and location	Stupava (Slovakia), 22 June 2023	
	Participants	Bratislava Control Chemical Laboratory (Slovakia), Bratislava Emergency Medical Service (Slovakia), ENVIRO Department for detection of hazardous substances and environmental crime (Slovakia), Bratislava Fire and Rescue System (Slovakia), AREU Agenzia Regionale Emergenza Urgenza (Italy)	
	Analysis and results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 9: Time to triage (SIGRUN): 69 sec (ACHIEVED) • KPI 10: Triage accuracy (SIGRUN): 90,91% (ACHIEVED) 	
	Quality	A: Maximum adequacy (>90% KPIs achieved)	

CO-WP5-13-D01- SIGRUN as an integration reference for facilitating the deployment and response tasks of emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: DEMONSTRATION			
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
	Result	Successful verification: YES	
Verification action #3	Date and location	Online survey, 22 June 2023 and thereafter.	
	Participants	All participants in the UC2 drill.	
	Analysis and results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Information exchange facilitation: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 2: Task execution efficiency: 87,50% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 3: Integration and cooperation: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 4: Implementation ease: 100,00% (ACHIEVED)KPI 5: First responder well-being: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 6: Added value in cross-border MCI management: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 7: Satisfaction with information content: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 8: Satisfaction with the operating procedure: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) 	
	Quality	A: Maximum adequacy (>90% KPIs achieved)	
	Result	Successful verification: YES	

Table 9 - Results sheet CO.WP5-13-D01

Evidence of implementation and compliance:

See Annex G – WP5 Result sheets Opportunities

11.3.5. CO.WP5-3: Harmonization of alert and warning procedures in emergency response

CO-WP5-3-D01- Standardisation of basic initial alerting information for emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: DEMONSTRATION			
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
Data relevance: Perceived importance of the data exchanged in the initial alert of a MCI or disaster to facilitate an efficient and effective emergency response.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 1: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration (questionnaire)
Data usefulness:	Score from 1 (VERY	KPI 2: A subjective	Demonstration (questionnaire)

CO-WP5-3-D01- Standardisation of basic initial alerting information for emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: DEMONSTRATION			
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
The perceived usefulness of the data exchanged during the drill in the initial alert to facilitate an efficient and effective emergency response.	LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	
METHANE UC compliance: The degree of adherence of the incident information shared in the UC to the METHANE model.	% (rate calculated by dividing the number of correctly shared METHANE data by the total METHANE dataset in the UC, expressed as a percentage).	KPI 3: A result of at least 80% of compliance.	Demonstration (functional validation)
Verification action #1	Date and location	Bratislava (Slovakia), 22 June 2023.	
	Participants	Consortium and local partners' experts involved in UC2 previous training tasks.	
	Analysis and results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Data relevance: 88,89% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 2: Data usefulness: 77,78% (NOT ACHIEVED) 	
	Quality	D: Sufficient adequacy (50-59% KPIs achieved)	
	Result	Successful verification: YES	
Verification action #2	Date and location	Stupava (Slovakia), 22 June 2023	
	Participants	Bratislava Control Chemical Laboratory (Slovakia), Bratislava Emergency Medical Service (Slovakia), ENVIRO Department for detection of hazardous substances and environmental crime (Slovakia), Bratislava Fire and Rescue System (Slovakia), AREU Agenzia Regionale Emergenza Urgenza (Italy)	
	Analysis and results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 3: METHANE UC compliance: 100% 	

CO-WP5-3-D01- Standardisation of basic initial alerting information for emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: DEMONSTRATION			
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
	Quality	A: Maximum adequacy (>90% KPIs achieved).	
	Result	Successful verification: YES	
Verification action #3	Date and location	Online survey, 22 June 2023 and thereafter.	
	Participants	All participants in the UC2 drill.	
	Analysis and results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Data relevance: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 2: Data usefulness: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) 	
	Quality	A: Maximum adequacy (>90% KPIs achieved)	
	Result	Successful verification: YES	

Table 10 - Results sheet CO.WP5-3-D01

Evidence of implementation and compliance:

See Annex G – WP5 Result sheets Opportunities

11.4. WP6 Results (BDI)**1.1.1. CO.WP6.2 Use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data****11.4.1.1. Preliminary Tests**

Details on the methodology and design of the demonstrations carried out can be found in Deliverable D7.3.

11.4.1.2. UC Results

TEST - 01	Description	KPI	Results
CO-WP6-1-T01- Use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data	Verify that the data stored in the SIGRUN platform is correctly stored, applying cryptographic mechanisms to ensure that only authorized access can access it. Also, the data transmitted over the network is secure.	KPI 1: Information available: Yes / No (Available = success)	<i>The results obtained are that the information is 100% available and that the data is exchanged encrypted over the network thanks to https. On the other hand, for the simulations, the option of encrypting the data in the database has been highlighted in order to speed up its operation, but this option can be activated at any time.</i>
		KPI 2: data transfer protocol configured to use encrypted communications : encryption setting	
		KPI 3: data is stored with in an	

TEST - 01	Description	KPI	Results
		encrypted format: encryption setting	

Table 11 - Results sheet CO.WP6-2-D01

The detail from the results sheets is included in Annex G.

11.4.2. CO.WP6.7: Use of Virtual Operations Support Teams (VOSTs)

11.4.2.1. Preliminary Test

To carry out this opportunity, simulated VOST messages was prepared in advance to the exercise. Integration of them was preliminary tested in lab conditions. This particular opportunity was subject of UC2 only.

11.4.2.2. UC Results

CO-WP6-7-D01- Use of Virtual Operations Support Teams (VOSTs) : DEMONSTRATION			
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
Potential exploitation of information shared on social media during an MCI or disaster to facilitate an effective and efficient emergency response for strategic and tactical level.	Percentage of agreement	KPI 1: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration
Potential exploitation of information shared on social media during an MCI or disaster to facilitate an effective and efficient emergency response for operational level.	Percentage of agreement	KPI 2: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration

CO-WP6-7-D01- Use of Virtual Operations Support Teams (VOSTs) : DEMONSTRATION			
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
Degree of consistency between information from VOST messages and that presented by the system.	% (rate calculated by dividing the number of correctly shared data by the total).	KPI 3: A result of at least 80% of compliance.	Demonstration
Verification action #1	Date and location	Bratislava (Slovakia), 22 June 2023.	
	Participants	Consortium and local partners' experts involved in UC2 previous training tasks.	
	Analysis and results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> KPI 3: VOST UC compliance: 100% 	
	Quality	A: Maximum adequacy (>90% KPIs achieved)	
	Result	Successful verification: YES	
Verification action #2	Date and location	Stupava (Slovakia), 22 June 2023	
	Participants	Bratislava Control Chemical Laboratory (Slovakia), Bratislava Emergency Medical Service (Slovakia), ENVIRO Department for detection of hazardous substances and environmental crime (Slovakia), Bratislava Fire and Rescue System (Slovakia), AREU Agenzia Regionale Emergenza Urgenza (Italy)	
	Analysis and results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> KPI 1: 92,50% (ACHIEVED) KPI 2: 90,00% (ACHIEVED) 	
	Quality	A: Maximum adequacy (>90% KPIs achieved).	
	Result	Successful verification: YES	

Table 12 - Results sheet CO.WP6-7-D01

11.5. Summary of stakeholders' feedback for the VALKYRIES solution and use case implementation

Exercise itself, as well as the selected tools and opportunities were the subject of research to what extent they have the potential to improve / increase the level of response action in case of MCI. The target audience was practitioners who participated in the UC2 exercise, so the feedback captured relates to the end-user perspective (it does not include the technical perspective). Namely, during the UC2 exercise, they were:

TOOLS

- GLOBAL COP (GC)
- iSafety C2 (iSC2)
- TASSICA 3 TRIAGE CARDS (TTC)
- Application for digitalizing triage process (TApp)

Findings are summarized and the level of satisfaction from the practitioners' point of view is as follows:

tool	Satisfactory
TApp	86,25 %
TTC	82,71 %
iSC2	86,55 %
GC	86,93 %

Table 13 - Satisfaction of practitioners with the UC2 tested tool

The conclusion is that the particular **tools are evaluated as effective and with the potential to improve response action.**

For more details, please see Annex D1.

OPPORTUNITIES

- **Triage process and its aspects**
- **METHANE reporting**
- **VOST**
- **Localization of near assets**
- **Cross-border sharing/trace of data**
- **Digitalising of data (focusing on reduction of voice communication)**
- **Wearables (for triage procedure)**

Feedback from the UC2 exercise participants is very positive. Almost all the replies were the best, respectively the second-best choices. This represents great commitment for next development with aim to incorporate the aspects into operational procedures for response in case of Multi Casualty Incidents, including cross-border events.

Conclusion is that identified opportunities have potential to improve response action.

For more details, please see Annex D2.

EXERCISE (itself)

Last, but not least, also the exercise itself was evaluated. The form of an online survey was used. Responders answered 12 questions. Within the main part (Q2- Q10) there were possibilities on scale of 5 options from the best to the poorest. Q10 was about general satisfactory. Q11 was more about impacts on self-improvement and Q12 is request for narrative contribution.

Average of the results are as follows:

best	55,2%
good	34,7%
moderate	7,9%
not good	2,2%
poor	0,0%

Table 14 - Evaluation of UC2 exercise

In addition, the overall satisfactory (Q10) reached values 70% for “great” and 30% for “satisfactory” (so all the participant vote for one of the first two options from five possible).

Conclusion is that the exercise was successful and fulfilled the expected objectives.

For more details, please see Annex D3.

12. Conclusions (Summary of the debriefing, recommendations and lessons learned)

Summarizing the discussions during preparation of the exercise, course of it as well as debriefing and evaluation, it is obvious that the exercise was effective. It met the project criteria, and covered the needs of end-users. The activity contributed to the practice of the required skills, the exchange of experience, the improvement of intervention in the case of presence of several units, the recognition of the most modern technologies and trends, and provide conditions for testing of the selected tools and identified opportunities.

Some minor recommendations have been captured. Of course, there is always room for improvements, but these issues were caused mostly by other limitations. Lessons learned indicates that the unexpected can happen and it is therefore advisable to have backup plans in place. In every case, everything is noted. For more details, please see Annexes D.

13. References and bibliography

1. **Consortium VALKYRIES** Deliverable "D4.3RoadMap for enhancing the pan-European technological capabilities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters"
2. **Consortium VALKYRIES** Deliverable "D2.8 Architecture Design Document"
3. **Consortium VALKYRIES** Deliverable "D7.3 System Validation and Evaluation"
4. **Consortium VALKYRIES** Deliverable "D7.4 Reference Integration and Lesson Learned Report"
5. **Consortium VALKYRIES** Deliverable "D7.1 Test Bed and Evaluation Methodology"

14. Annex A - Glossary

Acronym	Description
AHZS	Fire Rescue Service Car (FRS Technical Car)
C2	Command and Control (post)
CAS	FRS Water Tanker Truck (including deck gun)
COP	Common Operational Picture
CPT	Core Planning Team
DA	FRS Transport Vehicle
DoA	Description of Action (project)
EKOS	FRS HAZMAT Truck
EMS	Emergency Medical Service
EPG	Exercise Planning Group
EX	Exercise
EXCon	Exercise Control
EXSPEC	EXSPEC – Exercise Specification (also Demonstration Specification)
FER	Final Evaluation Report
FIR	First Impression Report
FR	First Responder
FRS	Fire and Rescue Service (firefighters)
FX	Field Exercise
GP	GLOBAL COP (one of the tools)
IOT	In order to
iSC2	iSafety C2 (one of the tools)
KChL	Control Chemical Laboratory (mobile one in this case - vehicle)
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LEMA	Local Emergency Management Authority
LIVEX	Live Exercise (also FX - Field Exercise)
NLT	Not later than
PTA	Primary Training Audience
RLS	Real Life Support
SAHS	FRS Ambulance
SAR	Search and Rescue
SO	Scenario Owner
STA	Secondary Training Audience
TA	Training audience
TApp	Application for Digitalizing Triage Process
TC	Test Conditions
TOs	Training Objectives
TP	Technical Partner

Acronym	Description
TPC	Technical partners coordinator
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TTX	Table Top Exercise (also CPX – Command Post Exercise)
UC	Use Case
VOST	Virtual Operations Support Team

Table 15 - Glossary

15. Annex B - FEEDBACK QUESTIONNAIRES

15.2. Annex B1 – QUESTIONNAIRE FOR THE EVALUATION OF THE EXERCISE (EN/SK version)

QUESTIONNAIRE FOR THE EVALUATION OF THE EXERCISE

DOTAZNÍK NA HODNOTENIE CVIČENIA

1. **According to your opinion, was the selection of a full-scale/table-top type of exercise adequate for the demonstration of the proposed solutions?** *Bol podľa vášho názoru výber súčinnostného typu cvičenia adakvátny na demonštráciu navrhovaných riešení*

Yes *Áno*

No *Nie*

Please, elaborate. *Prosím upresnite*

2. **Please rate your satisfaction as far as the preparation of the exercise is concerned (preparatory meetings, informative material, support for traveling logistics)** *Ohodnoťte svoju spokojnosť s prípravou cvičenia (prípravné stretnutia, informačný materiál, logistika)*

1-5 (1 poor—5 excellent) *(1 slabá – 5 vynikajúca)*

1	2	3	4	5
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Please, elaborate. *Prosím upresnite*

3. **Please rate your satisfaction on the training you received for the use of the proposed solutions in the exercise.** *Ohodnoťte svoju spokojnosť so školením, ktoré ste absolvovali na používanie navrhovaných riešení*

1-5 (1 poor—5 excellent) *(1 slabá – 5 vynikajúca)*

1	2	3	4	5
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Please, elaborate. *Prosím upresnite*

4. **To what extent was the scenario of the Use Case realistic and responding to a potentially real life emergency?** *Do akej miery bol scenár UC2 realistický a reagoval na potenciálne reálnu núdzovú situáciu?*

Not at all <i>Vôbec</i>	Limited <i>Obmedzene</i>	Moderate <i>Mierne</i>	Considerable <i>Značne</i>	Great <i>Veľmi</i>
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Please, elaborate. *Prosím upresnite*

5. **To what extent did the selected scenario showcase operational gaps in the response to a Multi-Casualty Incident and the added value that the proposed solutions bring in order to cover these gaps?** *V akej miere sa v vybratom scenári prejavili prevádzkové medzery v reakcii na ÚHPO a pridaná hodnota, ktorú navrhované riešenia prinášajú na pokrytie týchto medzier?*

Not at all <i>Vôbec</i>	Limited <i>Obmedzene</i>	Moderate <i>Mierne</i>	Considerable <i>Značne</i>	Great <i>Veľmi</i>
----------------------------	-----------------------------	---------------------------	-------------------------------	-----------------------

Please, elaborate. *Prosím upresnite*

6. **The extent, to which the objectives of the exercise i.e., effective exchange of information between different first responders and increased situational awareness for the agencies engaged in a MCI, are achieved.** *Rozsah, v akom sú dosiahnuté ciele cvičenia, t.j. efektívna výmena informácií medzi rôznymi zasahujúcimi jednotkami a zvýšená situačná informovanosť pre agentúry zapojené do ÚHPO.*

Not at all <i>Vôbec</i>	Limited <i>Obmedzene</i>	Moderate <i>Mierne</i>	Considerable <i>Značne</i>	Great <i>Veľmi</i>
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Please, elaborate. *Prosím upresnite*

7. **How would you rate the overall coordination of the exercise? Did the coordination facilitate the effective collaboration between the participants?** *Ako by ste ohodnotili celkovú koordináciu cvičenia? Uľahčila koordinácia efektívnu spoluprácu medzi účastníkmi?*

Poor <i>Slabo</i>	Inadequate <i>Nedostatočne</i>	Adequate <i>Dostatočne</i>	Good <i>Dobre</i>	Excellent <i>Výborne</i>
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Please, elaborate. *Prosím upresnite*

8. **How would you rate the logistics (location, venue, time, administrative support) of the exercise?** *Ako by ste ohodnotili logistiku (miesto, priestory, čas, administratívne zabezpečenie cvičenia)?*

Poor <i>Slabo</i>	Inadequate <i>Nedostatočne</i>	Adequate <i>Dostatočne</i>	Good <i>Dobre</i>	Excellent <i>Výborne</i>
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Please, elaborate. *Prosím upresnite*

9. **The extent, to which the timeline of the exercise was appropriately managed and followed the pre-defined schedule.** *Rozsah, v akom bol časový plán cvičenia riadený a dodržiaval vopred stanovený hramonogram.*

Not at all <i>Vôbec</i>	Limited <i>Obmedzene</i>	Moderate <i>Mierne</i>	Considerable <i>Značne</i>	Great <i>Veľmi</i>
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Please, elaborate. *Prosím upresnite*

10. **Overall, to what extent were you satisfied with the conduct of the exercise?**

Do akej miery ste boli celkovo spokojný s priebehom cvičenia?

Not at all <i>Vôbec</i>	Limited <i>Obmedzene</i>	Moderate <i>Mierne</i>	Considerable <i>Značne</i>	Great <i>Veľmi</i>
----------------------------	-----------------------------	---------------------------	-------------------------------	-----------------------

Please, elaborate. *Prosím upresnite*

11. **Your participation in the exercise, the implementation of tools and interaction with other stakeholders allowed you to increase your knowledge on innovative solutions and newly proposed methodologies that can be of added value for your operational work.**

Vaša účasť na cvičení, implementácia nástrojov a interakcia s ostatnými zainteresovanými stranami vám umožnili rozšíriť si znalosti o inovatívnych riešeniach a novonavrhaných metodológiách, ktoré môžu byť pridanou hodnotou pre vašu operatívnu prácu

Strongly disagree <i>Úplne nesúhlasím</i>	Disagree <i>Nesúhlasím</i>	Neutral <i>Ani súhlasím, ani nesúhlasím</i>	Agree <i>Súhlasím</i>	Strongly Agree <i>Úplne súhlasím</i>
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Please, elaborate. *Prosím upresnite*

12. **Please, indicate strengths and also areas that require improvement, to be considered for future exercises.** *Prosím, uveďte silné stránky a tiež oblasti, ktoré si vyžadujú zlepšenie a ktoré je potrebné zvážiť pri budúcich cvičeniach.*

15.3. Annex B2 – VALIDATION QUESTIONNAIRE (EN version)

QUESTIONNAIRE

FOR FEED-BACK SURVEY WITH RESPONDERS PARTICIPATING IN THE FIELD EXERCISE “MAGIC CLOUD”.

Dear Colleague,

You have just been participated in the field exercise carried out in the framework of the European project VALKYRIES which was at the same time demonstration based on Use Case 2 (UC2). This project aims to develop, implement and validate innovative technological solutions, operative procedures, education, training (E&T) and collaboration approaches in cross-sector and cross-border Multi casualty incidents (MCI – notice: in Slovakia also term “UHPO” is known in this meaning).

The role of this questionnaire is to receive feed-back evaluation from you of the demonstrated technological tools, operative procedures and E&T materials to improve collaboration among the first responders from different nations and different institutions.

We would like to ask you particularly to evaluate the VALKYRIES integrated solution named SIGRUN. This is a platform which integrates data from different sources and supports the Command and Control System (C2) in case of Multi casualty incidents (INDRA iSAFETY Application Modules for C2), visualizes the integrated data and creates a Common Operational Picture on both sides of the border (PARTICLE's Platform for Enhanced Situational Awareness and Secure Communications (GLOBAL COP) and provides digitalization of the triage (Application for digitalizing triage process), as well as traceability of the patients (TASSICA Triage Cards)

We strongly rely on your expert opinion to boost up the pre-standardization of the VALKYRIES project solutions at the EU level.

Thank you for your cooperation!

VALKYRIES Joint UC2 Team

General Information

Type of first responder's organization: *Fire&Rescue/Police/Medical....*

Role in organization:

Years of experience:

1. Please select which of the VALKYRIES solutions you have been using during the field exercise (multiple answers are possible).

	Yes	No
▪ INDRA: iSAFTY Application Modules for C2	1	2
▪ PARTICLE's Platform for Enhanced Situational Awareness and Secure Communications (GLOBAL COP)	1	2
▪ Application for digitalizing triage process	1	2
▪ TASSICA Triage Cards	1	2

2. We are suggesting you a series of statements. Please express your opinion for each of them choosing one of the answers on the scale.

Possible answers to the questions:

Strongly agree 5	Agree 4	Neither agree nor disagree 3	Disagree 2	Strongly disagree 1
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- 2.1. I think SIGRUN has been a very useful tool for my work.
- 2.2. I think SIGRUN has been a very useful tool for our organization.
- 2.3. Using SIGRUN makes it easier to manage Multi casualty incidents.
- 2.4. Using SIGRUN allows me to quickly manage Multi casualty incidents.
- 2.5. The use of SIGRUN is useful to correctly manage the Multi casualty incidents.
- 2.6. I am satisfied with SIGRUN to serve and manage the Multi casualty incidents.
- 2.7. Using SIGRUN makes it easier to manage Multi casualty incidents.
- 2.8. The use of SIGRUN increases the quality of Multi casualty incidents management.
- 2.9. I can manage the Multi casualty incidents correctly every time I use SIGRUN.
- 2.10. I feel comfortable with my SIGRUN ability.
- 2.11. Learning to operate SIGRUN is easy for me.
- 2.12. It is easy for me to be proficient in using SIGRUN.
- 2.13. SIGRUN gives error messages that clearly tell me how to troubleshoot.
- 2.14. Every time I make a mistake using SIGRUN, I recover easily and quickly.
- 2.15. The information (such as online help, on-screen messages and other documentation) provided with the SIGRUN is clear.
- 2.16. The end user requires significant training in order to successfully operate the proposed VALKYRIES project SIGRUN solution.

- 2.17. The operation of the proposed VALKYRIES project SIGRUN solution requires significant technical competence by the first responder to effectively use it.
- 2.18. The proposed VALKYRIES project SIGRUN solution can easily be integrated with other currently used technical systems and followed by your organization for the response to an Multi casualty incident.

3. To what extent the proposed SIGRUN solution facilitates the information sharing between different agencies involved in a cross-border Multi casualty incidents?

Great 5	Considerable 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1
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4. To what extent did you experience difficulties when using the proposed SIGRUN?

Great 5	Considerable 4	Moderate 3	Limited 2	Not at all 1
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5. How likely is you to suggest to yours first responder organization to adopt and use the proposed SIGRUN solution?

Extremely likely 5	Likely 4	Neutral 3	Unlikely 2	Extremely unlikely 1
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6. Does the proposed SIGRUN solution bring added value to the management of and response to cross-border Multi casualty incidents?

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderately 3	Little 2	Not at all 1
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7. Overall, are you satisfied with the functionalities of the proposed SIGRUN solution?

Greatly 5	Considerably 4	Moderately 3	Little 2	Not at all 1
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Question 8 – 11 are only for those responsible for the triage during exercise. If not, please continue with question 12.

UNIFICATION OF TRIAGE PRIORITY CODING AND TAGGING IN MCI (E.WP5-3)

Possible answers to the questions:

Strongly agree 5	Agree 4	Neither agree nor disagree 3	Disagree 2	Strongly disagree 1
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8. To what extend you agree or disagree that it is important that all emergency medical services use the same classification to designate the triage priority of victims in Multi casualty incidents?
9. To what extend you agree or disagree with the naming of the triage priorities used in the trial conducted?
10. To what extend you agree or disagree with the allocation of colours for the different priorities used in the test?
11. To what extend you agree or disagree that the use of the same classification and colour coding throughout the European Union would facilitate the joint work of emergency medical services in cross-border Multi casualty incidents?

INITIAL METHANE ALERT (E.WP5-7)

12. Do you think that the information conveyed in the initial incident statement test is appropriate for the needs of an emergency service in the first moments of an MCI or disaster?
13. Do you think that the METHANE reporting approach is useful for the needs of an emergency service in the first moments of an MCI or disaster?

USABILITY OF VOST (Virtual Operating Support Team)

14. To what extent do you agree or disagree that the VOST represent potential to improve response action on operational?
15. To what extent do you agree or disagree that the VOST represent potential to improve response action on strategic and tactical?

SIGRUN INFORMATION EXCHANGE PROCEDURE (E.WP5-6)

16. To what extent do you agree or disagree that the SIGRUN could facilitate the exchange of information between the different health services involved in the response to a Multi casualty incident?
17. To what extent do you agree or disagree that the localization of near (coming) vehicle/asset and its visualization might improve efficiency of response action in a Multi casualty incident compared to the current situation?
18. To what extent do you agree or disagree that the cross-border sharing/trace of data have potential to improve efficiency of response action in a Multi casualty incident compared to the current situation?
19. To what extent do you agree or disagree that digitalising of data (focusing on reduction of voice communication) have potential to improve efficiency of response action in a Multi casualty incident compared to the current situation?
20. To what extent do you agree or disagree that the wearables (for triage, for marking casualties, respectively for marking any other important things) have potential to improve efficiency of response action in a Multi casualty incident compared to the current situation?

Thank you for your cooperation!

15.4. Annex B3 – VALIDATION QUESTIONNAIRE (SK version)

DOTAZNÍK

PRE ZLOŽKY ZASAHUJÚCE V RÁMCI UC2 SLOVENSKO – TALIANSKO

PROJEKTU VALKYRIES V RÁMCI REAKCIE NA ÚHPO

Kolegovia,

Dnes ste sa zúčastnili spoločného slovensko-talianskeho cvičenia, ktoré sa uskutočnilo v rámci európskeho projektu VALKYRIES, ktorého cieľom je vyvinúť, implementovať a overiť inovatívne technologické riešenia, vzdelávanie, školenia (E&T) a prístupy spolupráce v medzisektorových, cezhraničných incidentoch s viacerými obeťami (ÚHPO). Väčšinou ide o udalosti, pri ktorých počet obetí ďaleko presahuje miestne zdroje a možnosti, ktoré zahlcujú miestny zdravotnícky systém, aspoň na určitý čas.

Úlohou tohto dotazníka je získať od vás spätnú väzbu o demonštrovaných technologických nástrojoch, operačných postupoch a materiáloch E&T na zlepšenie spolupráce medzi zasahujúcimi z rôznych krajín a rôznych inštitúcií.

Chceli by sme vás požiadať najmä o zhodnotenie integrovaného riešenia VALKYRIES s názvom SIGRUN. Ide o platformu, ktorá integruje údaje z rôznych zdrojov a podporuje C2 v prípade ÚHPO (aplikačné moduly INDRA iSAFETY pre C2), vizualizuje integrované údaje a vytvára spoločný operačný obraz na oboch stranách hranice (Platforma pre rozšírené situačné uvedomenie a bezpečnú komunikáciu PARTICLE (GLOBAL COP) a poskytuje digitalizáciu triedenia (Application for digitalizing triage process), ako aj sledovateľnosť pacientov (TASSICA Triage Cards). Pri podpore predstandardizácie riešení projektu VALKYRIES na úrovni EÚ sa veľmi spoliehame na váš odborný názor.

Ďakujeme za spoluprácu!

VALKYRIES UC2 tím

Všeobecné informácie

Typ organizácie:

Pozícia v organizácii:

Počet rokov praxe:

1. Vyberte, ktoré z riešení VALKYRIES ste použili počas spoločného slovensko-talianskeho cvičenia (viac odpovedí je možných)

	Áno	Nie
▪ INDRA: iSAFTY Application Modules for C2	1	2
▪ PARTICLE's Platform for Enhanced Situational Awareness and Secure Communications (GLOBAL COP)	1	2
▪ Application for digitalizing triage process	1	2
▪ TASSICA Triage Cards	1	2

2. Prosím vyjadrite svoj názor na nasledujúce vyhlásenia výberom jednej z možností.

Možnosti odpovedí:

Úplne súhlasím	Súhlasím	Ani súhlasím, ani nesúhlasím	Nesúhlasím	Úplne nesúhlasím
5	4	3	2	1

- 2.1. Myslím, že SIGRUN bol **pre moju prácu** veľmi užitočným nástrojom
- 2.2. Myslím, že SIGRUN bol **pre našu organizáciu** veľmi užitočným nástrojom
- 2.3. Používanie SIGRUN uľahčuje **riadenie ÚHPO**.
- 2.4. Použitie SIGRUN mi umožňuje **rýchlo riadiť ÚHPO**.
- 2.5. Použitie SIGRUN je **užitočné na správne riadenie ÚHPO**.
- 2.6. Som spokojný s tým, že SIGRUN obsluhuje a riadi ÚHPO.
- 2.7. Použitie SIGRUN zvyšuje **kvalitu riadenia** ÚHPO.
- 2.8. Zakaždým, keď použijem SIGRUN, dokážem správne riadiť ÚHPO.
- 2.9. Ovládanie SIGRUN je jednoduché
- 2.10. SIGRUN mi zobrazuje chybové hlásenia, ktoré mi jasne hovoria, ako problém vyriešiť
- 2.11. Informácie (ako napríklad online pomoc, správy na obrazovke a iná dokumentácia) poskytnuté so zariadením SIGRUN sú jasné
- 2.12. Koncový užívateľ potrebuje značné školenie, aby mohol úspešne prevádzkovať navrhované riešenie projektu VALKYRIES SIGRUN
- 2.13. Prevádzka navrhovaného riešenia projektu VALKYRIES SIGRUN si vyžaduje značnú technickú kompetenciu zasahujúcich, aby ho vedeli efektívne využívať.
- 2.14. Navrhované riešenie projektu VALKYRIES SIGRUN je možné jednoducho integrovať s inými v súčasnosti používanými tech. sys. a sledovať ho vašou org. pri reakcii na ÚHPO

3. Do akej miery navrhované riešenie projektu VALKYRIES SIGRUN uľahčuje zdieľanie informácií medzi rôznymi agentúrami zapojenými do cezhraničných ÚHPO?

Veľmi	Značne	Mierne	Obmedzene	Vôbec
5	4	3	2	1

4. Do akej miery ste sa stretli s ťažkosťami pri používaní navrhovaného riešenia projektu VALKYRIES SIGRUN?

Veľmi 5	Značne 4	Mierne 3	Obmedzene 2	Vôbec 1
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5. Aká je pravdepodobnosť, že navrhnete svojej organizácii, aby rpijala a používala navrhované riešenie projektu VALKYRIES SIGRUN?

Áno 5	Pravdepodobne áno 4	Ani áno, ani nie 3	Pravdepodobne nie 2	Nie 1
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6. Prináša navrhované riešenie projektu VALKYRIES SIGRUN pridanú hodnotu pre riadenie a reakciu na cezhraničné ÚHPO?

Veľmi 5	Značne 4	Mierne 3	Obmedzene 2	Vôbec 1
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7. Ste celkovo spokojný s funkčnosťou navrhovaného riešenia projektu VALKYRIES SIGRUN?

Veľmi 5	Značne 4	Mierne 3	Obmedzene 2	Vôbec 1
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Otázky 8-11 sú iba pre osoby zodpovedné za triedenie v rámci cvičenia. Ak ste nevykonávali triedenie, pokračujte na otázke č. 12

ZJEDNOTENIE PRIORITNÉHO KÓDOVANIA A OZNAČOVANIA V ÚHPO (E.WP5-3)

Možnosti odpovedí:

Úplne súhlasím 5	Súhlasím 4	Ani súhlasím, ani nesúhlasím 3	Nesúhlasím 2	Úplne nesúhlasím 1
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8. Do akej miery súhlasíte alebo nesúhlasíte s tým, že je dôležití, aby všetky záchranné zdravotnícke služby používali rovnakú klasifikáciu na určenie priority triedenia obetí pri ÚHPO?
9. Do akej miery súhlasíte alebo nesúhlasíte s vymenovaním priorít triedenia použitých vo vykonanom teste?
10. Do akej miery súhlasíte alebo nesúhlasíte s s pridelovaním farieb pre rôzne priority vo vykonanom teste?
11. Do akej miery súhlasíte alebo nesúhlasíte s tým, že používanie rovnakej klasifikácie a farebného kódovania v celej EÚ by uľahčilo spoločnú prácu záchranej zdravotnej služby pri cezhraničných ÚHPO?

Reportovanie metódou „METHANE“ (E.WP5-7)

12. Do akej miery súhlasíte alebo nesúhlasíte s tým, že údaje prenášané v rámci cvičenia sú vhodné na správne riadenie obetí záchrannou zdravotnou službou pri ÚHPO?
13. Myslíte si, že informácie poskytnuté v prvom teste vyhlásenia o incidente sú vhodné pre potreby pohotovostnej služby v prvých fázach ÚHPO?

POUŽITELNOSŤ VOST (Virtual Operating Support Team)

14. Do akej miery súhlasíte alebo nesúhlasíte s tým, že VOST predstavuje potenciál na zlepšenie činnosti na operatívnej úrovni?
15. Do akej miery súhlasíte alebo nesúhlasíte s tým, že VOST predstavuje potenciál na zlepšenie strategických a taktických opatrení?

POSTUP VÝMENY INFORMÁCIÍ SIGRUN (E.WP5-6)

16. Do akej miery súhlasíte alebo nesúhlasíte s tým, že by SIGRUN mohol uľahčiť výmenu informácií medzi rôznymi zdravotníckymi službami zapojenými do reakcie na ÚHPO?
17. Do akej miery súhlasíte alebo nesúhlasíte s tým, že lokalizácii blízkeho (približujúceho sa) vozidla a jeho vizualizácia môže zlepšiť efektivitu zásahu pri ÚHPO v porovnaní so súčasnou situáciou?
18. Do akej miery súhlasíte alebo nesúhlasíte s tým, že cezhraničné zdieľanie/sledovanie údajov má v porovnaní so súčasnou situáciou potenciál na zlepšenie účinnosti zásahu ÚHPO?
19. Do akej miery súhlasíte alebo nesúhlasíte s tým, že digitalizácia údajov (zameraná na redukciu hlasovej komunikácie) má v porovnaní so súčasnou situáciou potenciál na zlepšenie účinnosti zásahu ÚHPO?
20. Do akej miery súhlasíte alebo nesúhlasíte s tým, že nositeľné zariadenia (na triedenie, na označovanie obetí, resp. na označovanie akýchkoľvek iných dôležitých vecí) majú potenciál zlepšiť efektívnosť zásahovej činnosti pri incidente s viacerými obeťami v porovnaní so súčasnou situáciou?

Ďakujeme za vašu spoluprácu!

15.5. Annex B4 – FEEDBACK FORM for tools: Platform for Enhanced Situational Awareness and Secure Communications (GLOBAL COP) / iSAFETY C2 / TASSICA 3 TRIAGE Cards / Application for digitalizing triage process

General Information *(all optional)*

Všeobecné informácie *(dobrovoľné)*

Name *(Meno)*

Type of organization *(Typ organizácie)*

Role in organization *(Pozícia v organizácii)*

Years of experience *(Počet rokov praxe)*

Platform for Enhanced Situational Awareness and Secure Communications (GLOBAL COP) / iSAFETY C2 / TASSICA 3 TRIAGE Cards / Application for digitalizing triage process

(the same forms used for each of these tools)

Effectiveness *Účinnosť*

1. The proposed solution performed as expected according to the functions it was designed to.

Navrhované riešenie fungovalo podľa očakávania podľa funkcií, na ktoré bolo navrhnuté

Strongly agree <i>Úplne súhlasím</i>	Agree <i>Súhlasím</i>	Neither agree nor disagree <i>Ani súhlasím, ani nesúhlasím</i>	Disagree <i>Nesúhlasím</i>	Strongly disagree <i>Úplne nesúhlasím</i>
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2. The extent to which the solution assisted the completion of your tasks.

Určite mieru, do akej riešenie pomohlo pri plnení vašich úloh

Great <i>Veľká</i>	Considerable <i>Značná</i>	Moderate <i>Mierna</i>	Limited <i>Obmedzená</i>	Not at all <i>Žiadna</i>
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3. To what extent the proposed solution facilitates the information sharing between different agencies involved in a MCI.

Do akej miery navrhované riešenie uľahčuje zdieľanie informácií medzi rôznymi zložkami zapojenými do ÚHPO

Great <i>Veľká</i>	Considerable <i>Značná</i>	Moderate <i>Mierna</i>	Limited <i>Obmedzená</i>	Not at all <i>Žiadna</i>
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Efficiency *Efektívnosť* *(If applicable specific KPIs may be questioned)*

4. The proposed solution enables the faster implementation of your tasks in an MCI (Mass Casualty Incident).

Navrhované riešenie umožňuje rýchlejšiu implementáciu vašich úloh pri ÚHPO

Strongly agree <i>Úplne súhlasím</i>	Agree <i>Súhlasím</i>	Neither agree nor disagree <i>Ani súhlasím, ani nesúhlasím</i>	Disagree <i>Nesúhlasím</i>	Strongly disagree <i>Úplne nesúhlasím</i>
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5. The proposed solution enables the more successful implementation of your tasks in a MCI (Mass Casualty Incident) compared to the existing tools and conditions.

Navrhované riešenie umožňuje úspešnejšiu implementáciu vašich úloh pri ÚHPO v porovnaní s existujúcimi nástrojmi a podmienkami

Strongly agree <i>Úplne súhlasím</i>	Agree <i>Súhlasím</i>	Neither agree nor disagree <i>Ani súhlasím, ani nesúhlasím</i>	Disagree <i>Nesúhlasím</i>	Strongly disagree <i>Úplne nesúhlasím</i>
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Satisfaction *Spokojnosť*

6. To what extent did you experience difficulties when using the proposed solution?

Do akej miery ste mali ťažkosti pri používaní navrhovaného riešenia?

Great <i>Veľká</i>	Considerable <i>Značná</i>	Moderate <i>Mierna</i>	Limited <i>Obmedzená</i>	Not at all <i>Žiadna</i>
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7. To what extent the proposed solution is easy and simple to be used by a first responder? *Do akej miery je navrhované riešenie ľahké a jednoduché na použitie pre zasahujúcich?*

Great <i>Veľká</i>	Considerable <i>Značná</i>	Moderate <i>Mierna</i>	Limited <i>Obmedzená</i>	Not at all <i>Žiadna</i>
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8. The end user requires significant training in order to successfully operate the proposed solution. *Koncový používateľ potrebuje školenie, aby mohol úspešne prevádzkovať navrhované riešenie*

Strongly agree <i>Úplne súhlasím</i>	Agree <i>Súhlasím</i>	Neither agree nor disagree <i>Ani súhlasím, ani nesúhlasím</i>	Disagree <i>Nesúhlasím</i>	Strongly disagree <i>Úplne nesúhlasím</i>
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9. The operation of the proposed solution requires significant scientific and/or technical competence by the first responder. *Prevádzkovanie navrhovaného riešenia si vyžaduje značné vedeckú a/alebo technickú spôsobilosť zasahujúcich*

Strongly agree <i>Úplne súhlasím</i>	Agree <i>Súhlasím</i>	Neither agree nor disagree <i>Ani súhlasím, ani nesúhlasím</i>	Disagree <i>Nesúhlasím</i>	Strongly disagree <i>Úplne nesúhlasím</i>
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10. The proposed solution can easily be integrated and interoperates with other systems and/or procedures used/followed by your organization for the response to an MCI. *Navrhované riešenie je možné jednoducho integrovať a spolupracovať s inými systémami a/alebo postupmi, ktoré vaša organiz. používa/ktorými sa riadi pri ÚHPO*

Strongly agree <i>Úplne súhlasím</i>	Agree <i>Súhlasím</i>	Neither agree nor disagree <i>Ani súhlasím, ani nesúhlasím</i>	Disagree <i>Nesúhlasím</i>	Strongly disagree <i>Úplne nesúhlasím</i>
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11. Would you suggest to yours or other first responder organizations to adopt and use the proposed solution?

Navrhli by ste svojej alebo inej organizácii, aby prijali a použili navrhované riešenie?

Extremely likely <i>Áno</i>	Likely <i>Pravdepodobne áno</i>	Neutral <i>Ani áno, ani nie</i>	Unlikely <i>Pravdepodobne nie</i>	Extremely unlikely <i>Nie</i>
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Overall impact of the solution in its operational environment**Celkový dopad riešenia na jeho prevádzkové prostredie**

12. The proposed solution is expected to significantly enhance the well-being of the first responder during his/her operational duties.

Očakáva sa, že navrhované riešenie výrazne zlepši pohodu zasahujúcich počas jej/jeho operačných povinností

Strongly agree <i>Úplne súhlasím</i>	Agree <i>Súhlasím</i>	Neither agree nor disagree <i>Ani súhlasím, ani nesúhlasím</i>	Disagree <i>Nesúhlasím</i>	Strongly disagree <i>Úplne nesúhlasím</i>
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13. Are the victims' and first responders' personal data processed in any way by the use of the proposed solution?

Spracúvajú sa osobné údaje obetí a zasahujúcich nejakým spôsobom pri použití navrhovaného riešenia?

Extremely likely <i>Áno</i>	Likely <i>Pravdepodobne áno</i>	Neutral <i>Ani áno, ani nie</i>	Unlikely <i>Pravdepodobne nie</i>	Extremely unlikely <i>Nie</i>
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14. Do you expect that the operationalization of the solution requires its integration into a standardization or regulatory framework at organizational and/or national level?

Očakávate, že spravádzkovanie riešenia si vyžaduje jeho integráciu do štandardizačného alebo regulačného rámca na úrovni organizácie alebo národnej úrovni?

Extremely likely <i>Áno</i>	Likely <i>Pravdepodobne áno</i>	Neutral <i>Ani áno, ani nie</i>	Unlikely <i>Pravdepodobne nie</i>	Extremely unlikely <i>Nie</i>
--------------------------------	------------------------------------	------------------------------------	--------------------------------------	----------------------------------

15. Does the proposed solution bring added value to the management of and response to MCIs?

Prináša navrhované riešenie pridanú hodnotu pre riadenie a reakciu na ÚHPO?

Great <i>Veľmi</i>	Considerable <i>Značne</i>	Moderate <i>Mierne</i>	Limited <i>Obmedzene</i>	Not at all <i>Vôbec</i>
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16. Overall, were you satisfied with the functionalities and the use of the proposed solution?

Boli ste celkovo spokojní s funkciami a používaním navrhovaného riešenia?

Great <i>Veľmi</i>	Considerable <i>Značne</i>	Moderate <i>Mierne</i>	Limited <i>Obmedzene</i>	Not at all <i>Vôbec</i>
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17. Please, indicate key success factors of the implementation of the proposed solution.

Uvedte kľúčové factory úspechu implementácie navrhovaného riešenia

18. Please add recommendations for improvement for the proposed solution.

Pridajte odporúčania na zlepšenie navrhovaného riešenia

16. Annex C – UC2 implementation plan

IMPLEMENTATION PLAN

for execution of exercise related to the VALKYRIES UC#2

GENERAL DATA.

VALKYRIES is a project that focuses on analysing the current state of protocols, nomenclatures, technologies and procedures implemented by European first responders, to propose a series of pre-standardization and harmonization actions that would allow them to operate jointly in cross-border incidents. These harmonization proposals will be implemented on a platform as reference integration and, at the end of the project, their validity will be demonstrated in 4 cross-border and cross-sector use cases (UCs).

Goal of this document is to summarize and prepare all the information related to demonstrations of stated UCs and necessary to implement them in effective manner with aim to present VALKYRIES elements on a relatively simple case before moving on to an extensive deployment.

The data summarized in this document will also serve for other purposes and needs of the project.

FULL NAME:	CROSS-BORDER RESPONSE TO THE DISASTER CONTAINING THE SPREADING OF TOXIC SUBSTANCES
NICKNAME:	“MAGIC CLOUD”
SERIAL NUMBER:	002
LEVEL:	OPERATIONAL
FORM:	LIVEX
TYPE:	FX with the elements of TTX
DATES:	21 – 22 June 2023
AREA:	Training facility of Mol SR, Stupava, SLOVAKIA (GPS: 48°15'33''N, 16°58'58''E). Preparation in premises of FRS station No4, Bratislava – Dubravka, Saratovská st.
OFFICER SCHEDULING AND CONDUCTING THE EXERCISE	Martin Kostolný
EXERCISE DIRECTOR:	Zoran Benedikovič
PLANNING OFFICER:	Pavel Matulay
LOGISTIC OFFICER:	Beáta Korpesio
INCIDENT COMMANDER:	Ján Liberčan
EVALUATION DIRECTOR:	Merixell Bassols Tayeda

HOST INSTITUTION:	ISEMI with support of Department for Detection of Hazardous Substances and Environmental Crime, National Center for Specific Crimes, Presidium of the Police Force, Ministry of Interior of the Slovak republic	
PARTICIPATS:	ISEMI HaZZ PPZ KChL RPZ	INDRA TASSICA PARTICLE AREU BDI USN

TRAINING UNITS AND EQUIPMENT:

- SVK FRS, Unit HS Dubravka (12 persons) – confirmed
 - AHZS (1+3), EKOS (1+2), SAHS (1+1), CAS30 (1,2)
- SVK POLICE Unit – “Enviro/CBRN Department” (9 persons)
 - 2 persons as police securing order (1 personal car)
 - 3 + persons – CSI (reconnaissance and sampling, 1 van)
- SVK MEDICAL RESCUE (RZP, Martin Michalík, 2 ambulances)
 - 5 persons (at least, including one for IT team – 2 step procedure of triage)
- Control Chemical Laboratory (Milan Orolín + 2)
- Voluntary Fire & Rescue System Unit – 5 + 5 victims

SCENARIO SITUATION.

The toxic cloud coming from the fire is threatening densely populated territory of Slovakia, as well as its border area. The plume containing isocyanates is spreading by wind. A large number of victims are reported to the hotline. Several different intervention units must be deployed.

Fire itself is not in a focus of EX, but the first reconnaissance team identified suspicious chemical and similar material in various containers.

Effective communication and harmonized procedures are needed, including the view of the cross-border threat.

INTEL:

Private company operating landfill is storing different types of waste in large quantities. For unknown reasons, a fire broke out at this landfill.

Explosion/fire in the private company storing different materials – waste dump – has been reported to emergency number 112. Cloud is spreading. Number of people have serious symptoms (vomiting, burning eyes, nose and throat, also respiratory problems) as well as mortal victims are possible.

Company is situated between the Stupava, Zohor and northwestern part of Bratislava - Devínska Nová Ves. Close to Morava river and the borders with Austria (for project purpose it is Italy).

Two dead persons have been identified so far, together with several injured. They are complaining of vision loss, burning eyes, nose and throat, difficulty to breath – this looks to be main cause of death.

It is cold weather, soft northeast wind (1 to 2 degree of Beaufort scale, direction 25°). It is highly probable that similar symptoms will occur in Devínska Nová Ves and in border area of Austria. Area of 50 km² have to be immediately secured and monitored.

Responders will have to use PPE. Contamination of persons have to be taken into consideration. Special (specific) FRS units – HAZMAT Teams and other related forces have to be deployed immediately.

There is reasonable apprehension that a crime may have been committed, related criminal police unit is deployed as well. Standard police is deployed automatically as well as EMS.

In meantime, number of emergency calls are being received from this area. People are afraid of the cloud, some of them report problems with breathing and burning eyes.

Area should be checked and monitored. Mobile Control chemical laboratory is asked for support.

More ambulances are required. Victims are very likely contaminated. It is necessary to manage removal of the wounded, because some hospitals reports admitting patient issues.

AGENDA:

21st JUNE 2023 (Bratislava – FRS station No.: 4)		
8:00	8:30	Departure from Bratislava, arrival FRS station No.4, Address: Saratovská 3084/30, 841 02 Dúbravka.
8:30	9:00	Welcome, presentation of VALKYRIES, objectives
9:00	10:30	Presentation of tools (Application for digitalizing triage process, iSafety, ARATOS Bracelets)
10:30	10:45	Break
10:45	12:15	Presentation of technical parameters plus opportunities from WP4, WP5 and WP6 to be tested during the execution
12:15	13:15	Lunch break (on own preferences, proposals for restaurant will be provided)
13:15	16:00	Training – involving all positions of each emergency unit and follow all steps according to Exercise Specification document of UC2 Slovakia-Italy Possibility to visit exercise site (transport about 10 minutes)
16:00	16:30	Q&A
17:00	22:00	Guided tour, social dinner (TBC)
22nd JUNE 2023 (Stupava – Former Military Base)		
7:45	8:30	Departure from Bratislava, arrival to Stupava
8:30	11:00	Briefing and summarizing all necessary steps – implementation plan
11:00	11:30	Lunch (sandwiches)
11:30	14:30	UC2 execution – demonstration with application of VALKRIES project
14:30	16:00	Transport to FRS station 4 and Debriefing
16:00	17:00	Evaluation and analysing of VALKYRIES approach

EQUIPMENT – VEHICLES of units

Fire and Rescue System

- **AHZS** - Fire Rescue Service Car (FRS Technical Car)
 - 5 – 6 persons
 - reconnaissance, detection, marking of injuries/hazardous material/zoning
 - carrying out the wounded
- **CAS** - FRS Water Tanker Truck
 - 3 persons
 - water for the decontamination line
- **EKOS** - HAZMAT Truck
 - 3 persons
 - decontamination line, PPE, detection
- **SAHS** – FRS Ambulance
 - 2 persons
 - transport of injuries to the nest of wounded
 - partially decontamination of injuries
- **DA** - FRS Transport Vehicle
 - reinforcement unit

POLICE

- **standard police car**
 - 2 - 4 persons
 - securing order on the site
- **CBRN van**
 - 2 - 4 persons
 - PPE, detection, sampling...

EMS

- **RZP – EMS Ambulance**
 - 2 - 4 persons
 - triage, treatment, transport

CIVIL PROTECTION

- **Control Chemical Laboratory**
 - 2 - 4 persons
 - PPE, detection, sampling, analysis

POINTS

Incident commander post – improvised

- in the close suitable room
- IC is a firefighter
- IC has at disposal team leader of FRS, EMS, Police
- Communication via TETRAPOL (C2), walkie-talkie (responders)
- using papers / flipchart (no special equipment)

Nest of wounded – improvised

- outside tent / suitable room
- managed by EMS representative
- means of communication: TETRAPOL, mobile network (civil)

Crime scene

- separate space close to the fire
- fire is not affecting this site
- different containers with various substances

Decontamination site - responders

- build by FRS
- dedicated to responders

Decontamination site - victims

- build by FRS
- dedicated to the victims before leaving dangerous zone

C2

- ways of communication: TETRAPOL (CoordCom), mobile network
- improvised C2 – only VALKYRIES tools
- partially experts from project and partially persons from SK responders

VOST

- fictitious organization
- pre-prepared messages coming to C2 in form of e-mails

ACTIONS (MILESTONES)

- receiving an emergency call
- deployment of forces (basic sources and resources)
- arrival of forces/unit(s)
- IC establishing
- decontamination prepared
- reconnaissance (including measurements and detection)
- reporting (METHANE)
- SAR (search and rescue)
- fire localization and extinguishing
- triage (different levels)
- handing over and receiving the wounded
- transport of wounded

Evaluation will be carried out based on pre-pared forms in paper or online form.

COURSE OF THE ACTION:

Situation

Technological incident and release of the toxic plume. Number of people have serious symptoms and need immediate treatment. Toxic plume is heading to the densely populated part of the town as well as to close village in neighbouring country, right on the other side of the river. Due to the weather conditions, it is highly probable that toxicity will be serious even after at least 10 kilometres.

For research purposes there will be also injuries from the UC#1 – crash of the bus.

Area of Exercise and setup

17. Annex D – Results from the analysis of the questionnaire data (evaluation after exercise)

17.2. Annex D1 – Opportunities

VALKYRIES

UC2 after exercise feedback

Questionnaire for feedback survey with responders participating in the field exercise "MAGIC CLOUD"

Questionnaire for feedback survey with responders participating in the field exercise "MAGIC CLOUD" was part of the evaluation of the exercise related to UC2 implemented in Slovakia 21-22 June 2023. **This way the satisfaction of responders was expressed and captured.**

Objectives (how these elements can improve response action):

- SIGRUN platform (questions 2 – 7, including 18 sub-questions, and question 16),
- medical triage procedure and its aspects (questions 8 – 12)
- METHANE reporting procedure (question 13)
- VOST (question 14 and 15)
- localization of assets (question 17)
- cross-border data sharing (question 18)
- digitalising of data and reduction of voice communication (question 19)
- wearables (question 20).

There were 5 possible replies to every single question. Replies were quantified in a way that the first/best reply was multiplied by 5 and the last by 1 point. Summary of these results are stated in percentage (compared to the maximum possible points).

SIGRUN

Summary of replies for question 2 including 18 sub-questions leads to this result:

Strongly agree	62,10%
Agree	30,80%
Neutral	6,00%
Disagree	1,10%
Strongly disagree	0,00%

Figure 9 - Replies for questions related to SIGRUN

Questions 3 – 6 are more about external dependencies of SIGRUN. The last question (7) is about overall satisfaction and the replies are with double value.

Great/Extremely likely	45,45%
Considerable/Likely	42,42%
Moderate/Neutral	9,09%
Limited/Unlikely	3,03%
Not at all/Extremely unlikely	0,00%

Figure 10 - Replies for questions related to SIGRUN / External dependencies

Question 16 was about exchange of information between the response units (To what extent do you agree or disagree that the SIGRUN could facilitate the exchange of information between the different health services involved in the response to a Multi casualty incident?)

Strongly agree	55,60%
Agree	44,40%
Neutral	0,00%
Disagree	0,00%
Strongly disagree	0,00%

Figure 11 - Responses concerning SIGRUN as a facilitator of information exchange

CONCLUSION: SIGRUN works and has great potential to improve response action.

Triage process and its aspects

Summary of replies based on questions 8 – 12 representing how the proposed elements can improve triage itself

Strongly agree	72,58%
Agree	25,81%
Neutral	1,61%
Disagree	0,00%
Strongly disagree	0,00%

Figure 12 - Responses concerning triage process

CONCLUSION: Statements and findings formulated by project regarding triage procedure are correct and represent potential for improvement of response action.

METHANE

In area of reporting the situation on the site a METHANE method, as standardized procedure was discussed and tested. Results are as follows:

Strongly agree	59,60%
Agree	40,40%
Neutral	0,00%
Disagree	0,00%
Strongly disagree	0,00%

Figure 13 - Responses concerning METHANE method

CONCLUSION: METHANE procedure represents great potential for improvement of response action and it is recommended to use it in local Standard Operational Procedures (SOPs).

VOST

Topic on using of VOST message(s) was discussed and tested in simulated way. Feedback is as follows:

Strongly agree	78,95%
Agree	21,05%
Neutral	0,00%
Disagree	0,00%
Strongly disagree	0,00%

Figure 14 - Responses concerning VOST

CONCLUSION: Statements and findings formulated by project are correct and represent potential for improvement of response action.

Localization of near assets

Particular question to the audience was: To what extent do you agree or disagree that the localization of near (coming) vehicle/asset and its visualization might improve efficiency of response action in a Multi casualty incident compared to the current situation? Feedback are as follows:

Strongly agree	67,57%
Agree	32,43%
Neutral	0,00%
Disagree	0,00%
Strongly disagree	0,00%

Figure 15 - Responses concerning localization of near assets

CONCLUSION: Localization of near assets (vehicles, victims, equipment, etc.) creates conditions for improvement of response action. Accuracy and level of detailed information should be as precise as possible.

Cross-border sharing/trace of data

Particular question to the audience was: To what extent do you agree or disagree that the cross-border sharing/trace of data have potential to improve efficiency of response action in a Multi casualty incident compared to the current situation? Feedback are as follows:

Strongly agree	67,57%
Agree	32,43%
Neutral	0,00%
Disagree	0,00%
Strongly disagree	0,00%

Figure 16 - Responses concerning cross-border sharing/trace of data

CONCLUSION: Cross-border sharing/trace of data creates conditions for improvement of response action. Level of detailed information should be as precise as possible.

Digitalising of data (focusing on reduction of voice communication)

Particular question to the audience was: To what extent do you agree or disagree that digitalising of data (focusing on reduction of voice communication) have potential to improve efficiency of response action in a Multi casualty incident compared to the current situation? Feedback are as follows:

Strongly agree	55,56%
Agree	44,44%
Neutral	0,00%
Disagree	0,00%
Strongly disagree	0,00%

Figure 17 - Responses concerning digitalising of data

CONCLUSION: Digitalising of data (focusing on reduction of voice communication) creates conditions for improvement of response action.

Wearables (for triage procedure)

Particular question to the audience was: To what extent do you agree or disagree that the wearables (for triage, for marking casualties, respectively for marking any other important things) have potential to improve efficiency of response action in a Multi casualty incident compared to the current situation? Feedback are as follows:

Strongly agree	78,95%
Agree	21,05%
Neutral	0,00%
Disagree	0,00%
Strongly disagree	0,00%

Figure 18 - Responses concerning the use of wearables

CONCLUSION: Wearables (for triage procedure) creates conditions for improvement of response action.

CONCLUSION

Feedback from the UC2 exercise participants is very positive. Almost all the replies were the best, respectively the second-best choices. This represents great commitment for next development with aim to incorporate the tools, procedures and findings into operational procedures for response in case of Multi Casualty Incidents, including those containing cross-border aspects.

Feedback confirmed that identified opportunities have potential to improve response action.

17.3. Annex D2 – Tools

VALKYRIES

UC2 after exercise questionnaires evaluation of selected tools

During the UC2 Exercise implemented in Slovakia 21-22 June 2023, 4 tools proposed by VALKYRIES project was tested and at the same time evaluated using the pre-prepared questionnaire. It consisted from 16 questions (Q) plus 2 requests (R) for contributions. One and the same questionnaire was used for each tool.

The tools are:

1. Application for digitalizing triage process (TApp)
2. TASSICA Triage Cards (TTC)
3. iSafety C2 (iSC2)
4. GLOBAL COP (GC)

Questionnaires was enabled to the practitioners involved on exercise as well as to related project partners in paper as well as in online (google form) form. Here is the summary of the results:

Q1: Did the proposed solution performed as expected according to the functions it was designed to?

Possibilities to answer were divided on 5 levels, and the results are as follows:

Answer	TApp	TTC	iSC2	GC
Strongly agree	71 %	57 %	57 %	71 %
Agree	29 %	43 %	43 %	29 %
Neither agree nor disagree	0 %	0 %	0 %	0 %
Disagree	0 %	0 %	0 %	0 %
Strongly disagree	0 %	0 %	0 %	0 %

Table 16 - Responses for Evaluation of selected tools, Q1

Figure 19 - Responses for Evaluation of selected tools, Q1

Q2: The extent to which the solution assisted the completion of your tasks.

Possibilities to answer were divided on 5 levels, and the results are as follows:

Answer	TApp	TTC	iSC2	GC
Great	43 %	29 %	29 %	43 %
Considerable	57 %	57 %	57 %	57 %
Moderate	0 %	14 %	14 %	0 %
Limited	0 %	0 %	0 %	0 %
Not at all	0 %	0 %	0 %	0 %

Table 17 - Responses for Evaluation of selected tools, Q2

Figure 20 - Responses for Evaluation of selected tools, Q2

Q3: To what extent the proposed solution facilitates the information sharing between different agencies involved in a MCI.

Possibilities to answer was divided on 5 levels, and the results are as follows:

Answer	TApp	TTC	iSC2	GC
Great	57 %	43 %	43 %	57 %
Considerable	43 %	28 %	28 %	43 %
Moderate	0 %	29 %	29 %	0 %
Limited	0 %	0 %	0 %	0 %
Not at all	0 %	0 %	0 %	0 %

Table 18 - Responses for Evaluation of selected tools, Q3

Figure 21 - Responses for Evaluation of selected tools, Q3

Q4: The proposed solution enables the faster implementation of your tasks in an MCI (Mass Casualty Incident).

Possibilities to answer was divided on 5 levels, and the results are as follows:

Answer	TApp	TTC	iSC2	GC
Strongly agree	57 %	33 %	33 %	57 %
Agree	29 %	50 %	50 %	29 %
Neither agree nor disagree	14 %	17 %	17 %	14 %
Disagree	0 %	0 %	0 %	0 %
Strongly disagree	0 %	0 %	0 %	0 %

Table 19 - Responses for Evaluation of selected tools, Q4

Figure 22 - Responses for Evaluation of selected tools, Q4

Q5: The proposed solution enables the more successful implementation of your tasks in a MCI (Mass Casualty Incident) compared to the existing tools and conditions.

Possibilities to answer was divided on 5 levels, and the results are as follows:

Answer	TApp	TTC	iSC2	GC
Strongly agree	71 %	57 %	57 %	71 %
Agree	29 %	43 %	43 %	29 %
Neither agree nor disagree	0 %	0 %	0 %	0 %
Disagree	0 %	0 %	0 %	0 %
Strongly disagree	0 %	0 %	0 %	0 %

Table 20 - Responses for Evaluation of selected tools, Q5

Figure 23 - Responses for Evaluation of selected tools, Q5

Q6: The proposed solution enables the more successful implementation of your tasks in a MCI (Mass Casualty Incident) compared to the existing tools and conditions.

Possibilities to answer was divided on 5 levels, and the results are as follows:

Answer	TApp	TTC	iSC2	GC
Great	50 %	100 %	100 %	50 %
Considerable	16 %	0 %	0 %	16 %
Moderate	17 %	0 %	0 %	17 %
Limited	17 %	0 %	0 %	17 %
Not at all	0 %	0 %	0 %	0 %

Table 21 - Responses for Evaluation of selected tools, Q6

Figure 24 - Responses for Evaluation of selected tools, Q6

Q7: To what extent the proposed solution is easy and simple to be used by a first responder?

Possibilities to answer was divided on 5 levels, and the results are as follows:

Answer	TApp	TTC	iSC2	GC
Great	57 %	28 %	28 %	57 %
Considerable	14 %	14 %	14 %	14 %
Moderate	29 %	29 %	29 %	29 %
Limited	0 %	0 %	0 %	0 %
Not at all	0 %	29 %	29 %	0 %

Table 22 - Responses for Evaluation of selected tools, Q7

Figure 25 - Responses for Evaluation of selected tools, Q7

Q8: The end user requires significant training in order to successfully operate the proposed solution.

Possibilities to answer was divided on 5 levels, and the results are as follows:

Answer	TApp	TTC	iSC2	GC
Strongly agree	43 %	29 %	29 %	43 %
Agree	43 %	43 %	43 %	43 %
Neither agree nor disagree	0 %	14 %	14 %	0 %
Disagree	14 %	14 %	14 %	14 %
Strongly disagree	0 %	0 %	0 %	0 %

Table 23 - Responses for Evaluation of selected tools, Q8

Figure 26 - Responses for Evaluation of selected tools, Q8

Q9: The operation of the proposed solution requires significant scientific and/or technical competence by the first responder.

Possibilities to answer was divided on 5 levels, and the results are as follows:

Answer	TApp	TTC	iSC2	GC
Strongly agree	43 %	28 %	57 %	71 %
Agree	28 %	43 %	43 %	29 %
Neither agree nor disagree	0 %	0 %	0 %	0 %
Disagree	29 %	0 %	0 %	0 %
Strongly disagree	0 %	0 %	0 %	0 %

Table 24 - Responses for Evaluation of selected tools, Q9

Figure 27 - Responses for Evaluation of selected tools, Q9

Q10: The proposed solution can easily be integrated and interoperates with other systems and/or procedures used/followed by your organization for the response to an MCI.

Possibilities to answer was divided on 5 levels, and the results are as follows:

Answer	TApp	TTC	iSC2	GC
Strongly agree	43 %	43 %	43 %	43 %
Agree	43 %	57 %	57 %	43 %
Neither agree nor disagree	0 %	0 %	0 %	0 %
Disagree	14 %	0 %	0 %	14 %
Strongly disagree	0 %	0 %	0 %	0 %

Table 25 - Responses for Evaluation of selected tools, Q10

Figure 28 - Responses for Evaluation of selected tools, Q10

Q11: Would you suggest to yours or other first responder organizations to adopt and use the proposed solution?

Possibilities to answer was divided on 5 levels, and the results are as follows:

Answer	TApp	TTC	iSC2	GC
Extremely likely	57 %	29 %	29 %	57 %
Likely	29 %	57 %	57 %	29 %
Neutral	0 %	14 %	14 %	0 %
Unlikely	14 %	0 %	0 %	14 %
Extremely unlikely	0 %	0 %	0 %	0 %

Table 26 - Responses for Evaluation of selected tools, Q11

Figure 29 - Responses for Evaluation of selected tools, Q11

Q12: The proposed solution is expected to significantly enhance the well-being of the first responder during his/her operational duties.

Possibilities to answer was divided on 5 levels, and the results are as follows:

Answer	TApp	TTC	iSC2	GC
Strongly agree	57 %	43 %	43 %	57 %
Agree	43 %	28 %	28 %	43 %
Neither agree nor disagree	0 %	29 %	29 %	0 %
Disagree	0 %	0 %	0 %	0 %
Strongly disagree	0 %	0 %	0 %	0 %

Table 27 - Responses for Evaluation of selected tools, Q12

Figure 30 - Responses for Evaluation of selected tools, Q12

Q13: Are the victims' and first responders' personal data processed in any way by the use of the proposed solution?

Possibilities to answer was divided on 5 levels, and the results are as follows:

Answer	TApp	TTC	iSC2	GC
Extremely likely	43 %	14 %	14 %	43 %
Likely	43 %	86 %	86 %	43 %
Neutral	14 %	0 %	0 %	14 %
Unlikely	0 %	0 %	0 %	0 %
Extremely unlikely	0 %	0 %	0 %	0 %

Table 28 - Responses for Evaluation of selected tools, Q13

Figure 31 - Responses for Evaluation of selected tools, Q13

Q14: Do you expect that the operationalization of the solution requires its integration into a standardization or regulatory framework at organizational and/or national level?

Possibilities to answer was divided on 5 levels, and the results are as follows:

Answer	TApp	TTC	iSC2	GC
Extremely likely	43 %	29 %	29 %	43 %
Likely	57 %	71 %	71 %	57 %
Neutral	0 %	0 %	0 %	0 %
Unlikely	0 %	0 %	0 %	0 %
Extremely unlikely	0 %	0 %	0 %	0 %

Table 29 - Responses for Evaluation of selected tools, Q14

Figure 32 - Responses for Evaluation of selected tools, Q14

Q15: Does the proposed solution bring added value to the management of and response to MCIs?

Possibilities to answer was divided on 5 levels, and the results are as follows:

Answer	TApp	TTC	iSC2	GC
Great	57 %	43 %	43 %	57 %
Considerable	29 %	28 %	28 %	29 %
Moderate	14%	29 %	29 %	14%
Limited	0 %	0 %	0 %	0 %
Not at all	0 %	0 %	0 %	0 %

Table 30 - Responses for Evaluation of selected tools, Q15

Figure 33 - Responses for Evaluation of selected tools, Q15

Q16: Overall, were you satisfied with the functionalities and the use of the proposed solution?

Possibilities to answer was divided on 5 levels, and the results are as follows:

Answer	TApp	TTC	iSC2	GC
Great	57 %	29 %	29 %	57 %
Considerable	15 %	57 %	57 %	15 %
Moderate	14 %	14 %	14 %	14 %
Limited	14 %	0 %	0 %	14 %
Not at all	0 %	0 %	0 %	0 %

Table 31 - Responses for Evaluation of selected tools, Q16

Figure 34 - Responses for Evaluation of selected tools, Q16

Questions 17 and 18 were open.

Q17: Please, indicate key success factors of the implementation of the proposed solution.

TAPP	Feedback confirm that application allows more easier and faster working for EMS First Responders in a MCI, while digitisation of the triage process and real-time data sharing is key.
TTC	Feedback states that the simplicity and the effectiveness was most appreciated.
ISC2	Feedback confirms that this tool automates the entire data collection process and enables agile information sharing between agencies. Integration with SIGRUN facilitates this exchange.
GC	Feedback confirms that GLOBAL COP enables rapid deployment. It is deployed in the cloud and has a web interface. It allows information to be shared in an agile way.

Table 32 - Responses for Evaluation of selected tools, Q17

Q18: Please add recommendations for improvement for the proposed solution.

TApp	Feedback mentions concerns about no/poor signal connection or use in bad weather. The usability of the information in the mobile application can be improved. For example, when a patient has already gone through both triages and has to be assigned to a hospital, a change could be made to make it look faster.
TTC	n/a
iSC2	Feedback states that this tool is available on the market already.
GC	Feedback states that GLOBAL COP is not a final product. List extractions and reports could be added to facilitate data analysis and some screens could be improved as well as error checking.

*Table 33 - Responses for Evaluation of selected tools, Q18***CONCLUSION**

It is possible to quantify received feedback based on reached results. One of the possible ways is to assign 5 points to the first reply in each answer, 4 points to the second, etc. (1 point to the last). Then to summarize them and compare to the maximum possible results. Reached percentage presents high level of each tool covering different aspects as they were present in questions. These results shows that all the evaluated tools are more-less on the same level.

tool	Satisfactory
TApp	86,25 %
TTC	82,71 %
iSC2	86,55 %
GC	86,93 %

Table 34 - Conclusion for Evaluation of selected tools

Every evaluated tool overreached the level of the half (50 %), even though the second-best option (80 %). Received feedbacks are quite positive also, even they are not included in quantification. So, it is possible to state that the particular **tools are evaluated as effective and with potential to improve response action.**

At the same time, it is possible to state that the achieved high values create prerequisites (commitment) for next development with the aim of bringing these tools to the market.

17.4. Annex D3 – exercise satisfactory

EVALUATION OF THE EXERCISE "MAGIC CLOUD" UC2, SLOVAKIA, 21-22 June 2023

Exercise related to UC2 was implemented in Slovakia 21-22 June 2023. Evaluation of this exercise was provided in form of online survey. Responders answers 12 questions (Qs). The first was yes/no, the main part (Q2- Q10) there were possibilities on scale of 5 options from the best to the poorest, and the last one was request for narrative contribution. Q10 is about general satisfactory. Q11 is more about impacts on self-improvement and Q12 is request for narrative contribution. In this document, there is summary of it.

Q1: All the responders agreed that the selection of the exercise type (full scale and live exercise) was adequate for demonstration of the proposed solution. At the same time, it is important to state, that the exercise meet the need of Slovak responders for multi-agency training.

Q2: Please rate your satisfaction as far as the preparation of the exercise is concerned (preparatory meetings, informative material, support for traveling logistics)

Poor	0,0%
Inadequate	0,0%
Adequate	10,0%
Good	20,0%
Excellent	70,0%

Figure 35 - Responses for Exercise, Q2

Q3: Please rate your satisfaction on the training you received for the use of the proposed solutions in the exercise.

Poor	0,0%
Inadequate	0,0%
Adequate	0,0%
Good	50,0%
Excellent	50,0%

Figure 36 - Responses for Exercise, Q3

Q4: To what extent was the scenario of the Use Case realistic and responding to a potentially real life emergency?

Not at all	0,0%
Limited	0,0%
Moderate	0,0%
Considerable	50,0%
Great	50,0%

Figure 37 - Responses for Exercise, Q4

Q5: To what extent did the selected scenario showcase operational gaps in the response to a Multi-Casualty Incident and the added value that the proposed solutions bring in order to cover these gaps?

Not at all	0,0%
Limited	10,0%
Moderate	10,0%
Considerable	0,0%
Great	80,0%

Figure 38 - Responses for Exercise, Q5

Q6: The extent, to which the objectives of the exercise i.e., effective exchange of information between different first responders and increased situational awareness for the agencies engaged in a MCI, are achieved.

Not at all	0,0%
Limited	0,0%
Moderate	10,0%
Considerable	50,0%
Great	40,0%

Figure 39 - Responses for Exercise, Q6

Q7: How would you rate the overall coordination of the exercise? Did the coordination facilitate the effective collaboration between the participants?

Poor	0,0%
Inadequate	0,0%
Adequate	11,1%
Good	22,2%
Excellent	66,7%

Figure 40 - Responses for Exercise, Q7

Q8: How would you rate the logistics (location, venue, time, administrative support) of the exercise?

Poor	0,0%
Inadequate	0,0%
Adequate	0,0%
Good	60,0%
Excellent	40,0%

Figure 41 - Responses for Exercise, Q8

Q9: The extent, to which the timeline of the exercise was appropriately managed and followed the pre-defined schedule.

Not at all	0,0%
Limited	10,0%
Moderate	30,0%
Considerable	60,0%
Great	0,0%

Figure 42 - Responses for Exercise, Q9

Q10: Overall, to what extent were you satisfied with the conduct of the exercise?

Not at all	0,0%
Limited	0,0%
Moderate	0,0%
Considerable	30,0%
Great	70,0%

Figure 43 - Responses for Exercise, Q10

Q11: Your participation in the exercise, the implementation of tools and interaction with other stakeholders allowed you to increase your knowledge on innovative solutions and newly proposed methodologies that can be of added value for your operational work.

Strongly disagree	0,0%
Disagree	0,0%
Neutral	0,0%
Agree	30,0%
Strongly agree	70,0%

Figure 44 - Responses for Exercise, Q11

Q12: Please, indicate strengths and also areas that require improvement, to be considered for future exercises.

Strengths	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• coordination of representatives of several states;• exercise with the possibility of using innovative technologies.
Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• better spaces for theoretical preparation considering that it is an international participation (more representative)• organization and logistics (Some FRs were unable to attend the training session and had to train on the day of the exercise. I think this group lacked a bit of training in order to be more agile in the use of the application for digitalizing triage process. Nevertheless, the results were good and they were used correctly).
Recommendations	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Exercise could also take place at night.
Notices:	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• request from end-users for involving also for future training,• great effort of the organisation and the great involvement of the participants in all phases of the exercise made it possible to test the effectiveness of training, technology, operational procedures and inter-agency cooperation in the extreme circumstance of a complex multi-casualty accident,

Table 35 - Responses for Exercise, Q12

CONCLUSIONS

The basic premise is to evaluate the choice of the best answer option together with the second best (40 percent of the total scale). More than 50% vote for these options in every single question.

Average of the options are as follows:

poor	0,0%
not good	2,2%
moderate	7,9%
good	34,7%
best	55,2%

Table 36 - Conclusion for Evaluation of exercise

Overall satisfactory (Q10) reached values 70% for “great” and 30% for “satisfactory”.

Taking this feedback into consideration, it is possible to confirm, that **the exercise was successful**, met the project criteria, and covered the needs of end users. The activity contributed to the practice of the required skills, the exchange of experience, the improvement of intervention in the presence of several units, the recognition of the most modern technologies and trends, and the testing of the required tools and identified opportunities.

Contributions from the question 12 indicates, that there is still room form improvement. This is the commitment for organizing of future exercises and training activities, which have been identified and important.

18. Annex E – WP4 Result sheets Opportunities

18.2. CO-WP4-42- Reduce Voice Communication

18.2.1. CO-WP4-42- T01- Reduce Voice Communication

CO-WP4-42-T01- Reduce Voice Communication			
Description	<i>Integration test related to Incident Creation, Task Creation and assets creation and update and information access from several devices for UC2</i>		
Location/Participants	<i>Initial Testing: 19th June (remotely) Indra, Particle Intermediate Testing: 21th June (remotely) Indra, Particle Final Testing: 22nd June (On Site) Indra, Particle, ISEMI, Tassica, Fire and Rescue Service, Areu)</i>		
Requirements	REQ_COM-T4.3.2, REQ_COM-T4.3.10, REQ_COM-T4.3.19, REQ_COM-T4.3.22		
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> <u>1.</u> Incident Reported in SIGRUN <u>2.</u> Task Reported in SIGRUN <u>3.</u> Asset assignment to task in incident is reported in SIGRUN 4.Asset status is reported in SIGRUN 5.Asset location is reported in SIGRUN 6.GLOBAL COP information accessible through different devices 	<p><i>iSafety application updates data in SIGRUN</i></p> <p><i>GLOBAL COP visualizes the information in several devices (laptops, tablets)</i></p>	<p>KPI 1: Information about the incident available in SIGRUN: YES/NO (Available = success)</p> <p>KPI 2: information about the task available in SIGRUN: YES/NO (Available = success)</p> <p>KPI 3: Information about assets localization available in SIGRUN: YES/NO (Available = success)</p> <p>KPI 4: Information about assets associated to tasks available in SIGRUN. YES/NO (Available = success)</p> <p>KPI 5: Information related to Incident/tasks/assets in GLOBAL COP is available through different devices. YES/NO (Available = success)</p>	Test
	Description	Incident Creation	

CO-WP4-42-T01- Reduce Voice Communication		
Verification Step#1	Participants	PARTICLE, INDRA
	Location	Remotely/Onsite
	Execution	<p>An operator using iSafety, creates a new incident (Toxic Cloud), specifying type of the incident, location and a short description. When operator click on Save Button to create the incident in iSafety, this information is sent to SIGRUN.</p> <p>Then, this incident is created in SIGRUN, and this information is showed on Global COP web portal, and system applications can read this incident information from SIGRUN</p>
	Analysis and results	The information is available on SIGRUN (GLOBAL_COP) and iSafety
	History of corrective measures	Access errors appeared if the URL or API was not correct and If connectivity was not guaranteed. Not many corrective measures were done because the integration was previous verified in the other UC.
	Lessons learned	From previous UC: Check Communications. Check incident catalogue between the systems. Several tests must be performed before executing the whole test.
	Quality	A
	End-user feedback	No end user feedback.
	Result	YES
Verification Step#2	Description	Missions/Tasks Creation
	Participants	PARTICLE, INDRA
	Location	Remotely
	Execution	An Emergency service operator, using iSafety, creates a new mission (CONTROL MISSION and MEDICAL MISSION) associated to the incident, specifying type of the mission and a short description. When operator click on Save Button in order to create the task in iSafety, this information is sent to SIGRUN.
	Analysis and results	The information is available on iSafety and GLOBAL COP.
	History of corrective measures	Access errors appeared if the URL or API was not correct and If connectivity was not guaranteed. Not many corrective measures

CO-WP4-42-T01- Reduce Voice Communication		
		were done because the integration was previous verified in the other UC.
	Lessons learned	The catalogue of tasks has to match (iSafety/SIGRUN). Several tests need to be performed.
	Quality	A
	End-user feedback	No end user feedback.
	Result	YES
Verification Step#3	Description	Assets assignment to tasks and update
	Participants	PARTICLE, INDRA
	Location	Remotely
	Execution	On a third step, Emergency service operator, using iSafety, assign several assets to Medical Mission (AMBULANCE 1, AMBULANCE 2) and several assets to Control Mission (AHZS, EKOS, CAS, SAH). Then operator changes the status of the assets when they are “on the way”.
	Analysis and results	The information is available on ISafety and GLOBAL-COP
	History of corrective measures	The same that previous verifications but also the assets catalogue has to be the same between SIGRUN and iSafety (previous check). Several tests need to be performed.
	Lessons learned	The asset catalogue has to match (iSafety/SIGRUN). The biggest complexity has been modelling the units and assets with the SIGRUN data model. Each organisation is different and the exercise quite complicated. We have tried to homogenise the missions and tasks between the agencies in order to better understand the operational vision but in reality each agency has its own type of mission and should be adjusted in more detail for real use.
	Quality	A
	End-user feedback	No end user feedback.
	Result	YES

Table 37 – Results sheet CO-WP4-42-T01

Below is a more detailed test with the complete exercise. The verification steps are repeated depending on the missions, tasks and resources that are managed from command and control.

TEST-ID	CO-WP4-42- T01- Reduce Voice Communication				
Location and date	<i>Initial Testing: 19th June (remotely) Indra, Particle</i> <i>Intermediate Testing: 21th June (remotely) Indra, Particle</i> <i>Final Testing: 22nd June (On Site) Indra, Particle, ISEMI, Tassica, Fire and Rescue Service, Areu)</i>				
Participants	Indra, Particle, ISEMI, Tassica, Fire and Rescue Service, Areu)				
ACTION		TYPE (iSafety)		Description	Results
Incident Creation	Incident	TOXIC CLOUD		Incident Creation	OK
Mission Creation	Mission 1	CONTROL		Control Task	OK
Mission Creation	Mission 2	MEDICAL SUPPORT		Medical Support task	OK
Mission Creation	Mission 1	AHZS,EKOS,CAS, SAHS			OK
Asset Update	Mission 1	AHZS,EKOS,CAS, SAHS	"ON THE WAY"	FireFighters on the way	OK
Asset Update	Mission 1	AHZS,EKOS,CAS, SAHS	"ON SITE"	FireFighters on the way	OK
Asset Assigment	Mission 2	AMBULANCE 1, AMBULANCE 2			OK
Asset Update	Mission 2	AMBULANCE 1, AMBULANCE 2	"ON THE WAY"	Ambulances on the way	OK
Asset Update	Mission 2	AMBULANCE 1, AMBULANCE 2	"ON SITE"	Ambulances on site	OK
Asset update	Mission 1	POLICE CAR			
Asset update	Mission 1	POLICE CAR	"ON THE WAY"		OK
Asset update	Mission 1	POLICE CAR	"ON SITE"	Police car arrived	OK
Mission Creation	Mission 3	CONTROL			OK
Asset update	Mission 3	CBRN Van	"ON THE WAY"	CBRN van on the way	OK
Mission Creation	Mission 4	Medical Support		Ambulances from Italy	OK
Asset update	Mission 4	AMBULANCE 3	"ON THE WAY"	Ambulance from Italy on the way	OK
Asset Update	Mission 1	AHZS,EKOS,CAS, SAHS	"RESOLVED"	Free the resources	OK
Asset update	Mission 3	CBRN Van	"ON SITE"	CBNR on site	OK
Asset update	Mission 4	AMBULANCE 3	"ON SITE"	Ambulance from Italy on the site	OK
Asset Update	Mission 2	AMBULANCE 1, AMBULANCE 2	"RESOLVED"	Ambulances free	OK
Asset update	Mission 3	CBRN Van	"RESOLVED"	CBRN free	OK
Asset update	Mission 1	POLICE CAR	"RESOLVED"	Police car free	OK

ACTION		TYPE (iSafety)		Description	Results
Incident close	Incident	TOXIC CLOUD	Close incident	Close incident	OK

Table 38 – Detailed test CO-WP4-42-T01

18.2.2. CO-WP4-42-T02- Reduce Voice Communication

CO-WP4-42-T02- Reduce Voice Communication			
Description	<i>Integration Test related to Triage Information (UC2), the information should be the same in both countries and also different devices</i>		
Date and Location	<i>Several Tests were performed</i> - 19th June - First Test (remotely) - 21th June- Pre-demo Test (remotely) - 22nd June- Demonstration Test (On Site)		
Participants	INDRA, TASSICA, PARTICLE		
Requirements	COM_T4.3_2, REQ_COM_T4.3_22, REQ_COM_T4.4_10, REQ_COM_T4.4_11, REQ_COM_T4.5.2.		
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
1. Victims registration in SIGRUN 2. Victims' status time update in SIGRUN 3. Victims triage data update in SIGRUN 4. GLOBAL COP information accessible through different devices 5. GLOBAL COP information accessible in different countries	System applications updates incident data in SIGRUN Command and control systems read data from SIGRUN GLOBAL COP visualizes the information in several devices (laptops, tablets) GLOBAL COP visualizes the information in both countries	KPI 1: Victim Registration available: YES/NO (Available = success) KPI 2: Victim status time update (Triage STATUS) available: YES/NO (Available = success) KPI 3: Victims triage data update (Triage STATUS) available: YES/NO (Available = success) KPI 4: Information related Triage Process in GLOBAL COP is available through different devices. YES/NO (Available = success) KPI 5: Information about Triage Process in GLOBAL COP is available in both countries. YES/NO (Available = success)	Test

CO-WP4-42-T02- Reduce Voice Communication		
Verification action #1	Description	<i>Victim Registration and Medical Information Registration Verification</i>
	Execution	<i>Incident (Toxic Cloud) is created into SIGRUN Platform Victim Age/Gender is registered in the platform. Status Triage information is updated (AT,ET) Main Pathology is updated Triage Classification is updated Transport is updated Staff reporting information is available</i>
	Analysis and results	<i>The information is displayed in GLOBAL-COP</i>
	History of corrective measures	<i>The terminals must be setup for staff information. Connectivity with URL and API must be configured and checked previously.</i>
	Lessons learned	<i>The communications and access to URL/API for terminals and applications deployed with GLOBAL COP must be checked before and the application for digitalizing triage process must be checked in every terminal before to avoid problems during the test</i>
	Quality	A
	End-user feedback	<i>No feed Back from user</i>
	Result	YES
Verification action #2	Description	<i>GLOBAL COP Information visualized in TABLET and the same for both countries</i>
	Execution	<i>We check that the same information displayed in workstation is displayed in GLOBAL COP and the workstations from Command Post for each country</i>
	Analysis and results	<i>The information is displayed in a tablet GLOBAL-COP</i>
	History of corrective measures	<i>The terminals must be setup for staff information.</i>
	Lessons learned	<i>The communications and access to API/URL must be checked before the test</i>
	Quality	A
	End-user feedback	<i>No feed Back from user</i>
	Result	YES

Table 39 – Results sheet CO-WP4-42-T02

18.2.3. CO-WP4-42_T03- Reduce Voice Communication

CO-WP4-42-T03- Reduce Voice Communication			
Description	Test for Verification Real Time Update in SIGRUN Platform (UC2)		
Date and Location	22nd June- Demonstration Test (UC2 Demonstration Site)		
Participants	INDRA, TASSICA, PARTICLE, ISEMI, AREU		
Requirements	REQ_COM_T4.3.1		
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
<p>1. Incident reported in SIGRUN (< than 60 s)</p> <p>-2. Task Registration in SIGRUN (< than 60 s)</p> <p>-3. Assets registration in SIGRUN (< than 60 s)</p> <p>- Assets update in SIGRUN (< than 60 s)</p>	<p>System applications update data in SIGRUN</p> <p>Command and control systems read data from SIGRUN</p>	<p>KPI 1: Time elapsed (since Incident is created in iSafety and registered in SIGRUN Database)</p> <p>< 60 sec 100% success</p> <p>Between 60 and 90 sec 50% success</p> <p>Between 90 to 120 sec 25% success</p> <p>> 120 sec 0% success</p> <p>KPI 2: Time elapsed (since task is created in iSafety and registered in SIGRUN Database)</p> <p>< 60 sec 100% success</p> <p>Between 60 and 90 sec 50% success</p> <p>Between 90 to 120 sec 25% success</p> <p>> 120 sec 0% success</p> <p>KPI 3: Time elapsed (since asset is created in iSafety and registered in SIGRUN Database)</p> <p>< 60 sec 100% success</p> <p>Between 60 and 90 sec 50% success</p> <p>Between 90 to 120 sec 25% success</p> <p>> 120 sec 0% success</p> <p>KPI 4: Information about Triage Process in GLOBAL COP is available in both countries.</p> <p>YES/NO (Available = success)</p>	Test
Verification action #1	Description	Incident Creation	
	Execution	Incident (Toxic Cloud) is created into SIGRUN Platform by an operator	
	Analysis and results	The information is displayed in GLOBAL-COP. We verify that we have the iSafety logs and	

CO-WP4-42-T03- Reduce Voice Communication		
		<i>that we have the information in the SIGRUN database for subsequent analysis.</i>
	History of corrective measures	<i>The tests were executed correctly but the records in SIGRUN should be reviewed, for some reason the date of modification of the incident is overlaid and the original creation date is not maintained.</i>
	Lessons learned	<i>To ensure that everything works and can be tested, many pre-tests have to be carried out to check that the data between the two applications is correct. The integration must also be reviewed.</i>
	Quality	A
	End-user feedback	<i>No feed Back from user</i>
	Result	NO <i>The test was executed correctly, and the data appeared in the GLOBAL COP but there was a problem in the data analysis from the logs, for some reason the incident start date was not kept and was only overwritten with the modifications. We have discarded the data.</i>
Verification action #2	Description	<i>Task Creation</i>
	Execution	<i>A task (Control) is created into the incident</i>
	Analysis and results	<i>The information is displayed in GLOBAL-COP</i>
	History of corrective measures	<i>The communications to API/URL must be checked before Execution. The catalogue with the type of tasks must have been previously configured and must match between SIGRUN and the Command-and-Control applications.</i>
	Lessons learned	
	Quality	A
	End-user feedback	<i>No feed Back from user</i>
	Result	YES
Verification action #2	Description	<i>Asset assignment to a Task</i>
	Execution	<i>An asset is attached to the previous task created (Fire Unit)</i>
	Analysis and results	<i>The information is displayed in GLOBAL-COP. We ensure that we have the application logs locally and the data in the central DB for further analysis.</i>
	History of corrective measures	<i>To ensure that everything works and can be tested, many pre-tests have to be carried out to check that the data between the two applications is correct.</i>

CO-WP4-42-T03- Reduce Voice Communication		
	Lessons learned	<i>The environment is the same as the previous tests and we can extract the same lessons.</i>
	Quality	A
	End-user feedback	<i>No feed Back from user</i>
	Result	YES

Table 40 – Results sheet CO-WP4-42-T03

The results have been extracted with the full table shown in the previous test (CO-WP4-42_T01).

18.3. CO.WP4.21: Historical data analysis from the missions and platform

18.3.1. CO-WP4-21- T01- Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms

CO-WP4-21- T01- Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms			
Description	SIGRUN must be capable of integrating data form multiples sources, such as, specific data for each first responder during an emergency, allowing to analyse the data to create a trained model.		
Location/Participants	UMU		
Requirements	REQ_COM_T7.2_1, REQ_COM_T7.2_2, REQ_COM_T7.2_3		
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
Creation of a model which can speed up tasks in an emergency response.	Execution time: Time prediction – less than 1000ms. System resource consumption: Imperceptible	KPI 1: Adequacy: 90%. KPI 2: Penalties in execution time: less than 5000ms	Demo
	Description	Data analysis	
	Participants	UMU	
	Location	Remotely	
	Execution	<i>To demonstrate this requirement, the database with the gathered data during use cases by different sources of different first responders has been checked to analyse the data generated and apply preprocessed techniques to the data and create trained models.</i>	
	Analysis and results	<i>Different data processing techniques have been applied to obtain the most important features, and then three Machine Learning models have been generated. The first one consists of predicting the second triage based on the data obtained in the first one. The second model predicts the patient's death after the first triage. The last model predicts the patient's worsening after the first triage. All information about the processing techniques and the generated models can be found in D.7.2.</i>	
History of corrective measures			

CO-WP4-21- T01- Historical data analysis from the missions and platforms

	Lessons learned	<i>Analysing triage data generated in different use cases and creating predictive models is highly important for first responders to obtain patterns and trends that may go unnoticed.</i>
	Quality	A
	End-user feedback	<i>No end user feedback.</i>
	Result	YES

Table 41 – Results sheet CO-WP4-21-T01

19. Annex F – WP5 Result sheets Opportunities

19.2. CO.WP5-1: Standardisation of terms in planning, preparedness and execution of the emergency response

19.2.1. CO-WP5-1-D01 - VALKYRIES collaborative glossary for emergency response planning, preparedness and execution: DEMONSTRATION

CO-WP5-1-D01 - VALKYRIES collaborative glossary for emergency response planning, preparedness and execution: DEMONSTRATION			
Description	<p>The prototype VALKYRIES Collaborative Glossary for Emergency Response Planning, Preparedness and Execution (VALKYRIES GLOSSARY) has provided a common understanding of terms for VALKYRIES researchers and all partners involved in the planning and execution of demonstrators. It has also served as a fundamental reference for the development of the SIGRUN federated system.</p> <p>Information was collected on how stakeholders assess the acceptance of the proposed unified glossary.</p>		
Traceability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Traceability with identified requirements: REQ_COM_T5.2_10, REQ_BASE_T5.3_3, REQ_COM_T5.4_2 Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-4, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9 		
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
Importance of all emergency services using a unified glossary to plan and respond to Mci and disasters	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 1: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by respondents.	Demonstration
Verification action	Date and location	Bratislava (Slovakia), 22 June 2023.	
	Participants	Consortium and local partners' experts involved in UC2 previous organization tasks.	
	Description	<p>A questionnaire was performed to evaluate the acceptance of a unified glossary for UC2 planning, preparedness and execution. Question number 1 of this survey is related to this enabler.</p> <p>The questionnaires are anonymous. Only the institution to which the author belongs is known.</p>	
	Execution	<p>The consultation took place during the UC2 workdays, after the training of the participants and before the execution of the MCI drill.</p> <p>The survey was addressed to all participants from all institutions that have used the VALKYRIES Community Glossary for Emergency Planning, Preparedness and Response in their tasks of preparing and conducting the UC.</p>	

CO-WP5-1-D01 - VALKYRIES collaborative glossary for emergency response planning, preparedness and execution: DEMONSTRATION		
	Analysis and results	After analysing the responses, the following result was obtained: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Importance: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • Predominant response: TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT
	History of corrective measures	
	Lessons learned	
	Quality	A, maximum adequacy (>90% compliance with the KPIs).
	End-user feedback	
	Result	Successful verification: YES

Table 42 – Results sheet CO.WP5-1-D01

Evidence of implementation and compliance:

See Annex F, section WP5 UC2 demonstration evidence (evidence 1 and 3, question1)

19.3. CO.WP5-7: Harmonization of operating procedures in emergency response

VALKYRIES Project proposes two enablers to achieve harmonisation and pre-standardisation in the field of MCI operating procedures:

- Unification of triage with regard to priorities and casualty labelling codes in MCI and disasters.
- Standardised triage card TASSICA 3 as a non-technological tool to support traceability, unified prioritisation, interoperability and labelling of victims.

Both have been tested and evaluated in the UC2.

19.3.1. CO.WP5-7-1-D01 - Unification of triage priority coding and tagging in MCI and disasters at EU level: DEMONSTRATION

CO.WP5-7-1-D01 - Unification of triage priority coding and tagging in MCI and disasters at EU level: DEMONSTRATION	
Description	<p>The VALKYRIES project proposes a EU-wide standardised a pentapolar triage code, based primarily on NATO standards, to unify the coding and labelling of casualties in mass casualty incidents (MCI) and disasters. The assessment of the enabler in the UC2 demonstrator was carried out through the following verification actions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A questionnaire was developed in the UC workdays to collect respondents' opinions on the standardized coding and classifying victims proposed by VALKYRIES Project in the UC (VERIFICATION ACTION #1). • The degree of compliance of the UCs implementation with the VALKYRIES recommendations regarding the standardised classification and coding (colour) of victims was verified on the basis of the data stored in the SIGRUN federated system during the UC drill (VERIFICATION ACTION #2).

CO.WP5-7-1-D01 - Unification of triage priority coding and tagging in MCI and disasters at EU level: DEMONSTRATION			
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Finally, an online survey was conducted at the end of the UC drill to collect participants' evaluation (VERIFICATION ACTION #3). 		
Traceability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Traceability with identified requirements: REQ_COM_T5.1_2, REQ_BASE_T5.3_3 Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-4, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9 		
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
Relevance: Degree of importance attached to the use of a common classification and coding of victim priorities in a MCI.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 1: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration
Stakeholder coding and labelling agreement: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 2: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration
Cross-border cooperation improvement : The perceived improvement in cross-border cooperation between EMS when using a standardised classification and coding system.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 3: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration
UC coding standardisation	YES/NO (compliance = success).	KPI 4: The information related to the	Demonstration

CO.WP5-7-1-D01 - Unification of triage priority coding and tagging in MCI and disasters at EU level: DEMONSTRATION

compliance: The degree of adherence in the UC to the standardised classification and coding of MCI victims proposed by VALKYRIES.		triage of victims in SIGRUN complies with the standardised classification and coding proposed by VALKYRIES.	
Verification action #1	Date and location	Bratislava (Slovakia), 22 June 2023.	
	Participants	Consortium and local partners' experts involved in UC2 previous training tasks.	
	Description	A survey was carried out containing questions (2, 3, and 4) regarding the following aspects: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Importance of EMS using the same classification to designate triage priority in MCI and disasters. • Use of a specific name for triage priorities • Specific assignment of colours for different triage priorities. • Assessment of the use of the same classification and colour coding in the EU to facilitate EMS working together in cross-border MCI. The questionnaires are anonymous. Only the institution to which the author belongs is known.	
	Execution	During the UC2 workdays, all training sessions with responders worked with the pentapolar classification proposed by VALKYRIES for the coding and labelling of triage priorities for mass casualty incidents (MCI) and disasters. At the end of these sessions, all members of the emergency services participating in the exercise were asked to complete a survey. Respondents answered the survey on a voluntary and anonymous basis.	
	Analysis and results	After analysing the responses, the following results were obtained: KPIs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Relevance: 100% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 2: Stakeholder coding and tagging agreement: 100% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 3: Cross-border cooperation improvement: 100% (ACHIEVED) PREDOMINANT RESPONSE: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT • Stakeholder coding and tagging agreement: TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT 	

CO.WP5-7-1-D01 - Unification of triage priority coding and tagging in MCI and disasters at EU level: DEMONSTRATION		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cross-border cooperation improvement: TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT
	History of corrective measures	
	Lessons learned	
	Quality	A: Maximum adequacy (>90% KPIs achieved)
	End-user feedback	
	Result	Successful verification: YES
Verification action #2	Date and location	Stupava (Slovakia), 22 June 2023
	Participants	Bratislava Control Chemical Laboratory (Slovakia), Bratislava Emergency Medical Service (Slovakia), ENVIRO Department for detection of hazardous substances and environmental crime (Slovakia), Bratislava Fire and Rescue System (Slovakia), AREU Agenzia Regionale Emergenza Urgenza (Italy)
	Description	The degree of compliance with the proposed standardised classification and coding (colour) of victims during the UC has been assessed on the basis of the data recorded in SIGRUN during the conduct of UC2 drill.
	Execution	A cross-national MCI exercise was carried out with the participation of various emergency services assuming the different roles involved in the emergency response (first responders, disaster managers, technologists, etc.). The information related to victims' triage coding was created and shared by first responders through SIGRUN. The identification data and pathology of the drill victims were fictitious. Connectivity 4G between applications is required for the evaluation within SIGRUN. The connectivity between the terminals and the SIGRUN platform will be verified prior to the test. The terminals will be previously configured with the associated users.
	Analysis and results	After analysing the responses, the following results were obtained: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 4: Coding compliance: YES (ACHIEVED) All categories and colour codes used to indicate the triage priority of victims in the various SIGRUN federated tools used in UC2 have been aligned with the triage categories and codes proposed by VALKYRIES.
	History of corrective measures	

CO.WP5-7-1-D01 - Unification of triage priority coding and tagging in MCI and disasters at EU level: DEMONSTRATION

	Lessons learned	
	Quality	A: Maximum adequacy (>90% KPIs achieved)
	End-user feedback	
	Result	Successful verification: YES
Verification action #3	Date and location	On line survey, 22 June 2023 and thereafter.
	Participants	All participants in the UC2 drill.
	Description	<p>At the end of the workdays, an extensive online survey was conducted to gather the participants' assessment of various aspects of the UC2, both in relation to the various VALKYRIES enablers brought to the demonstrator, and in relation to the organisation and development of the use case itself. Some of these questions (8, 9, 10 and 11) asked about topics such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The significance of EMS employing a uniform classification for triage prioritization in MCIs and disasters. • Adoption of a unified labelling for triage levels. • Dedicated colour allocations for each triage priority. <p>Evaluation of the adoption of consistent classification and colour coding across the EU to aid EMS collaboration during cross-border MCIs.</p>
	Execution	<p>This evaluation was carried out in coordination with other VALKYRIES enablers, using the SIGRUN platform as integration tool, in the same drill detailed for VERIFICATION ACTION #2.</p> <p>The simulation worked with the pentapolar classification proposed by VALKYRIES for the coding and labelling of triage priorities in mass casualty incidents (MCI) and disasters.</p> <p>At the end of the drill, all members of the emergency services participating in the exercise were asked to complete a survey. Respondents answered the survey voluntarily and anonymously. Only the institution to which the author belongs is known.</p>
	Analysis and results	<p>After analysing the responses, the following results were obtained:</p> <p>KPIs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Relevance: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 2: Stakeholder coding and tagging agreement: 87,50% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 3: Cross-border cooperation improvement: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) <p>PREDOMINANT RESPONSE:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevance: TOTALLY AGREE

CO.WP5-7-1-D01 - Unification of triage priority coding and tagging in MCI and disasters at EU level: DEMONSTRATION

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stakeholder coding and tagging agreement: TOTALLY AGREE Cross-border cooperation improvement: TOTALLY AGREE
	History of corrective measures	
	Lessons learned	
	Quality	A: Maximum adequacy (>90% KPIs achieved)
	End-user feedback	
	Result	Successful verification: YES

Table 43 – Results sheet CO.WP5-7-1-D01

Evidence of implementation and compliance

See Annex F, section WP5 Preliminary test and UC2 demonstration evidence:

- Evidence 1 and 3 (questions 2, 3 and 4)
- Evidence 6

See Annex B2 – VALIDATION QUESTIONNAIRE (EN version) (questions 8, 9, 10 and 11)

19.3.2. CO-WP5-7-2-D01 - TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in mci and disasters: DEMONSTRATION
CO-WP5-7-2-D01 - TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in mci and disasters: DEMONSTRATION

Description	<p>VALKYRIES proposes the use of a standardised triage card (TASSICA 3) in the EU for the recording of key casualty information by the different emergency services that may intervene in a MCI.</p> <p>UC2 assessed the validity of the TASSICA 3 triage card as a mean of supporting interoperability between services (professional or volunteer, civilian or military), fairness in prioritising treatment, recording casualty information and traceability in mass casualty and disaster situations.</p> <p>The assessment of the enabler in the UC2 demonstrator was carried out through the following verification actions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A questionnaire was developed to collect respondents' opinions on the TASSICA 3 triage card (VERIFICATION ACTION #1). The effectiveness of this enabler was also assessed objectively in UC2 (VERIFICATION ACTION #2). 		
Traceability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Traceability with identified requirements: REQ_COM_T5.1_2, REQ_COM_T5.2_10, REQ_BASE_T5.3_3, REQ_COM_T5.3_5 Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-4, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9 		
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method

CO-WP5-7-2-D01 - TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in mci and disasters: DEMONSTRATION

Inter-rater reliability: The consistency in triage decisions among different first responders using the TASSICA triage card.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 1: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration
Decision-making confidence: improvement in healthcare staff confidence in making triage decisions using the TASSICA triage card, as measured by self-reported score	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 2: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration
Traceability: the extent to which the card helps to improve the traceability of victims throughout the chain of care at the scene of an MCI.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 3: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration
Victim information completeness and accuracy: degree of ease of recording complete and accurate	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 4: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration

CO-WP5-7-2-D01 - TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in mci and disasters: DEMONSTRATION

victim information using the TASSICA triage card.			
First responder wellbeing: The degree to which the card helps the first responder in their care tasks and reduces their stress during operations.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 5: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration
Task execution efficiency: The reduction in time taken to perform tasks in an MCI compared to using other options, as perceived by first responders.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 6: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration
Collaboration efficiency: The improvement in cross-border EMS collaboration, to coordinate and perform joint tasks using the TASSICA triage card, as perceived by first responders.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 7: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration

CO-WP5-7-2-D01 - TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in mci and disasters: DEMONSTRATION

Stakeholder satisfaction: The overall satisfaction of first responders with the TASSICA triage card.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 8: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration
Time to triage: The average time taken to assign triage priorities using the TASSICA triage card.	Time (in seconds) from the victim first approach to the determination of triage priority and immediate actions.	KPI 9: A maximum acceptable average time to assign primary triage priorities: 1,5 min (90 sec).	Demonstration
Triage accuracy rate: The percentage of correct triage decisions made using the TASSICA triage card.	% (rate calculated by dividing the number of correctly triaged casualties by the total number of triaged casualties, expressed as a percentage).	KPI 10: Minimum 80% of correctly triaged casualties made using the TASSICA triage card.	Demonstration
Verification action #1	Date and location	Bratislava (Slovakia), 22 June 2023.	
	Participants	Consortium and local partners' experts involved in UC2 previous training tasks.	
	Description	<p>A questionnaire was prepared with questions (5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, and 12) on the following aspects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The data are collected by the researchers. • The questionnaire collects questions referring to the following aspects: • Extent to which the card helps to homogenise triage priorities, decide on life-saving gestures, ensure traceability of a victim, and facilitates the recording of health information. 	

CO-WP5-7-2-D01 - TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in mci and disasters: DEMONSTRATION

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Degree in which its use reduces the stress of healthcare staff in decision making. • Assessment of its use in facilitating joint EMS work in cross-border MCI. • Rating on enabling more efficient execution of tasks in a MCI compared to other procedures. • Overall level of satisfaction <p>The survey was open to all the First Responders involved in the exercise. The respondents answered the survey anonymously. Only the institution to which the author belongs is known.</p> <p>The personal details of the victims used during the simulation exercise are fictitious.</p>
	Execution	<p>Within the development days of the UC2, a training session was carried out in relation to the operational procedure using TASSICA 3 triage card. In this session, the participants practised all the steps and roles involved in the different specific operational procedures proposed for attending to victims of an MCI or disaster.</p> <p>At the end of these sessions, all members of the emergency services participating in the exercise were asked to complete a survey. Respondents answered the survey on a voluntary and anonymous basis.</p>
	Analysis and results	<p>After analysing the responses, the following results were obtained:</p> <p>KPIs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Inter-rater reliability: 80,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 2: Decision-making confidence: 80,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 3: Traceability: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 4: Victim information completeness and accuracy: 80,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 5: First responder wellbeing: 90,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 6: Task execution efficiency: 80,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 7: Collaboration efficiency: 60,00% (NOT ACHIEVED) • KPI 8: Stakeholder satisfaction: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) <p>PREDOMINANT RESPONSE:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inter-rater reliability: QUITE IN AGREEMENT • Decision-making confidence: TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT • Traceability: TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT • Victim information completeness and accuracy: TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT • First responder wellbeing: QUITE IN AGREEMENT • Task execution efficiency: QUITE IN AGREEMENT • Collaboration efficiency: QUITE IN AGREEMENT

CO-WP5-7-2-D01 - TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in mci and disasters: DEMONSTRATION

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stakeholder satisfaction: QUITE IN AGREEMENT
	History of corrective measures	
	Lessons learned	
	Quality	A: Maximum adequacy (>90% KPIs achieved)
	End-user feedback	
	Result	Successful verification: YES
Verification action #2	Date and location	Stupava (Slovakia), 22 June 2023
	Participants	Bratislava Control Chemical Laboratory (Slovakia), Bratislava Emergency Medical Service (Slovakia), ENVIRO Department for detection of hazardous substances and environmental crime (Slovakia), Bratislava Fire and Rescue System (Slovakia), AREU Agenzia Regionale Emergenza Urgenza (Italy)
	Description	<p>The objective validity of the TASSICA 3 triage card was assessed on the basis of the data recorded by VALKYRIES' evaluators during the conduct of UC2 drill.</p> <p>A data sheet was defined to manually record the information needed to evaluate TASSICA 3 triage card during the UC execution.</p>
	Execution	<p>A cross-border CBRN multi-casualty exercise was conducted at UC2. It was led by the Slovakian Emergency Services in cooperation with Italian medical rapid response teams (AREU).</p> <p>The search, decontamination, triage, stabilisation and evacuation of MCI victims were carried out in three identical consecutive exercises, each using a different operating procedure:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Procedure normally used in the service (with the usual triage cards). 2. Procedure using TASSICA 3 triage cards. 3. Procedure using SIGRUN federated system. <p>Collection of the information necessary to evaluate the TASSICA 3 triage card was made manually by a network of VALKYRIES' evaluators. The number and location of those evaluators during the execution of the UC was defined in order to properly carry out the data collection for the evaluation of the proposed enabler.</p>
	Analysis and results	<p>After analysing the responses, the following results were obtained:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> KPI 9: Time to triage threshold (TASSICA 3): 25,18 sec (ACHIEVED)

CO-WP5-7-2-D01 - TASSICA 3 standardised triage card to ensure interoperability, equity, victims information register and traceability in mci and disasters: DEMONSTRATION		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> KPI 10: Triage accuracy rate (TASSICA 3): 100% (ACHIEVED) <p>The following results were obtained using the procedures in place before the VALKYRIES proposal:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Time to triage threshold: 37,05 sec Triage accuracy rate: 77,27% <p>The use of the TASSICA 3 Triage Card reduces the time required for primary triage of MCI victims by 32.01% and significantly improves the accuracy of triage.</p>
	History of corrective measures	
	Lessons learned	
	Quality	A: Maximum adequacy (>90% KPIs achieved)
	End-user feedback	
	Result	Successful verification: YES

Table 44 – Results sheet CO.WP5-7-2-D01

Evidence of implementation and compliance:

See Annex F, section WP5 Preliminary test and UC2 demonstration evidence:

- Evidence 1 and 3 (questions 5 to 12)
- Evidence 5

19.4. CO.WP5-12: Standardization of information sharing in emergency response

19.4.1. CO-WP5-12-D01 - Emergency medical services minimum data set (EMS MDS) for sharing information in MCI and disasters: DEMONSTRATION

CO-WP5-12-D01 - Emergency medical services minimum data set (EMS MDS) for sharing information in MCI and disasters: DEMONSTRATION	
Description	<p>VALKYRIES proposes a Minimum Data Set (EMS MDS) for Emergency Medical Services to share during MCIs and disasters concerning victim care. This EMS MDS includes data such as victim identification, characteristics, contact details, location, injuries, clinical updates, and other vital information.</p> <p>The assessment of this enabler was carried out through a questionnaire developed in the UC workdays to collect respondents' opinions on the EMS MDS proposed by VALKYRIES Project in the UC (VERIFICATION ACTION #1).</p>
Traceability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Traceability with identified requirements: REQ_COM_T5.2_4, REQ_COM_T5.2_5, REQ_COM_T5.2_8, REQ_COM_T5.2_10, REQ_COM_T5.2_11, REQ_COM_T5.2_12, REQ_COM_T5.2_13, REQ_COM_T5.2_14, REQ_BASE_T5.3_3, REQ_COM_T5.3_4, REQ_COM_T5.3_7, REQ_COM_T5.3_9, REQ_COM_T5.3_10, REQ_COM_T5.3_11, REQ_COM_T5.3_12, REQ_COM_T5.3_13,

CO-WP5-12-D01 - Emergency medical services minimum data set (EMS MDS) for sharing information in MCI and disasters: DEMONSTRATION

	REQ_COM_T5.3_15, REQ_COM_T5.3_16, REQ_COM_T5.3_20, REQ_COM_T5.3_21, REQ_COM_T5.3_22 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-4, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9 		
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
Data relevance: The perceived relevance of the data exchanged during the trial for proper management of casualties by EMS in an MCI or disaster	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 1: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration
Data usefulness: The perceived usefulness of the exchanged data in the performance of care tasks by first responders.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 2: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration
Verification action #1	Date and location	Bratislava (Slovakia), 22 June 2023.	
	Participants	Consortium and local partners' experts involved in UC2 training tasks.	
	Description	A survey was carried out containing questions (1 and 2) related to the following aspects: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Opinion on whether the data transmitted in the test are appropriate for the proper management of casualties by an EMS in MCI or disasters. Whether the data exchanged has been useful to complete their care tasks. 	
	Execution	Within the development days of the UC2, a training session was carried out in relation to the operating procedures using SIGRUN federated system. This exercise worked with the EMS-MDS proposed by VALKYRIES for standardization of sharing information related to victims in mass casualty	

CO-WP5-12-D01 - Emergency medical services minimum data set (EMS MDS) for sharing information in MCI and disasters: DEMONSTRATION	
	<p>incidents (MCI) and disasters. In this simulation, the participants practised all the steps and roles involved in the different specific operating procedures proposed for attending to victims of a MCI or disaster.</p> <p>At the end of these sessions, all members of the emergency services participating in the exercise were asked to complete a survey. Respondents answered the survey on a voluntary and anonymous basis. Only the institution to which the author belongs is known.</p>
Analysis and results	<p>After analysing the responses, the following results were obtained:</p> <p>KPIs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Data relevance: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 2: Data usefulness: 77,78% (NOT ACHIEVED) <p>PREDOMINANT RESPONSE:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data relevance: QUITE IN AGREEMENT • Data usefulness: TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT
History of corrective measures	
Lessons learned	<p>The subjective KPIs established for the WP5 enablers have compliance criteria such that very positive results (but less than 80% of respondents with a favourable opinion) are considered as non-compliance with the KPI. As these KPIs have been defined in previous stages of the project, they will not be revised at this stage, but will be the subject of lessons learned for other future research projects.</p>
Quality	D: Sufficient adequacy (50-59% KPIs achieved)
End-user feedback	
Result	Successful verification: YES

Table 45 – Results sheet CO.WP5-12-D01

Evidence of implementation and compliance:

See Annex F, section WP5 Preliminary test and UC2 demonstration evidence (evidence 2 and 3, questions 1 and 2)

19.5. CO.WP5-13: Establishing a common federated system for sharing information in emergency response

19.5.1. CO-WP5-13-D01- SIGRUN as an integration reference for facilitating the deployment and response tasks of emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: DEMONSTRATION

CO-WP5-13-D01- SIGRUN as an integration reference for facilitating the deployment and response tasks of emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: DEMONSTRATION			
Description	<p>In the UC2, a set of technological solutions, federated through SIGRUN and integrated into the first responders operating procedures, was used as a sample for the demonstration end evaluation of this enabler through the following verification actions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A questionnaire was developed among the participants of the UC workshops to collect their opinion on the benefits of using the proposed solution, SIGRUN, integrated in their operating procedures (VERIFICATION ACTION #1). • The degree of compliance with some KPIs defined for the evaluation of this VALKYRIES was verified in the UC on the basis of the data stored in the federated SIGRUN system during the simulation (VERIFICATION ACTION #2). • Finally, at the end of the exercise, an online survey was carried out among the participants to collect their opinion on the impact of using SIGRUN integrated in their operating procedures (VERIFICATION ACTION #3). 		
Traceability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Traceability with identified requirements: REQ_COM_T5.2_4, REQ_COM_T5.2_5, REQ_COM_T5.2_6, REQ_COM_T5.2_7, REQ_COM_T5.2_8, REQ_COM_T5.2_9, REQ_COM_T5.2_10, REQ_COM_T5.2_11, REQ_COM_T5.2_12, REQ_COM_T5.2_13, REQ_COM_T5.2_14, REQ_BASE_T5.3_3, REQ_COM_T5.3_4, REQ_COM_T5.3_6, REQ_COM_T5.3_7, REQ_COM_T5.3_8, REQ_COM_T5.3_9, REQ_COM_T5.3_10, REQ_COM_T5.3_11, REQ_COM_T5.3_12, REQ_COM_T5.3_13, REQ_COM_T5.3_14, REQ_COM_T5.3_15, REQ_COM_T5.3_16, REQ_COM_T5.3_17, REQ_COM_T5.3_18, REQ_COM_T5.3_19, REQ_COM_T5.3_20, REQ_COM_T5.3_21, REQ_COM_T5.3_22 • Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-4, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9 		
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
Information exchange facilitation: The perceived improvement in information exchange between services using SIGRUN.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 1: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration

CO-WP5-13-D01- SIGRUN as an integration reference for facilitating the deployment and response tasks of emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: DEMONSTRATION

Task execution efficiency: The perceived improvement in the efficiency of task execution in an MCI using SIGRUN compared to the current situation.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 2: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration
Integration and cooperation: The perceived improvement in integration and cooperation with other services and/or procedures in responding to an MCI using SIGRUN.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 3: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration
Implementation ease: The perceived ease and simplicity of implementing SIGRUN by first responders in an MCI.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 4: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration
First responder well-being: The perceived improvement in the well-being of first responders during their	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 5: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration

CO-WP5-13-D01- SIGRUN as an integration reference for facilitating the deployment and response tasks of emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: DEMONSTRATION

operational tasks in an MCI using SIGRUN.			
Added value in cross-border MCI management: The perceived added value of using SIGRUN for managing and responding to an MCI affecting several communities or countries.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 6: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration
Satisfaction with information content: The overall satisfaction with the content of the information exchanged using SIGRUN.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 7: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration
Satisfaction with the operating procedure: The degree of satisfaction with the operational procedure implemented and based on the capabilities offered by SIGRUN.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 8: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration

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Time to triage: The average time taken to assign triage priorities using SIGRUN.	Time (in seconds) from the victim first approach to the determination of triage priority and immediate actions.	KPI 9: A maximum acceptable average time to assign primary triage priorities: 1,5 min (90 sec).	Demonstration
Triage accuracy: The percentage of correct triage decisions made using SIGRUN.	% (rate calculated by dividing the number of correctly triaged casualties by the total number of triaged casualties, expressed as a percentage).	KPI 10: Minimum 80% of correctly triaged casualties made during the MCI drill using SIGRUN.	Demonstration
Verification action #1	Date and location	Bratislava (Slovakia), 22 June 2023.	
	Participants	Consortium and local partners' experts involved in UC2 previous training tasks.	
	Description	<p>A survey was carried out with questions (4 to 12) on the following aspects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extent to which SIGRUN could facilitate the exchange of information between services. • Extent to which the tested procedure would allow a more efficient execution of assigned tasks in a MCI compared to the current situation. • Opinion on whether this system would facilitate integration and joint work with other services and/or procedures in the response to an MCI • Opinion on the ease and simplicity of implementation by a first responder in a MCI • Opinion on the improvement of the well-being of first responders during their operational tasks in a MCI • Added value to the management and response in a MCI affecting several communities or countries 	

CO-WP5-13-D01- SIGRUN as an integration reference for facilitating the deployment and response tasks of emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: DEMONSTRATION

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overall satisfaction with the content of the information exchanged. <p>Degree of satisfaction with the operational procedure implemented and based on the capabilities offered by SIGRUN.</p>
	Execution	<p>During the UC2 workshop days, an in-person training was conducted on how to respond to mass casualty incidents (MCI) or disasters using the SIGRUN federated system, showcasing various federated tools as examples within a unified common operational picture (COP). Throughout this session, participants engaged in exercises simulating every step and role within the recommended operational methods.</p> <p>Upon concluding these workshops, all attending emergency service members were requested to fill out a survey. This aimed to collect feedback regarding SIGRUN's effectiveness in enhancing logistics, deployment, and medical response procedures by first responders during MCIs or disasters. Respondents answered the survey on a voluntary and anonymous basis. Only the institution to which the author belongs is known.</p>
	Analysis and results	<p>After analysing the responses, the following results were obtained:</p> <p>KPIs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Information exchange facilitation: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 2: Task execution efficiency: 88,89% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 3: Integration and cooperation: 44,44% (NOT ACHIEVED) • KPI 4: Implementation ease: 55,56% (NOT ACHIEVED) • KPI 5: First responder well-being: 88,89% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 6: Added value in cross-border MCI management: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 7: Satisfaction with information content: 77,78% (NOT ACHIEVED) • KPI 8: Satisfaction with the operating procedure: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) <p>PREDOMINANT RESPONSE:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information exchange facilitation: QUITE IN AGREEMENT • Task execution efficiency: TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT • Integration and cooperation: QUITE IN AGREEMENT • Implementation ease: TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT • First responder well-being: QUITE IN AGREEMENT

CO-WP5-13-D01- SIGRUN as an integration reference for facilitating the deployment and response tasks of emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: DEMONSTRATION		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Added value in cross-border MCI management: QUITE IN AGREEMENT • Satisfaction with information content: TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT • Satisfaction with the operating procedure: QUITE IN AGREEMENT
	History of corrective measures	
	Lessons learned	
	Quality	C: High adequacy (60-79% KPIs achieved)
	End-user feedback	
	Result	Successful verification: YES
Verification action #2	Date and location	Stupava (Slovakia), 22 June 2023
	Participants	Bratislava Control Chemical Laboratory (Slovakia), Bratislava Emergency Medical Service (Slovakia), ENVIRO Department for detection of hazardous substances and environmental crime (Slovakia), Bratislava Fire and Rescue System (Slovakia), AREU Agenzia Regionale Emergenza Urgenza (Italy)
	Description	The objective KPIs relating to the triage time and accuracy using SIGRUN were assessed based on the data recorded in this federated platform during the conduct of the UC2 drill.
	Execution	<p>As mentioned above in relation to CO-WP5-7-2-D01, a cross-border MCI exercise was conducted in which various emergency services took on roles essential to emergency management, including first responders, disaster managers, technologists and others. Real-time data was generated and shared by each of these roles.</p> <p>This demonstration was seamlessly integrated with other VALKYRIES tools, using the SIGRUN platform as the basic integration framework, bringing together different technological and software resources to support emergency responders as an example. Throughout the use case, relevant data will be collected to facilitate the planned demonstrations.</p> <p>The identification data and pathology of the drill victims were fictitious.</p> <p>The terminals were previously configured with the associated users. The permissions and users required for the test within SIGRUN were enabled taking into account GRPD issues.</p> <p>Connectivity 4G between applications is required for the evaluation within SIGRUN. The connectivity between the</p>

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		terminals and the SIGRUN platform was verified prior to the test.
	Analysis and results	<p>After analysing the responses, the following results were obtained:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 9: Time to triage (SIGRUN): 69 sec (ACHIEVED) • KPI 10: Triage accuracy (SIGRUN): 90,91% (ACHIEVED) <p>The following results were obtained using the procedures in place before the VALKYRIES proposal:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time to triage threshold: 37,05 sec • Triage accuracy rate: 77,27% <p>The use of SIGRUN does not reduce the time spent on primary triage of MCI victims, but significantly improves the accuracy of triage while facilitating real-time information exchange between all those involved in the response.</p>
	History of corrective measures	
	Lessons learned	
	Quality	A: Maximum adequacy (>90% KPIs achieved)
	End-user feedback	
	Result	Successful verification: YES
Verification action #3	Date and location	Online survey, 22 June 2023 and thereafter.
	Participants	All participants in the UC2 drill.
	Description	<p>Upon concluding UC2, a comprehensive online survey was administered to collect feedback from participants on multiple facets of the exercise. This included their views on the different VALKYRIES tools introduced during the demonstration and their thoughts on the structure and progression of the use case itself</p> <p>Some of these questions (3, 2.8, 18, 2.18, 2.3, 6, 16, 2.6) asked about topics such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The potential of SIGRUN to enhance information sharing between services. • The potential improvement in task efficiency during an MCI with the tested procedure compared to existing practices. • Views on the system's capability to promote integration and collaborative efforts with other services and/or procedures during an MCI response. • Feedback on the system's implementation ease and straightforwardness for a first responder in an MCI. • Perception of the system's impact on enhancing the well-being of first responders during MCI operations.

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		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The added benefit to the handling and response of an MCI affecting multiple communities or nations. • Overall contentment with the nature of the information shared. • Level of satisfaction with the operating procedures deployed, leveraging the features provided by SIGRUN.
	Execution	<p>This evaluation action was carried out in a harmonised way with the other VALKYRIES enablers, within the reference integration implementation provided by the SIGRUN platform, on the same MCI simulation described for VERIFICATION ACTION #2.</p> <p>In this case, the information taken into account for the evaluation of the enabler was collected through the online survey of those responders involved in the MCI simulation. Respondents answered the survey on a voluntary and anonymous basis. Only the institution to which the author belongs is known.</p>
	Analysis and results	<p>After analysing the responses, the following results were obtained:</p> <p>KPIs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Information exchange facilitation: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 2: Task execution efficiency: 87,50% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 3: Integration and cooperation: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 4: Implementation ease: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 5: First responder well-being: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 6: Added value in cross-border MCI management: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 7: Satisfaction with information content: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 8: Satisfaction with the operating procedure: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) <p>PREDOMINANT RESPONSE:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information exchange facilitation: AGREE • Task execution efficiency: STRONGLY AGREE • Integration and cooperation: STRONGLY AGREE • Implementation ease: STRONGLY AGREE • First responder well-being: AGREE • Added value in cross-border MCI management: AGREE • Satisfaction with information content: AGREE • Satisfaction with the operating procedure: STRONGLY AGREE

CO-WP5-13-D01- SIGRUN as an integration reference for facilitating the deployment and response tasks of emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: DEMONSTRATION	
History of corrective measures	
Lessons learned	
Quality	A: Maximum adequacy (>90% KPIs achieved)
End-user feedback	
Result	Successful verification: YES

Table 46 – Results sheet CO.WP5-13-D01

Evidence of implementation and compliance:

See Annex F, section WP5 UC2 demonstration evidence:

- Evidence 2 and 3 (questions 5 to 12)
- Evidence 5

See Annex B2 – VALIDATION QUESTIONNAIRE (EN version)+ (questions 3, 2.8, 18, 2.18, 2.3, 6, 16, 2.6)

19.6. CO.WP5-3: Harmonization of alert and warning procedures in emergency response

19.6.1. CO-WP5-3-D01- Standardisation of basic initial alerting information for emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: DEMONSTRATION

CO-WP5-3-D01- Standardisation of basic initial alerting information for emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: DEMONSTRATION	
Description	<p>VALKYRIES endorses the METHANE model, which was presented in the UK by JESIP through its "Joint Doctrine: the interoperability framework." This model offers a unified method for the quick, clear, and consistent sharing of crucial incident information among emergency services during a mass casualty incident (MCI) or disaster. The METHANE model served as a benchmark for the creation of SIGRUN and the incorporation of the sample software tools. Its application and effectiveness have been assessed in the UC2 demonstrator.</p> <p><i>M/ETHANE. Joint doctrine: the interoperability framework. Edition 2 July 2016. Pg 9. https://www.jesip.org.uk/uploads/resources/JESIP-Joint-Doctrine.pdf</i></p> <p>The assessment of this enabler in the UC2 demonstrator was carried out through the following verification actions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A questionnaire was developed in the UC workdays to collect respondents' opinions on the proposed enabler to sharing initial information regarding the incident when an MCI or disaster is declared (VERIFICATION ACTION #1). • The degree of compliance of the UC implementation with the proposed METHANKE model was verified on the basis of the data stored in the SIGRUN federated system during the UC drill (VERIFICATION ACTION #2).

CO-WP5-3-D01- Standardisation of basic initial alerting information for emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: DEMONSTRATION			
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Finally, an online survey was conducted at the end of the UC drill to collect participants' evaluation of the simulation (VERIFICATION ACTION #3). 		
Traceability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Traceability with identified requirements: REQ_COM_T5.2_6, REQ_COM_T5.2_7, REQ_COM_T5.2_8, REQ_COM_T5.2_11, REQ_COM_T5.2_12, REQ_COM_T5.2_13, REQ_COM_T5.2_14, REQ_BASE_T5.3_3, REQ_COM_T5.3_4, REQ_COM_T5.3_5, REQ_COM_T5.3_7, REQ_COM_T5.3_8, REQ_COM_T5.3_9, REQ_COM_T5.3_10, REQ_COM_T5.3_11, REQ_COM_T5.3_12, REQ_COM_T5.3_13, REQ_COM_T5.3_14, REQ_COM_T5.3_15, REQ_COM_T5.3_16, REQ_COM_T5.3_17, REQ_COM_T5.3_18, REQ_COM_T5.3_20, REQ_COM_T5.3_21 Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-4, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9 		
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
Data relevance: Perceived importance of the data exchanged in the initial alert of a MCI or disaster to facilitate an efficient and effective emergency response.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 1: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration
Data usefulness: The perceived usefulness of the data exchanged during the drill in the initial alert to facilitate an efficient and effective emergency response.	Score from 1 (VERY LOW / NOT AT ALL AGREED) to 5 (VERY HIGH / TOTALLY AGREED).	KPI 2: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration
METHANE UC compliance: The degree of	% (rate calculated by dividing	KPI 3: A result of at least	Demonstration

CO-WP5-3-D01- Standardisation of basic initial alerting information for emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: DEMONSTRATION			
adherence of the incident information shared in the UC to the METHANE model.	the number of correctly shared METHANE data by the total METHANE dataset in the UC, expressed as a percentage).	80% of compliance.	
Verification action #1	Date and location	Bratislava (Slovakia), 22 June 2023.	
	Participants	Consortium and local partners' experts involved in UC2 previous training tasks.	
	Description	<p>A survey was carried out containing questions (3 and 4) related to the following aspects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Criticality of the information transmitted in the initial declaration of an MCI or disaster to increase the effectiveness of the health response and reduce the risk to responders. • Opinion on whether the information provided is appropriate to the needs of EMS in the early stages of an MCI or disaster. 	
	Execution	<p>During the UC working days, a training session was conducted focusing on the operational procedures for dealing with an MCI or disaster using the integrated SIGRUN solution, exemplified through various federated tools under a shared Common Operating Picture (COP). In this training, participants went through and acted out all the steps and roles associated with the proposed operating procedures. Upon concluding the sessions, each participant from the emergency services involved in the training was asked to complete a questionnaire. This was to gather their feedback to assess whether the METHANE approach was considered appropriate for the initial dissemination of critical incident information.</p> <p>Respondents answered the questionnaire on a voluntary and anonymous basis. Only the institution to which the author belongs is known.</p>	
	Analysis and results	<p>After analysing the responses, the following results were obtained:</p> <p>KPIs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Data relevance: 88,89% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 2: Data usefulness: 77,78% (NOT ACHIEVED) <p>PREDOMINANT RESPONSE:</p>	

CO-WP5-3-D01- Standardisation of basic initial alerting information for emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: DEMONSTRATION		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data relevance: QUITE IN AGREEMENT • Data usefulness: TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT
	History of corrective measures	
	Lessons learned	As mentioned above, the subjective KPIs established for the WP5 enablers have compliance criteria such that very positive results (but less than 80% of respondents with a favourable opinion) are considered as non-compliance with the KPI. As these KPIs have been defined in previous stages of the project, they will not be revised at this stage, but will be the subject of lessons learned for other future research projects.
	Quality	D: Sufficient adequacy (50-59% KPIs achieved)
	End-user feedback	
	Result	Successful verification: YES
Verification action #2	Date and location	Stupava (Slovakia), 22 June 2023
	Participants	Bratislava Control Chemical Laboratory (Slovakia), Bratislava Emergency Medical Service (Slovakia), ENVIRO Department for detection of hazardous substances and environmental crime (Slovakia), Bratislava Fire and Rescue System (Slovakia), AREU Agenzia Regionale Emergenza Urgenza (Italy)
	Description	<p>The acronym METHANE defines a dataset related to the incident characteristics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • M: confirmation of whether it is a major incident • E: Exact location • T: Type of incident • H: Active Hazards • A: Recommended access • N: Estimated number of casualties • E: Emergency services present at the scene <p>The degree of compliance with this METHANE model during the UC has been assessed on the basis of the data recorded in SIGRUN during the conduct of UC2 drill.</p>
	Execution	<p>This verification action was performed in a harmonised way with the other VALKYRIES enablers, within the reference integration implementation provided by the SIGRUN platform.</p> <p>A cross-national MCI exercise was carried out with the participation of experts assuming the different roles involved in the emergency response (first responders, disaster managers, technologists, etc.).</p>

CO-WP5-3-D01- Standardisation of basic initial alerting information for emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: DEMONSTRATION

		Through the various tools integrated in SIGRUN, information on the characteristics of the incident was exchanged from the beginning and throughout the exercise. Connectivity 4G between applications is required for the evaluation within SIGRUN. The connectivity between the terminals and the SIGRUN platform was verified prior to the test. The terminals were previously configured with the associated users.
	Analysis and results	After analysing the responses, the following results were obtained: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 3: METHANE UC compliance: 100% The initial incident report and subsequent incident updates were made by completing all the items listed in the METHANE protocol.
	History of corrective measures	
	Lessons learned	
	Quality	A: Maximum adequacy (>90% KPIs achieved)
	End-user feedback	
	Result	Successful verification: YES
Verification action #3	Date and location	Online survey, 22 June 2023 and thereafter.
	Participants	All participants in the UC2 drill.
	Description	An online questionnaire was used to gather feedback from participants on various facets of UC2 after its completion. These opinions related not only to the various enablers of VALKYRIES presented in the demonstration, but also to the structuring and execution of the use case itself. Some of these questions (12, 13) asked about topics such as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The importance of the information provided in the initial announcement of an MCI or disaster in improving the effectiveness of the health care response and minimising the risks to first responders. • Views on whether the information provided meets the early needs of Emergency Services during an MCI or disaster.
	Execution	This assessment was carried out in synchrony with the other VALKYRIES enablers, based on the MCI simulation described for VERIFICATION ACTION 2, using the SIGRUN platform as the reference integration. For this assessment, enabler data were collected from the online survey completed by participants in the MCI simulation.

CO-WP5-3-D01- Standardisation of basic initial alerting information for emergency services in MCI and disasters in the EU: DEMONSTRATION	
	Participants completed the survey voluntarily and anonymously, identifying only their institution.
Analysis and results	After analysing the responses, the following results were obtained: KPIs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: Data relevance: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 2: Data usefulness: 100,00% (ACHIEVED) PREDOMINANT RESPONSE: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data relevance: STRONGLY AGREE • Data usefulness: STRONGLY AGREE
History of corrective measures	
Lessons learned	
Quality	A: Maximum adequacy (>90% KPIs achieved)
End-user feedback	
Result	Successful verification: YES

Table 47 – Results sheet CO.WP5-3-D01

Evidence of implementation and compliance:

See Annex F, section WP5 UC2 demonstration evidence:

- Evidence 2 and 3 (questions 3 and 4)
- Evidence 7

See Annex B2 – VALIDATION QUESTIONNAIRE (EN version) (questions 12 and 13)

19.7. WP5 UC2 demonstration evidence

19.7.1. Evidence 1 UC2 WP5: Survey 1

UC2 Demonstration

- E.WPS-1: VALKYRIES COLLABORATIVE GLOSSARY FOR EMERGENCY RESPONSE PLANNING, PREPAREDNESS AND EXECUTION.
- E.WPS-3: UNIFICATION OF TRIAGE PRIORITY CODING AND TAGGING IN MCI AND DISASTERS AT EU LEVEL
- E.WPS-4: TASSICA 3 STANDARDISED TRIAGE CARD TO ENSURE INTEROPERABILITY, EQUITY, VICTIMS INFORMATION REGISTER AND TRACEABILITY IN MCI AND DISASTERS.

UNIFICATION OF TERMINOLOGY AND CRITERIA IN MCI AND DISASTERS (E.WPS-1, E.WPS-3)

1- Do you think it is important that all emergency services use the same terminology for planning and responding against MCI and disasters?

TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT	QUITE IN AGREEMENT	MODERATELY AGREE	LITTLE AGREEMENT	NOT AT ALL IN AGREEMENT
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2- Do you think it is important that all emergency medical services use the same classification to designate the triage priority of victims in MCI and disasters?

TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT	QUITE IN AGREEMENT	MODERATELY AGREE	LITTLE AGREEMENT	NOT AT ALL IN AGREEMENT
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3- Do you agree with the allocation of colours for the different priorities used in the test?

TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT	QUITE IN AGREEMENT	MODERATELY AGREE	LITTLE AGREEMENT	NOT AT ALL IN AGREEMENT
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4- Do you think that the use of the same classification and colour coding throughout the European Union would facilitate the joint work of emergency medical services in cross-border MCI?

TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT	QUITE IN AGREEMENT	MODERATELY AGREE	LITTLE AGREEMENT	NOT AT ALL IN AGREEMENT
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USING A STANDARDISED TRIAGE CARD (E.WPS-4)

5- To what extent do you think that the TASSICA card helps to homogenise the triage priorities assigned to victims in an MCI?

TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT	QUITE IN AGREEMENT	MODERATELY AGREE	LITTLE AGREEMENT	NOT AT ALL IN AGREEMENT
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6- To what extent do you think that the TASSICA card helps you to decide which life-saving gestures are appropriate for a given victim in a MCI?

TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT	QUITE IN AGREEMENT	MODERATELY AGREE	LITTLE AGREEMENT	NOT AT ALL IN AGREEMENT
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VALKYRIES

7- To what extent do you think the TASSICA triage card helps to ensure the traceability of a victim at the scene of an MCI?

TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT	QUITE IN AGREEMENT	MODERATELY AGREE	LITTLE AGREEMENT	NOT AT ALL IN AGREEMENT
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8- To what extent do you think the TASSICA triage card facilitates the recording of victims' health information in the response to a MCI?

TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT	QUITE IN AGREEMENT	MODERATELY AGREE	LITTLE AGREEMENT	NOT AT ALL IN AGREEMENT
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OVERALL ASSESSMENT

9- To what extent do you think that the TASSICA card reduces the stress of healthcare personnel in decision-making in the triage of victims in a MCI?

TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT	QUITE IN AGREEMENT	MODERATELY AGREE	LITTLE AGREEMENT	NOT AT ALL IN AGREEMENT
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10- Do you think that the use of the same standardised triage card throughout the European Union would facilitate the joint work of emergency medical services in cross-border MCI?

TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT	QUITE IN AGREEMENT	MODERATELY AGREE	LITTLE AGREEMENT	NOT AT ALL IN AGREEMENT
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11- To what extent do you think that the TASSICA card allows you to perform your tasks more efficiently in a MCI compared to other cards?

VERY HIGH	HIGH	MODERATE	UNDER	VERY LOW
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12- How satisfied are you overall with the TASSICA triage card you have used?

VERY HIGH	HIGH	MODERATE	UNDER	VERY LOW
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COMMENTS, ASSESSMENTS, SUGGESTIONS:

INSTITUTION: EMIS BRATISLAVA
DATE: 22.6.2023

Figure 45 – Evidence 1 UC2 WP5: Survey 1

19.7.2. Evidence 2 UC2 WP5: Survey 2

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UC2 Demonstration

- E.WPS-2: EU STRUCTURED REPOSITORY OF EMERGENCY RESPONSE PLANS
- E.WPS-5: EMERGENCY MEDICAL SERVICES MINIMUM VICTIM DATA SET (EMV MDS) FOR SHARING INFORMATION IN MCI AND DISASTERS
- E.WPS-9: STANDARDISATION OF BASIC INITIAL ALERTING INFORMATION FOR EMERGENCY SERVICES IN MCI AND DISASTERS IN THE EU.
- E.WPS-6: SGRUN AS AN INTEGRATION REFERENCE FOR FACILITATING THE DEPLOYMENT AND RESPONSE TASKS OF EMERGENCY SERVICES IN MCI AND DISASTERS IN THE EU.

MINIMUM DATA SET (E.WPS-5)

1- Do you think that the data transmitted in the trial are appropriate for the proper management of victims by an emergency health service in MCI or disasters?

TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT	QUITE IN AGREEMENT	MODERATELY AGREE	LITTLE AGREEMENT	NOT AT ALL IN AGREEMENT
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2- Has the data exchanged helped you to complete your care tasks?

TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT	QUITE IN AGREEMENT	MODERATELY AGREE	LITTLE AGREEMENT	NOT AT ALL IN AGREEMENT
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INITIAL METHANE ALERT (E.WPS-7)

3- Do you believe that the information conveyed in the initial declaration of an MCI or disaster is critical to increase the effectiveness of the health response and to reduce the risk to responders?

TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT	QUITE IN AGREEMENT	MODERATELY AGREE	LITTLE AGREEMENT	NOT AT ALL IN AGREEMENT
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4- Do you think that the information conveyed in the initial incident statement test is appropriate for the needs of an emergency service in the first moments of an MCI or disaster?

TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT	QUITE IN AGREEMENT	MODERATELY AGREE	LITTLE AGREEMENT	NOT AT ALL IN AGREEMENT
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VALKYRIES INFORMATION EXCHANGE PROCEDURE (E.WPS-2, E.WPS-6)

5- To what extent do you think that the proposed solution could facilitate the exchange of information between the different health services involved in the response to a MCI?

TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT	QUITE IN AGREEMENT	MODERATELY AGREE	LITTLE AGREEMENT	NOT AT ALL IN AGREEMENT
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6- To what extent do you think that the tested procedure would allow you to perform your tasks more efficiently in a MCI compared to the current situation?

TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT	QUITE IN AGREEMENT	MODERATELY AGREE	LITTLE AGREEMENT	NOT AT ALL IN AGREEMENT
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VALKYRIES

7- Do you think that the tested procedure would facilitate integration and joint work with other services and/or procedures in the response to a MCI?

TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT	QUITE IN AGREEMENT	MODERATELY AGREE	LITTLE AGREEMENT	NOT AT ALL IN AGREEMENT
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8- To what extent do you think that the tested procedure is easy and simple to apply by a first responder in a MCI?

TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT	QUITE IN AGREEMENT	MODERATELY AGREE	LITTLE AGREEMENT	NOT AT ALL IN AGREEMENT
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OVERALL ASSESSMENT

9- Do you think that the proposed solution would significantly improve the well-being of health first responders during their operational tasks in a MCI?

TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT	QUITE IN AGREEMENT	MODERATELY AGREE	LITTLE AGREEMENT	NOT AT ALL IN AGREEMENT
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10- Do you think that the proposed solution could bring added value to the management and response in MCI affecting several communities or several countries?

TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT	QUITE IN AGREEMENT	MODERATELY AGREE	LITTLE AGREEMENT	NOT AT ALL IN AGREEMENT
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11- What is your overall level of satisfaction with the CONTENT (DATA) that has been exchanged in the tested MCI response exercise?

VERY HIGH	HIGH	MODERATE	UNDER	VERY LOW
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12- What is your overall level of satisfaction with the INFORMATION EXCHANGE PROCEDURE that has been tested?

VERY HIGH	HIGH	MODERATE	UNDER	VERY LOW
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COMMENTS, EVALUATIONS, SUGGESTIONS:

INSTITUTION:
DATE: 20.06.2023

Figure 46 – Evidence 2 UC2 WP5: Survey 2

19.7.3. Evidence 3 and 4 UC2 WP5: Surveys datasheets

Evidence 3
UC2 WP5

Evidence 4
UC2 WP5

22/06/2023 UC2. BRATISLAVA, SLOVAKIA. WP5 SURVEY 1

Questions	FIRST RESPONDERS										NOT AT ALL IN AGREEMENT	LITTLE AGREEMENT	MODERATELY AGREE	QUITE IN AGREEMENT	TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT	% POSITIVE (4+5)	PREDOMINANT VALUE
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10							
1	5	5	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	10,00%	90,00%	TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT	
2	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	100,00%	TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT	
3	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	4	4	5	0,00%	0,00%	30,00%	70,00%	100,00%	TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT	
4	5	4	5	4	4	5	5	5	4	5	0,00%	0,00%	40,00%	60,00%	100,00%	TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT	
5	3	3	4	4	5	4	5	4	5	4	0,00%	0,00%	20,00%	40,00%	80,00%	QUITE IN AGREEMENT	
6	2	5	4	5	5	4	3	5	5	5	0,00%	10,00%	20,00%	60,00%	80,00%	TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT	
7	5	5	5	5	4	5	4	4	5	5	0,00%	0,00%	30,00%	70,00%	100,00%	TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT	
8	5	4	4	5	4	3	3	4	5	5	0,00%	0,00%	20,00%	40,00%	80,00%	TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT	
9	5	4	4	4	4	4	3	4	5	4	0,00%	0,00%	70,00%	20,00%	90,00%	QUITE IN AGREEMENT	
10	3	4	4	4	3	5	5	5	4	5	0,00%	0,00%	40,00%	40,00%	80,00%	QUITE IN AGREEMENT	
11	2	3	3	4	4	4	3	5	5	5	VERY LOW	LOW	MODERATE	VERY HIGH	% POSITIVE	PREDOMINANT VALUE	
12	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	5	5	0,00%	10,00%	30,00%	30,00%	60,00%	HIGH	
	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	5	5	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	20,00%	100,00%	HIGH	

22/06/2023 UC2. BRATISLAVA, SLOVAKIA. WP5 SURVEY 2

Questions	RESPONDERS										NOT AT ALL IN AGREEMENT	LITTLE AGREEMENT	MODERATELY AGREE	QUITE IN AGREEMENT	TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT	% POSITIVE (4+5)	PREDOMINANT VALUE
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10							
1	4	4	4	5	5	4	5	4	5	5	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	55,56%	44,44%	QUITE IN AGREEMENT	
2	2	4	4	4	5	3	5	5	5	5	0,00%	11,11%	11,11%	33,33%	44,44%	TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT	
3	4	4	5	5	5	3	4	4	5	5	0,00%	0,00%	11,11%	44,44%	88,89%	QUITE IN AGREEMENT	
4	3	3	4	4	4	5	5	5	5	5	0,00%	0,00%	22,22%	33,33%	77,78%	TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT	
5	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	5	5	5	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	22,22%	100,00%	QUITE IN AGREEMENT	
6	4	5	5	4	4	3	5	5	5	5	0,00%	11,11%	11,11%	33,33%	55,56%	TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT	
7	4	3	3	2	3	3	5	5	5	5	0,00%	11,11%	44,44%	11,11%	33,33%	QUITE IN AGREEMENT	
8	4	4	3	2	3	2	5	5	5	5	0,00%	22,22%	22,22%	33,33%	55,56%	TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT	
9	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	5	4	5	0,00%	0,00%	11,11%	77,78%	88,89%	QUITE IN AGREEMENT	
10	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	5	4	5	0,00%	0,00%	77,78%	22,22%	100,00%	QUITE IN AGREEMENT	
11	4	3	4	3	5	4	5	5	5	5	VERY LOW	LOW	MODERATE	VERY HIGH	% POSITIVE	PREDOMINANT VALUE	
12	4	4	4	4	5	4	4	5	5	5	0,00%	0,00%	33,33%	44,44%	77,78%	TOTALLY IN AGREEMENT	
	4	4	4	4	5	4	4	5	5	5	0,00%	0,00%	66,67%	33,33%	100,00%	QUITE IN AGREEMENT	

Figure 47 – Evidence 3 and 4 UC2 WP5: Surveys datasheets

19.7.4. Evidence 5 UC2 WP5: Victims datasheet

VALKYRIES UC 2. WP5 DATA SHEET. STUPAVA, SLOVAKIA. 22/06/2023.

INCIDENT	ID PAX	1T BENCHMARK	ID SIGRUN	1T SIGRUN	ID SLO USUAL	1T SLO USUAL	1T TIME SLO USUAL	ID IT USUAL	1T IT USUAL	1T TIME IT USUAL	ID TASSICA 3	1T TASSICA 3	TIME TASSICA 3	
Toxic Spill	1	1	TASS0049	2	1	2	45	1	2	27	326	1	24	
Toxic Spill	2	1	TASS0032	1	2	1	34	2	1	26	320	1	29	
Toxic Spill	8	2	TASS0052	2	8	3	39	8	2	25	319	2	32	
Toxic Spill	9	2	TASS0058	2	9	2	26	9	2	22	295	2	50	
Toxic Spill	10	2	TASS0070	2	10	2	77	10	2	28	317	2	45	
Toxic Spill	11	3	TASS0061	3	11	3	35	11	3	82	316	3	33	
Toxic Spill	15	3	TASS0067	3	15	3	37	15	3	22	296	3	7	
Toxic Spill	18	3	TASS0047	3	18	2	55	18	2	41	318	3	24	
Toxic Spill	19	3	TASS0026	3	19	3	50	19	3	36	297	3	7	
Toxic Spill	21	0	TASS0055	0	21	0	15	21	0	24	298	0	12	
Toxic Spill	23	0	TASS0064	0	23	0	40	23	0	29	315	0	14	
											90,91% ACCURACY	32,91 TIME (sec)	100,00% ACCURACY	25,18 TIME (sec)

VALKYRIES UC 2. WP5 SIGRUN times estimation.

USER	412	AREU
INITIAL TIME	12:47	12:48
END TIME	12:53	12:52
AVERAGE TIME	0:01:30	0:00:48
TOTAL AVERAGE	0:01:09	

77,27% ACCURACY AVERAGE
37,05 TIME (sec) AVERAGE

Figure 48 – Evidence 5 UC2 WP5: Victims datasheet

19.7.5. Evidence 6 UC2 WP5: Triage compliance with VALKYRIES proposal

Label	Last Updated	Gender	Age / Age Group	Assistance Status	AT	ET	Main Pathology	Transport	Destination	Location	Triage History	Incident	By Unit	By Staff
TASS0047 []	June 22, 2023, 1:05 p.m. 3 months ago	F	38 / ADULT	In destination	MINOR	MINOR	TRAUMA [upper extremity]	U102	FN TT	→	→	Toxic Spill	AREU - EMS	
TASS0067 []	June 22, 2023, 1:05 p.m. 3 months ago	M	49 / ADULT	In destination	MINOR	DELAYED	TRAUMA [thorax]	U110	UNB Kramare	→	→	Toxic Spill		RZP 2 AMB 1 412
TASS0052 []	June 22, 2023, 1:05 p.m. 3 months ago	M	60 / ADULT	In destination	DELAYED	DELAYED	BURNS [thorax, abdomen/pelvis, lower extremity]		UNB Ruzinov	→	→	Toxic Spill	AREU - EMS	
TASS0026 []	June 22, 2023, 1:05 p.m. 3 months ago	F	55 / ADULT	In destination	MINOR	MINOR	TRAUMA	U102	FNTT	→	→	Toxic Spill	AREU - EMS	
TASS0055 []	June 22, 2023, 1:11 p.m. 3 months ago	F	- / ELDER	Evacuated	DECEASED	DECEASED		CCHL Van	SCM	→	→	Toxic Spill		RZP 2 AMB 1 412
TASS0049 []	June 22, 2023, 1:05 p.m. 3 months ago	M	61 / ELDER	In destination	DELAYED	IMMEDIATE	BURNS [head/neck]	U127	UNB Ruzinov	→	→	Toxic Spill		RZP 2 AMB 1 412
TASS0032 []	June 22, 2023, 12:56 p.m. 3 months ago	M	25 / ADULT	In destination	IMMEDIATE	IMMEDIATE	BURNS [head/neck, abdomen/pelvis, lower extremity]	K01	UNB Ruzinov	→	→	Toxic Spill		RZP 2 AMB 1 412
TASS0061 []	June 22, 2023, 1:05 p.m. 3 months ago	F	81 / ADULT	In destination	MINOR	MINOR	TRAUMA [head/neck]	U121	UNB Kramare	→	→	Toxic Spill	AREU - EMS	
TASS0064 []	June 22, 2023, 12:53 p.m. 3 months ago	M	- / ADULT	Waiting for assistance	DECEASED	DECEASED				→	→	Toxic Spill	AREU - EMS	
TASS0070 []	June 22, 2023, 1:04 p.m. 3 months ago	F	17 / -	In destination	DELAYED	DELAYED	TRAUMA [lower extremity]	U125	FN TT	→	→	Toxic Spill	AREU - EMS	
TASS0058 []	June 22, 2023, 12:54 p.m. 3 months ago	M	- / ELDER	In destination	DELAYED	DELAYED	TRAUMA [lower extremity]	U101	UNB Kramare	→	→	Toxic Spill		RZP 2 AMB 1 412

Figure 49 – Evidence 6 UC2 WP5: Triage compliance with VALKYRIES proposal

19.7.6. Evidence 7 UC2 WP5: METHANE compliance

Figure 50 – Evidence 7 UC2 WP5: METHANE compliance

19.7.7. Images UC2 WP5

Figure 51 – Images UC2 related to WP5

20. Annex G – WP6 Result sheets Opportunities

20.2. CO.WP6.2: Use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data

20.2.1. CO-WP6-2-T01- Use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data

CO-WP6-1-T01- Use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data			
Description	Verify that the data stored in the SIGRUN platform is correctly stored, applying cryptographic mechanisms to ensure that only authorized access can access it. Also, the data transmitted over the network is secure.		
Location/Participants	UMU		
Requirements	REQ_COM_T6.1_1		
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
Data stored in the SIGRUN platform is encrypted, as well as data transmitted over the network.	100% of data transferred and stored in the SIGRUN platform is encrypted, except for the cases defined in the premises and limitations	KPI 1: Information available: Yes / No (Available = success) KPI 2: data transfer protocol configured to use encrypted communications: encryption setting KPI 3: data is stored with in an encrypted format: encryption setting	Analysis
	Description	Data encrypted	
	Participants	UMU	
	Location	Remotely	
	Execution	To carry out this demonstration, SIGRUN has been configured to store encrypted data and to exchange encrypted data over the network, thus ensuring that the data is protected. SIGRUN works by default with https, which means that its exchanges are encrypted, and the database used by SIGRUN has the capacity to encrypt the data so that it remains confidential in the event of an information leak.	
Analysis and results	<i>The results obtained are that the information is 100% available and that the data is exchanged encrypted over the network thanks to https. On the other hand, for the simulations, the option of encrypting the data in the database has been highlighted in order to speed up its operation, but this option can be activated at any time.</i>		

CO-WP6-1-T01- Use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data	
	History of corrective measures
	Lessons learned <i>We have learned that confidentiality of data is a highly important aspect, especially when dealing with medical issues, which is why data encryption mechanisms have been implemented.</i>
	Quality A
	End-user feedback No end user feedback.
	Result YES

Table 48 – Results sheet CO-WP6-1-T01

20.3. CO.WP6.7: Use of Virtual Operations Support Teams (VOSTs)

CO-WP6-7-T01- Use of Virtual Operation Support Teams (VOSTs)

CO-WP6-7-T01- Use of Virtual Operations Support Teams (VOSTs)			
Description	<p>VALKYRIES endorses the VOST model. It is supposed existence such team of experts and messages created by them. The content of the messages is not the subject of the research as well as the way how it is provided to the responders and C2. Particular messages were prepared in advance. Principle was presented during briefing to all of the exercise participants, as well as evaluation process/form.</p> <p>The assessment of this opportunity in the UC2 demonstrator was carried out through the following verification actions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The degree of compliance of the UC implementation with the proposed VOST model was verified on the basis of the data stored in the SIGRUN federated system during the UC exercise (VERIFICATION ACTION #1). • Finally, an online survey was conducted at the end of the UC exercise to collect participants' evaluation of the simulation (VERIFICATION ACTION #2). 		
Traceability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Traceability with identified requirements: REQ_BASE_T6.5_1; REQ_COM_T6.5_3; REQ_COM_T6.5_4 • Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives: VALK-OBJ-1, VALK-OBJ-2, VALK-OBJ-3, VALK-OBJ-4, VALK-OBJ-5, VALK-OBJ-6, VALK-OBJ-7, VALK-OBJ-8, VALK-OBJ-9 		
ME	MR	KPI	Verification method
Potential exploitation of information shared on social media during an MCI or	Percentage of agreement	KPI 1: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.	Demonstration

CO-WP6-7-T01- Use of Virtual Operations Support Teams (VOSTs)

<p>disaster to facilitate an effective and efficient emergency response for strategic and tactical level.</p>			
<p>Potential exploitation of information shared on social media during an MCI or disaster to facilitate an effective and efficient emergency response for operational level.</p>	<p>Percentage of agreement</p>	<p>KPI 2: A subjective favourable perception of at least 80% by stakeholders.</p>	<p>Demonstration</p>
<p>Degree of consistency between information from VOST messages and that presented by the system.</p>	<p>% (rate calculated by dividing the number of correctly shared data by the total).</p>	<p>KPI 3: A result of at least 80% of compliance.</p>	<p>Demonstration</p>
<p>Verification action #1</p>	<p>Date and location</p>	<p>Stupava (Slovakia), 22 June 2023</p>	
	<p>Participants</p>	<p>Control Chemical Laboratory (Slovakia), Bratislava Emergency Medical Service (Slovakia), ENVIRO Police Department for detection of hazardous substances and environmental crime (Slovakia), Bratislava Fire and Rescue System (Slovakia), AREU Agenzia Regionale Emergenza Urgenza (Italy)</p>	
	<p>Description</p>	<p>Predefined VOST message provided to C2.</p>	
	<p>Execution</p>	<p>Content from predefined VOST message visualised in the tool (GLOBAL COP).</p>	
	<p>Analysis and results</p>	<p>Course of the exercise demonstrated ability of the system to provide required information to related personnel (YES/NO).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 3: VOST UC compliance: 100% <p>Required information was presented in optimal way.</p>	

CO-WP6-7-T01- Use of Virtual Operations Support Teams (VOSTs)		
	History of corrective measures	
	Lessons learned	
	Quality	A: Maximum adequacy (>90% KPIs achieved)
	End-user feedback	
	Result	Successful verification: YES
Verification action #2	Date and location	Online survey, 22 June 2023 and thereafter.
	Participants	All participants in the UC2 exercise.
	Description	An online questionnaire was used to gather feedback from UC2 participants: To what extent do you agree or disagree that the VOST represents potential to improve response action on strategic and tactical level? To what extent do you agree or disagree that the VOST represents potential to improve response action on operational level?
	Execution	Questionnaire fulfilled by the UC2 exercise participants.
	Analysis and results	After analysing the responses, the following results were obtained: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KPI 1: 92,50% (ACHIEVED) • KPI 2: 90,00% (ACHIEVED)
	History of corrective measures	
	Lessons learned	
	Quality	A: Maximum adequacy (>90% KPIs achieved)
	End-user feedback	
	Result	Successful verification: YES

Table 49 – Results sheet CO-WP6-7-T01

21. Annex H – Selected pictures from UC2 execution; Evidence - Presentations, Screenshots from the exercises and data in SIGRUN platform for the particular use case, questionnaires, movies, photos etc.

Figure 52 – Selected pictures from UC2

21.2. Screenshots of the Applications for UC2

For the UC2 scenario the entire dataset was centralized on SIGRUN. At the very beginning of the incident, the operator will be able to create a new incident. For UC2 the incident is typed such as Toxic Spill. Thus, a new tab on iSafety will be created named as IN/0000005. Many fields shall be filled to provide as many information as possible for first responders to increase the agility and feasibility of the solution. iSafety is performed as an emergency tool ready to execute and provide response for the victims.

Likewise, the application it is controlled by the Date and Time, which is stored on the system furthermore fields like: Location, Information and Status of the incident as well as resources like Mission and Assets may be assigned.

Figure 53 – iSafety event screenshot

As the incident progresses, more missions and unit deployments are reported. The following picture grant an overall picture to provide a global vision of the incident. This content shall be a basic in a multi casualty emergency incident. The operator will be able to deploy a list of Missions within the Incident. Elements such as Units, Assets (vehicles), Locations, Date and Time are related to the Mission. At last but not least, element status column provides the behaviour of each mission and assigned resources. It will be well performed situation in terms of decision-making and diligence.

Figure 54 – iSafety unit element control screenshot

This tool is called GLOBAL COP and is strictly synchronized with SIGRUN. It is the application in charge for the incident visualization. The entire dataset gathered on SIGRUN will be analysed and treated over this panel. The user will manage any data regarding Geolocation, Vehicle deployment (Assets) and Medical Support. Due to the incident it is categorized as CBRN the resources deployed will be aligned to response and provide as many assets as need it.

Figure 55 – GLOBAL COP

In the course of the incident, any measures to mitigate the effects of the chemical incident will be represented on the dashboard. New missions will be filled on the application.

Figure 56 – GLOBAL COP main window

One of the GLOBAL COP mission is report in terms of metrics about the level of complexity for health data. The following UC2 dashboard in the early stage of the incident inform that there is a Toxic Spill mission active with one resource on route. It provides a general dataset of medical information useful for medical resources.

Figure 57 – GLOBAL COP Incidents window

Next, going into deep the medical dashboard for UC2 is deploying an application for digitalizing triage process. Any victim listed on SIGRUN are going to be carefully treated. For UC2, on the beginning two individuals has been filled such as: TASS0058 and TASS0061. First responders has categorized such as DELAYED and MINOR status on the system.

Figure 58 – GLOBAL COP Victims window

During next period of time new victims are listed on the system.

Figure 59 – GLOBAL COP Victims window progress

This is the Victims tab on the GLOBAL COP app. labelling the victims in the table. Will be classified by time, gender, age, assistance status, AT (Assistance Triage), ET (Evacuation Triage), Main Pathology (assigned to ET), Transport, Destination, Location, Triage History (if applies), Incident, By Unit and By Staff.

Label	Last Updated	Gender	Age / Age Group	Assistance Status	AT	ET	Main Pathology	Transport	Destination	Location	Triage History	Incident	By Unit	By Staff
TASS0026 [1]	June 22, 2023, 12:52 p.m. 4 seconds ago	M	- / ADULT	Waiting for assistance	MINOR						→	→	Toxic Spill AREU - EMS	
TASS0055 [1]	June 22, 2023, 12:52 p.m. 20 seconds ago	F	- / ELDER	Waiting for assistance	DECEASED						→	→	Toxic Spill AREU - EMS	RZP 2 AMB 1 412
TASS0052 [1]	June 22, 2023, 12:51 p.m. 52 seconds ago	M	- / ADULT	Waiting for assistance	DECEASED						→	→	Toxic Spill AREU - EMS	
TASS0058 [1]	June 22, 2023, 12:51 p.m. 4 minutes ago	M	- / ELDER	Waiting for assistance	DECEASED	DECEASED	TRAUMA [lower extremity]				→	→	Toxic Spill AREU - EMS	RZP 2 AMB 1 412
TASS0049 [1]	June 22, 2023, 12:51 p.m. 4 minutes ago	M	- / ELDER	Waiting for assistance	DECEASED						→	→	Toxic Spill AREU - EMS	RZP 2 AMB 1 412
TASS0070 [1]	June 22, 2023, 12:50 p.m. 2 minutes ago	F	- / -	Waiting for assistance	DECEASED						→	→	Toxic Spill AREU - EMS	
TASS0047 [1]	June 22, 2023, 12:50 p.m. 2 minutes ago	F	- / -	Waiting for assistance	MINOR						→	→	Toxic Spill AREU - EMS	
TASS0032 [1]	June 22, 2023, 12:49 p.m. 2 minutes ago	M	- / ADULT	Waiting for assistance	IMMEDIATE						→	→	Toxic Spill AREU - EMS	RZP 2 AMB 1 412
TASS0061 [1]	June 22, 2023, 12:47 p.m. 4 minutes ago	F	- / ADULT	Waiting for assistance	MINOR						→	→	Toxic Spill AREU - EMS	

Figure 60 – GLOBAL COP Victims list

Figure 61 – Exercise MAGIC CLOUD – Demonstration of UC2